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**Rumo à conformação e projeto virtuais: modelação
de materiais baseada em dados por técnicas ML e
restrições baseadas na física**

Towards virtual forming and design: data-driven material
modelling using Machine Learning techniques and physics-
based constraints

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Towards virtual forming and design: data-driven material modelling using Machine Learning techniques and physics-based constraints

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Palavras-chave

Redes Neurais Recorrentes, Método dos Campos Virtuais, Treino Indirecto, Modelo Constitutivo Baseado em Dados, Elastoplasticidade, Restrições Baseadas em Física

Resumo

A análise por elementos finitos (FEA) revolucionou a área da engenharia através da virtualização do design de produto, permitindo reduzir o tempo de desenvolvimento e custos relacionados com a prototipagem física. A importância crescente da FEA também criou a necessidade de se desenvolver modelos de materiais mais precisos. Os modelos constitutivos, embora amplamente disponíveis em *softwares* comerciais de simulação FEA, não são soluções prontas a usar já que a sua qualidade depende de um procedimento de identificação inversa de parâmetros. Os métodos clássicos de caracterização de materiais e de identificação de parâmetros baseiam-se em experiências simples, incapazes de capturar trajetórias de deformação complexas tais como as que se observam em processos de conformação de chapas metálicas. Como tal, para calibrar modelos mais avançados são necessários inúmeros testes de modo a obter bases de dados experimentais suficientemente abrangentes, tornando o processo dispendioso e demorado. O conceito de Material Testing 2.0 (MT2.0) mudou o paradigma na área da caracterização de materiais recorrendo a técnicas de correlação de imagem digital (DIC) para capturar dados de comportamento do material na totalidade do provete de teste. Isto permitiu o desenvolvimento de novos provetes heterogéneos capazes de fornecer dados mais ricos sobre o comportamento do material, reduzindo o número de testes necessários para a calibração dos modelos. Apesar destes avanços, os modelos constitutivos fenomenológicos continuam limitados pela sua formulação explícita, a qual é naturalmente tendenciosa devido às simplificações introduzidas por suposições tomadas no seu desenvolvimento.

Aliadas à filosofia MT2.0, as Redes Neurais Artificiais (ANNs) têm o potencial de liderar uma mudança de paradigma no campo da modelação constitutiva. Além da eficiência computacional que oferecem e da fácil integração com *solvers* FEA, as ANNs apresentam a vantagem principal de aproveitar a elevada densidade de dados DIC para capturar o comportamento do material baseadas puramente nos mesmos, evitando postulados sobre formulações explícitas e, conseqüentemente a necessidade de identificação de parâmetros. No entanto, as abordagens mais comuns neste campo utilizam conjuntos de dados rotulados com base em variáveis impossíveis de obter experimentalmente. Apesar de todas estas vantagens, as ANNs são modelos com um elevado número de parâmetros internos e, portanto, difíceis de interpretar. A grande variedade de hiperparâmetros também as torna difíceis de configurar e treinar. A precisão final dos modelos baseados em ANNs depende fortemente da quantidade e qualidade dos dados de treino, que em certos casos poderão ser caros de obter. As ANNs

também apresentam dificuldades em obter soluções fisicamente consistentes, a menos que algum conhecimento físico do problema lhes seja fornecido, especialmente nos casos em que se utilizam conjuntos de dados limitados.

Esta tese contribui para o campo da modelação constitutiva através da proposta de uma metodologia disruptiva que acopla Redes Neurais Recorrentes (RNNs) com o Método dos Campos Virtuais (VFM) para capturar, puramente através de dados, o comportamento elastoplástico de metais. O método baseia-se exclusivamente em dados de variáveis experimentalmente mensuráveis, aproveitando de forma eficaz a informação disponível em ensaios DIC para treinar indiretamente as RNNs. A abordagem é também computacionalmente eficiente, uma vez que não recorre a FEA para cálculos adicionais. A consistência física é garantida com a previsão da matriz de rigidez tangente do material e a termos de penalidade adicionados à função-custo, baseados na física. São também propostas novas metodologias de validação baseadas em Indicadores de Desempenho Chave (KPI) e experiências baseadas em testes heterogêneos para melhor avaliar a precisão do modelo, para além das métricas de erro padrão. Os resultados finais mostram dinâmicas de treino estáveis resultando em modelos com boa precisão, dependendo do número e da natureza dos campos virtuais utilizados. Em geral, os modelos apresentam uma resposta de acordo com a referência, registando erros baixos comparados com a magnitude geral das tensões. Quando avaliados com dados provenientes de diferentes provetes heterogêneos, verifica-se que alguma capacidade de extrapolação é garantida, alcançando-se também uma correta reconstrução da força global, indicando soluções fisicamente consistentes.

Os impactos resultantes desta investigação provêm do aumento da eficiência computacional obtida através do VFM, da melhoria da precisão do modelo obtida com a aprendizagem baseada em dados, conduzindo a simulações FEA mais fiáveis. É também conseguida uma utilização mais eficiente dos conjuntos de dados DIC por intermédio das ANNs, reduzindo o número de testes experimentais necessários para a caracterização de materiais e ultrapassando a necessidade de identificação de parâmetros. Tudo isto traduz-se, em suma, à redução do tempo e dos custos relacionados com o processo de desenvolvimento de produto.

Keywords

Recurrent Neural Networks, Virtual Fields Method, Indirect training, Data-driven Constitutive Models, Elastoplasticity, Physics-based Constraints

Abstract

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) revolutionized the engineering field virtualizing the product design to reduce the development time and costs of physical prototypes. The growing importance of FEA also increased the need for accurate material models. Although widely available in commercial FEA simulation packages, constitutive models are not ready-made solutions and their quality depends on an accurate inverse parameter identification procedure. Classical methods for material characterization and parameter identification rely on simplified experiments unable to capture complex strain paths observed in sheet metal forming processes. As such, advanced models require numerous tests to build comprehensive experimental databases, making the process costly and time-consuming. The concept of Material Testing 2.0 (MT2.0) changed the paradigm for material characterization using full-field measurements to provide extensive material behaviour data over the entire test specimen. This concept unlocked the development of new heterogeneous tests that yield richer material behaviour data, reducing the number of tests needed for model calibration. Nevertheless, despite these advancements, phenomenological constitutive models are still limited by their explicit formulation that is naturally biased due to simplifying assumptions.

Along with MT2.0, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) can potentially lead the next paradigm shift in the field of constitutive modelling. Besides the computational efficiency and the seamless integration with FEA solvers, a key advantage of ANNs is the ability to leverage the vast datasets from full-field measurements to capture the material behaviour purely from data, avoiding postulating an explicit formulation and the need for parameter identification. Nonetheless, common approaches rely on labelled datasets based on variables that are not available experimentally. Despite the advantages, ANNs are parameter-rich models, not easily interpretable, and can be hard to configure/train due to the large number of hyperparameters. The predictive accuracy is highly dependent on the quantity and quality of the training data, which may be cost-prohibitive to acquire. ANNs also often struggle to provide physically consistent solutions, unless additional physics-based knowledge is encoded, especially in low-data regimes.

This thesis contributes to the field of material modelling through the proposal of a disruptive methodology coupling Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) with the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) to implicitly capture the unified elastoplastic behaviour of metals. The developed method relies on experimentally measurable data only, effectively harnessing the information available from full-field measurements to indirectly train the RNNs. The

approach is also computationally efficient, as it does not resort to FEA for further calculations. Physical-consistency is ensured with the prediction of the material tangent stiffness and additional physics-based penalty terms. New validation procedures employing external Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and experiments based on heterogeneous mechanical tests are also proposed to better evaluate the model predictive accuracy beyond standard error metrics. The final results show stable training dynamics and good accuracy is achievable, depending on the number and nature of the virtual fields. The models show, in general, a response in good agreement with the reference registering low errors compared to the overall magnitude of the stresses. When evaluated on unseen data from different heterogeneous specimens, extrapolation capacity is retained and correct force reconstruction is achieved, indicating good physical agreement.

The resulting impacts from this research are (i) increased computational efficiency gained through the coupling data-driven modelling with the VFM, (ii) the data-centric capabilities of the ANNs not only allow for improved model accuracy, leading to reliable FEA simulations, but also (iii) unlock the full potential of the information-rich datasets from full-field measurements, thus (iv) reducing the number of experimental tests needed for material characterization and (v) bypassing the need for parameter identification, (vi) leading to improved development lead-time and cost reduction of the overall process.

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Acronyms

AI Artificial Intelligence.

ANN Artificial Neural Network.

DIC Digital Image Correlation.

FEA Finite Element Analysis.

GRU Gated-Recurrent Unit.

KPI Key Performance Indicator.

ML Machine Learning.

MT2.0 Material Testing 2.0.

RAFR Reconstructed Axial Force Ratio.

RNN Recurrent Neural Network.

UMAT User-Material subroutine.

VFM Virtual Fields Method.

VM Virtual Machine.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

The growth in computer power and the developments in computational mechanics paved the way for numerical simulation software to revolutionize the engineering industry. Particularly, FEA tools allowed to virtualize the product design process, as well as material selection, reducing the development time and costs of physical prototyping between design iterations. The resulting technical and economic benefits are crucial to a variety of industries, such as aerospace and automotive. Naturally, as FEA became a fundamental part of the product development workflow, the demand for accurate material models also has grown over the years [1,2].

Constitutive models are provided by governing equations relating the deformation undergone by a material with the corresponding stress. In metal forming, the mechanical behaviour is generally described by phenomenological models, made widely available by commercial FEA simulation packages. The model complexity depends on the phenomena it represents and its flexibility to exactly capture the material behaviour, potentially leading to large non-linear equations with many material-dependent parameters. Despite their wide availability, constitutive models are not ready-made solutions as the parameters need to be calibrated through an inverse identification process, which dictates their final accuracy. Traditional models often struggle when applied to more complex mechanical processes involving highly heterogeneous strain paths, such as metal forming. For decades, conventional material testing and parameter identification had been limited to simple experiments, based on homogeneous specimens, due to restrictions imposed to the geometries and the lack of high-resolution measurement equipment. Therefore, the calibration of more advanced models with classical methods required many tests to collect comprehensive experimental data, making the process time and cost-consuming [3]. The concept of Material Testing 2.0 (MT2.0) [4] promised to tackle these challenges, offering a new paradigm for material characterization. MT2.0 makes use of full-field measurement techniques, such as Digital Image Correlation (DIC), to provide comprehensive displacement data over the entirety of the specimen. This unlocked the development of new heterogeneous mechanical tests that,

due to non-uniform geometries or boundary conditions, provide a large range of strain states [5–8]. Such increased levels of heterogeneity had been proven invaluable for the accurate identification of material parameters [9]. Moreover, it allows avoiding long experimental campaigns, as well as expanding the analysis to high levels of strain beyond the ones reached in classical methods. Despite these advancements, phenomenological constitutive models are still constrained by their explicit formulation and are generally biased, due to the simplifying assumptions of first-order principles [10]. It must be noted that the generality of the existent phenomenological constitutive models were developed using classical homogeneous tests and their results are not able to reproduce the complex strain fields observed in forming processes. Additionally, a given model is not guaranteed to provide good results in different settings from those used to calibrate it [11].

The emergence of Big Data and the exponential increase in computer power in recent years led to the unprecedented growth of various fields of Artificial Intelligence (AI), notably Machine Learning (ML) [12]. Among the plethora of ML algorithms, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been prominent in providing superior modelling performance across a broad spectrum of applications. ANNs have the potential to revolutionize material behaviour modelling [13]. The key advantage is the ability to capture complex material behaviours purely from data, without any assumptions or predefined constitutive equations [14]. This capability not only allows to mitigate the biases inherent to the explicit form of the conventional models, but also avoids the inverse calibration process [10]. However, there are some drawbacks related to the use of ANNs: (i) these are parameter-rich models that suffer from low interpretability, i.e. it is challenging to explain why a given input originates the corresponding output; (ii) their optimal configuration and stable training dynamics may be hard to achieve due the large number of hyperparameters, which require extensive tuning supported by cross-validation techniques; (iii) the predictive accuracy is highly dependent on the quantity and quality of the training data, which may be cost-prohibitive to acquire; (iv) ANNs often struggle to provide physically consistent solutions, unless additional physics-based knowledge is encoded either into the architecture itself or penalty terms, especially in low-data regimes.

The motivation for this research lies in bridging the gap between traditional material testing and modern data-driven approaches. ANNs align with the MT2.0 philosophy, flourishing in large-data environments, effectively harnessing the vast datasets from full-field measurements. The data-centric learning capabilities of ANNs mean that available information will be used more efficiently, leveraging its full potential and, more importantly, allow to mitigate any biases that would be introduced by resorting to explicit models. ANNs also offer increased flexibility in different scenarios, e.g. (i) if new data is made available, previously trained models could be improved or expanded by retraining them on the new data and (ii) pre-trained models on a given material could potentially be used to model a different material, via transfer learning, if the data on the new material is scarce. Furthermore, the increased reliance on virtual simulation tools has made it critical to develop material models that can seamlessly integrate into these frameworks. Within this scope, the direct input-output mapping from ANNs and fast inference times result in improved computational efficiency when integrated in FEA solvers.

1.2 Objectives and achievements

One of the key challenges on the field of material characterization today is the development of constitutive models capable of overcoming the limitations of the traditional equation-based approaches. The driving force behind the present work is to develop accurate constitutive models that eliminate the need for complex inverse parameter identification procedures. This implies learning the material behaviour without resorting to an explicit formulation based on empirical parameters. Another key objective of this thesis is to devise a modelling methodology that capitalizes on the advancements introduced by the MT2.0 paradigm, capable of leveraging the full potential of the dense datasets obtained from the full-field measurements of heterogeneous tests. As a result, it is mandatory that the developed models be efficiently and reliably integrated into FEA software, particularly for sheet metal forming simulations. This aim of this work is illustrated in Figure 1.1.

As outlined in the previous section, ML models, particularly ANNs possess the necessary capabilities to address such challenges, as well as the necessary flexibility to seamlessly adapt to diverse experimental setups. Therefore, this thesis presents a disruptive methodology coupling Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) with the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) for material behaviour modelling. The method is compatible with the vast amounts of data available from full-field measurements, using experimentally measurable variables only, i.e. displacements/strains and global force. The full-field data is used to train the RNNs and capture the full and unified elastoplastic behaviour of metals, with the global and local equilibrium being imposed via the VFM. The methodology does not rely on any postulates and is purely data-centric, effectively avoiding the inverse parameter identification of explicitly defined models and the inherent biases. Moreover, the trained RNN models can be efficiently implemented into existing FEA solvers. The physical correctness of the final models is ensured through the use of physics-based constraints during training and the predictive accuracy ensured through a carefully curated validation workflow that relies not only on the standard error metrics, but also on external KPIs, additional heterogeneous mechanical tests and FEA simulations with the models' being implemented in a UMAT.

The methodology can be seamlessly integrated with the existent state-of-the-art material characterization processes, namely MT2.0 with significant impacts related to (i) increased computational efficiency due to the VFM and does not rely on FEA for further calculations, (ii) improved model accuracy resulting in more reliable FEA simulations, (iii) reduced number of experimental tests required to characterize the mechanical behaviour of metals within the field of metal forming, leading to (iv) a reduction on the development lead-time of engineering metal parts, consequently (v) reducing the costs of the overall development process.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of the developed indirect training methodology, based on the VFM to learn the material behaviour and integration of the resulting model with a FEA solver, via a UMAT.

1.3 Scientific contributions

During the development of this thesis, 6 papers were published, thereby contributing to the scientific community through their dissemination in international journals and conference proceedings. The contributions as first author are as follows:

Journal articles

- P1.** R. Lourenço, A. Andrade-Campos, P. Georgieva. The use of Machine-Learning techniques in material constitutive modelling for metal forming processes. *Metals*, 12 (3) (2022) 427. doi: [10.3390/met12030427](https://doi.org/10.3390/met12030427)
- P2.** R. Lourenço, P. Georgieva, E. Cueto, A. Andrade-Campos. An indirect training approach for implicit constitutive modelling using recurrent neural networks and the virtual fields method. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 425 (2024) 116961. doi: [10.1016/j.cma.2024.116961](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2024.116961)
- P3.** R. Lourenço, A. Tariq, P. Georgieva, A. Andrade-Campos, B. Deliktas. On the use of physics-based constraints and validation KPI for data-driven elastoplastic constitutive modelling. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* [Submitted]
- P4.** R. Lourenço, P. Georgieva, A. Andrade-Campos. Data-driven elastoplastic constitutive modelling with physics-informed RNNs using the Virtual Fields Method for indirect training. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* [Submitted]

Conference proceedings

- C1.** R. Lourenço, A. Andrade-Campos, P. Georgieva. The Virtual Fields Method to Indirectly Train Artificial Neural Networks for Implicit Constitutive Modelling. *Key Engineering Materials*, 926 (2022) 2060–2068. doi: [10.4028/p-gy2di7](https://doi.org/10.4028/p-gy2di7)
- C2.** R. Lourenço, E. Cueto, P. Georgieva, A. Andrade-Campos. On the constraints and consistency in implicit constitutive modelling using ANNs and indirect training. *Materials Research Proceedings* 28 (2023) 1143-1154. doi: [10.21741/9781644902479-125](https://doi.org/10.21741/9781644902479-125)

The following contributions were made as a second author:

1. A. Andrade-Campos, N. Bastos, M. Conde, M. Gonçalves, J. Henriques, R. Lourenço, J. M. P. Martins, M. G. Oliveira, P. Prates and L. Rumor. On the inverse identification methods for forming plasticity models using full-field measurements. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 1238 (1) (2022) 012059. doi: [10.1088/1757-899X/1238/1/012059](https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1238/1/012059).

1.4 Reading guidelines

Following the general introduction given in Chapter 1, this thesis is organized into five main chapters. Chapter 2 presents an overview of Machine Learning techniques, particularly ANNs, applied to constitutive modelling for metal forming processes. The paper provides a discussion on the classical phenomenological approach taken to constitutive modelling and the different ways ANNs have been introduced in the field, namely, in inverse parameter identification, as constitutive model correctors and as full data-driven implicit models [P1].

Chapter 3 introduces a novel indirect training methodology combining RNNs, based on Gated-Recurrent Units (GRUs), with the Virtual Fields Method (VFM), for data-driven constitutive modeling. The paper used for this chapter lays the foundations for this innovative approach and proves its feasibility in the context of ANN training highlighting the advantages of the method compared to the standard supervised learning approaches taken in the literature [P2].

Chapter 4 consists of a paper discussing the importance of incorporating physics-based constraints and external Key Performance Indicator (KPI) into the training and validation workflows of data-driven models for elastoplastic constitutive modelling. This approach ensures physically sound predictions. Several physical constraints are proposed and explored proving to have a significant impact on the final predictive accuracy of the model. New validation metrics beyond standard error statistics are also presented, including heterogeneous mechanical tests [P3].

Chapter 5 revisits the indirect training approach coupling GRU-based RNNs and the VFM presented in Chapter 3, however, introduces a more robust model architecture and puts into practice the knowledge gained from the paper presented in Chapter 4 to fully train the model from scratch. The influence on the number of virtual fields in the training and predictive accuracy of the RNN, and other aspects of the new architecture are discussed [P4].

Finally, Chapter 6 presents the conclusions and perspectives for future work on the topic of data-driven constitutive modelling with unlabelled data coupling the VFM and GRU-based RNNs.

Chapter 2

Machine Learning for constitutive modelling: overview and opportunities

The application of ML to material constitutive is not fully explored and remains a highly active area of research, with many innovative methods being proposed. However, significant challenges persist, particularly regarding data requirements, model training, and achieving high accuracy when applied to metal plasticity.

This Chapter is based on the following published paper:

R. Lourenço, A. Andrade-Campos, P. Georgieva. The use of Machine-Learning techniques in material constitutive modelling for metal forming processes. *Metals*, 12 (3) (2022) 427. doi: [10.3390/met12030427](https://doi.org/10.3390/met12030427)

2.1 The use of machine learning techniques in material constitutive modelling for metal forming processes

Accurate numerical simulations require constitutive models capable of providing precise material data. Several calibration methodologies have been developed to improve the accuracy of constitutive models. Nevertheless, one model's performance is always constrained by its mathematical formulation. Machine learning (ML) techniques, such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have the potential to overcome these limitations. Nevertheless, the use of ML for material constitutive modelling is very recent and not fully explored. Difficulties related to data requirements and training are still open problems. This work explores and discusses the use of ML techniques towards the accuracy of material constitutive models in metal plasticity, particularly contributing as (i) a parameter identification inverse methodology, (ii) a constitutive model corrector, (iii) a data-driven constitutive model using empirical known concepts and (iv) a general implicit constitutive model using data-driven learning approach. These approaches are discussed and examples are given in the framework of non-linear elastoplasticity. To

conveniently train these ML approaches, a large amount of data concerning material behaviour must be used. Therefore, non-homogeneous strain field and complex strain path tests measured with digital image correlation (DIC) techniques must be used for that purpose.

2.1.1 Introduction

Considerable developments in the field of Computational Mechanics and the growth in computational power made it possible for numerical simulation software to emerge and completely revolutionize the engineering industry. In fact, industry's high-demand-fuelled and fast-paced development cycles accelerated the adoption of computational analysis software [3, 15]. With a wide array of software solutions in the market, capable of virtualizing entire design workflows, numerical simulation has become a vital component of the product development process. Indeed, this virtualization has allowed companies to massively reduce the number of time-consuming experiments between design iterations, thus reducing delays and costs and allowing companies to reach higher levels of competitiveness [1]. In this context, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) has been widely used as a powerful numerical simulation tool in engineering analyses, such as structural analysis, heat transfer and fluid flow. In FEA, the material behavior is defined by specific constitutive models, which the ability to adequately describe a given material directly impacts the reliability of the numerical results. As such, material characterization has received increasing attention given the need from computational analysis software for precise material data [1].

Conventionally, constitutive laws are established according to first-principle assumptions in order to generalize experimental observations made on simple loading regimes. In recent years, the fast development of complex materials exhibiting non-linear behavior pushed the formulation of advanced and more complex constitutive models to accurately describe phenomena such as hardening and anisotropy. The challenge lies in reducing the error between the numerical predictions and the experimental value. To improve this differential, the models are enhanced with additional empirical parameters, albeit with the cost of adding complexity to the empirical expressions and making them more difficult to calibrate [16]. Although the advances in imaging techniques, such as DIC, allowed for much richer information to be extracted from experimental observations, conventional models are sometimes incompatible with the abundance of data [10, 17]. However, independently of a model's flexibility to adapt to the experimental results, it is always limited by its mathematical formulation, as it is written explicitly. Additionally, even if a model could be perfectly calibrated, with a given set of experiments, there is no guarantee that it would provide a perfect result for a different set of experiments [11].

In recent years, the advent of Big Data combined with improved algorithms and the exponential increase in computing power led to an unprecedented growth in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) [12]. AI techniques, such as ML, allow computer systems to implicitly learn and recognize patterns purely based on data. For this reason, ML has become an important technology in various engineering fields [18]. From all ML algorithms, ANNs are extremely popular given their superior modelling performance in a wide range of applications, as universal function approximators [18, 19]. As such, neural networks have the potential to provide a radically different approach to material

modelling, with the main advantage that it is not necessary to postulate a mathematical formulation or identify empirical parameters [14]. In general, data-driven approaches can better exploit the large volumes of data from modern experimental measurements, while avoiding the bias induced by constitutive models [10]. These ML techniques rely on different methods to determine the stress tensor corresponding to a given strain state (and other conditions such as temperature, strain rate, etc.). For instance, in [11, 17] Nearest Neighbour Interpolation is employed, while in [20–23] the authors employ a low-dimensional representation of the constitutive equation based uniquely on data. Bessa and co-workers [24] employ clustering techniques, while others employ spline approximations. ANNs were also used for modelling viscoplasticity behaviours [25, 26]. Alternative solutions to pure data-driven models were given, naming hybrid models [22], that enhance/correct existing well-known models with information coming from data, thus performing a sort of data-driven correction. However, there is no consensus about the best data-driven strategy. Even regarding ML methods, different models were employed. In [25], a Multi-layer Feedforward Neural Network (FFNN) is presented. In turn, in [27], a Nested Adaptive Neural Network (NANN) is proposed as a variation of a standard FFNN. On [26, 28], both authors use a FFNN with error backpropagation, but in [26] the algorithm is modified and based only on the error of the strain energy and the external work, without the need for stress data. The major problem of data-driven and ML models is that their accuracy depends on the data used for training, including its quality and quantity. These models require massive amounts of necessarily dissimilar data. However, most data obtained from mechanical tests, even heterogeneous tests, is similar in strain states [29]. Therefore, new mechanical tests are needed to extract the large quantity/quality of material behaviour data to accurately train these models.

2.1.2 Classical Material Modelling

Phenomenological approach

Material modelling refers to the development of constitutive laws, representing the material behavior at the continuum level. Conventionally, constitutive laws are developed based on simplified assumptions and empirical expressions. Such expressions rely on empirical parameters, computed or calibrated via experimental methods. The calibration process ensures the compatibility between the observed and numerically simulated mechanical responses [16, 30]. As models become more advanced in their physical basis, empirical expressions get more complex, often requiring extensive experimental campaigns [3].

The highly complex nature of material behavior and the research of new materials in recent years led to the development of a great number of constitutive models targeting different phenomena. In the framework of plasticity, one can highlight the classic models by Tresca, von Mises [31] or Hill [32]. Such models are formulated as flow rules based on the yield function of the material.

Elastoplasticity

A material under load suffers plastic deformation starting at the uniaxial yield stress σ_y . Beyond this point, hardening phenomena take place. Reversing the load at a given

strain ε , plastic deformation ceases and stress starts to linearly decrease with strain, with gradient equal to the Young's modulus, E [33]. Once the stress reaches zero, the strain remaining in the material is the plastic strain ε^P , whereas the recovered strain ε^e is the elastic strain. The following relationships are easily derived [31]:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^e + \varepsilon^P, \quad (2.1)$$

$$\sigma = E\varepsilon^e = E(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^P). \quad (2.2)$$

There are plenty of developed yield criteria with the most commonly used in engineering practice being that of von Mises. The criterion relies on the knowledge of an equivalent stress $\bar{\sigma}$, the so called von Mises stress, defined in tensor notation as [33]:

$$\bar{\sigma} = \left(\frac{3}{2} \boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \boldsymbol{\sigma}' \right)^{1/2}, \quad (2.3)$$

where, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$ is the deviatoric stress tensor. Similarly, an effective plastic strain rate \dot{p} can be established, such that:

$$\dot{p} = \left(\frac{2}{3} \dot{\varepsilon}^P : \dot{\varepsilon}^P \right)^{1/2}. \quad (2.4)$$

The yield function, thus, assumes the following representation [33]:

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, p) = \bar{\sigma} - \sigma_y = \bar{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) - \sigma_y(p), \quad (2.5)$$

written here as a function of the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and accumulated plastic strain p , such that:

$$p = \int dp = \int \dot{p} dt. \quad (2.6)$$

The performance of the material thus depends on the previous states of stress and strain, that is, plasticity is path-dependent [25]. In this case, the plastic range can be characterized by two internal variables: the back stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\chi}$, representing kinematic hardening and the drag stress R representing isotropic hardening. The yield function is, therefore, modified as [33]:

$$f = J(\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \boldsymbol{\chi}) - R - k \leq 0, \quad (2.7)$$

where k is a material constant and J is a distance in the stress space. For large deformations, the elastoplasticity can be formulated based on the co-rotational configuration. An in-depth overview of this can be seen in [34].

2.1.3 Machine learning approaches for constitutive modelling in metal forming

Material constitutive models are mathematical formulations representing the main characteristics, behaviours and functions of the materials. Generally, continuum mechanical models, such as the ones presented in section 2.1.2, are written in a differential form and require a calibration procedure. However, even with a very robust calibration, known in

the field as parameter identification, the accuracy of the model is always constrained by its mathematical formulation. Additionally, the development of analytical constitutive models requires a large effort in both time and resources. Today's state-of-the-art constitutive models required decades to develop and validate. However, there is still a margin for multiple improvement opportunities, particularly using ML techniques, as the one presented in section 2.1.6. The most straightforward fields of application are the following:

Parameter identification inverse modelling

One category of inverse problems in metal forming is called *parameter identification*. The aim is to estimate material parameters for constitutive models, i.e. estimate parameters to calibrate the models. The development of new materials and the effort to characterize the existent ones led to the formulation of new complex constitutive laws. Nevertheless, many of these new laws demand the identification of a large number of parameters adjusted to the material whose behaviour is to be simulated. In cases where the number of parameters is high, it might be necessary to solve the problem as an inverse non-linear optimization problem.

The parameters' determination should always be performed confronting mathematical/numerical and experimental results. Therefore, the comparison between the mathematical model and the experimental results (observable data) is a function that must be evaluated and minimized. This is generally the objective function of these problems [35–37].

When using the Finite Element Method (FEM) to reproduce the material behaviour, the most used method is the Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) technique that consists in creating a FEM model of a mechanical test, collecting displacement or strain components at some points/nodes and calculating a cost function with the difference between numerical and experimental displacements at these nodes. Minimizing this cost function concerning the unknown constitutive parameters provides the solution to the problem. This method is very general and flexible and can be used with local, average or full-field measurements. Other methods have been also proposed such as the Constitutive Equation Gap Method (CEGM), the Equilibrium Gap Method (EGM), the Reciprocity Gap Method (RGM) and the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) [38]. A review of these methods can be found in [39].

Considering the direct problem, which is to obtain the strain, displacement and stresses given the input variables (such as boundary conditions, geometry, and material parameters), an inverse problem can be devised in a given way to obtain the material parameters and stresses, when the inputs are the geometry, boundary conditions, displacements, and strains. In this context, ML can be used to solve the inverse problem efficiently, modelling the inverse process using the direct problem results as training data. The solution for the direct problem can be easily obtained using FEA software. This approach is illustrated in Figure 2.1.

Constitutive model corrector

In the last decades, a large number of analytical constitutive models were developed. Although a large effort has been put in these successive developments, a model is always

Figure 2.1: ML as inverse model for parameter identification. The training data is obtained using the direct problem FEA results.

a simplification of reality and is always constrained by a mathematical formulation. Nevertheless, the effort and the knowledge gained in these last decades should not be neglected for the development of new constitutive models. Therefore, one approach to develop new constitutive models using ML techniques can take advantage of this knowledge, as starting point, and can be used as what can be called as *model corrector* or *model enhancement*.

The approach of the model corrector starts after the calibration of the well-known analytical model. It consists on confronting the real observations, generally from experimental tests, with the numerical simulations. After the parameter identification process, the differences between the real and numerical values can be collected and evaluated, in a way similar to a data decomposition process (see Figure 2.2). These differences do not come only from the errors of the measurement techniques but also from the limitation (non-mathematical flexibility) of the analytical model. Then, the ML model is used to model the differences as a different (refined) scale model. For accurate simulations, both analytical and ML corrector models must be introduced in the FEA software, resulting in a hybrid constitutive model.

Data-driven constitutive model using empirical known concepts

An upper level of the previous approaches is using ML exclusively to model the behaviour of the material. However, the architecture and the development of the ML model considers some physical and empirical knowledge gained in the last decades in the development of analytical models, which are numerically implemented *a posteriori*. An example of this influence is the selection of the input and output features of the ML model. Generally, these ML material models that use empirical knowledge are developed in a differential point of view, such as the known analytical models, and all output features are time-derivatives of the input features. Additionally, all features, including internal variables, have specific physical or empirical representations or concepts, such as hardening, grain size, recovery, etc.

These ML material models can easily fully replace the existent constitutive models implemented in FEA software because both share the same type of structure and input/output features (see Figure 2.3). Although the majority of the implementations is done explicitly, these models can theoretically be implemented in implicit FEA codes,

Figure 2.2: ML as constitutive model corrector/improvement. The real behaviour (measured values) is decomposed into the analytical model (retrieved after a full-field calibration process) and the ML model. The training of the ML model uses the data obtained after the decomposition.

such as ABAQUS [40]. To train these models, a non-straightforward analysis and decomposition of the experimental data is required for each specific feature of the model. This procedure takes into account the meaning of each feature (i.e. of each internal variable).

General implicit constitutive model using data-driven learning approach

The use of ML technology to fully model the behaviour of the material without any preconception, knowledge, analytical or mathematical formulation is the ultimate goal of this scientific thematic. Although not mature, this approach has a large potential because (i) the material behavior is caused by a multitude of phenomena too complex to be handled individually, as it is traditionally done in the development of analytical models; (ii) the amount of data now retrieved using full-field methods and heterogeneous tests is difficult to be analysed in the same way as the data previously acquired from classical homogeneous mechanical tests and (iii) no previous concepts or knowledge is required, and preconceptions can mean constraints for disruptive developments.

An illustration of the development of an ML constitutive model using full-field experimental data and its integration into FEA simulation software is depicted in Figure 2.3. The most difficult step in the development of this approach is training the model, which, in this case, does not use any physical knowledge as a training constraint. Additionally, output features of the model, such as components of the stress tensor, cannot be measured in real experimental mechanical tests.

2.1.4 Review on Implicit data-driven material modelling

The concept of implicit material modelling relies on the material behavior being captured within the connections of an ANN, trained using experimental or even synthetic data.

Figure 2.3: ML model as a full constitutive model, which is implemented into a FEA simulation software. The ML material model is trained indirectly using full-field measurements from experimental tests. This approach can optionally use empirical known concepts.

That is, the relationships between stress and strain are learned purely based on data, without resorting to a mathematical model or any kind of assumptions. The neural network should not only be able to reproduce the data it was trained on, but also possess the ability to approximate the results of other experiments. In this regard, while explicit material models may often not be able to reproduce new sets of experiments [11], ANNs are highly flexible and adaptable in the sense that these can be improved by being retrained with new data [41, 42].

The possibility of extending neural network concepts to constitutive modelling was first explored by Ghaboussi, Garret and Wu [43]. The authors trained feedforward neural networks with backpropagation using experimental data and tested them against several well-known analytical models describing the behavior of concrete in plane stress subjected to two load settings: monotonic biaxial loading and uniaxial compressive cyclic loading. For the first setting, both stress and strain-controlled models were developed in order to tackle the path dependency of the material behaviour. The models were trained to predict strain and stress increments, respectively, using the current states of stress and strain as inputs, with the addition of a stress or strain increment. For the cyclic load setting, the model was trained to predict the strain increment, based on the current state and the previous two states of stress and strain. The authors reported promising results for both load settings with the ANN-based models showing, in some cases, better performance than some of the analytical formulations. With their research, Ghaboussi and coworkers effectively proved the powerful interpolation and generalization capabilities of ANNs applied to constitutive modelling tasks, thus, laying the foundations for the further development of implicit material models. Their methodology was later applied to the constitutive modelling of concrete (Wu and Ghaboussi [44]), sand (Ghaboussi *et al.* [45] and Ellis *et al.* [46]) and composites (Ghaboussi *et al.* [47]).

An early application of the implicit modelling approach in the framework of metal plasticity is due to Furukawa and Yagawa [25]. The authors introduced the first mathematical description of the concept relying on a state-space representation and proposed an implicit viscoplastic model using neural networks, based on the well-known Chaboche's model. The model was trained using synthetic data and was tested against experimental data. Due to the fact that the internal variables of the Chaboche's model are not experimentally obtainable, a simple technique was proposed in order to derive the states of kinematic and isotropic stresses from the experimental curves. Overall, the authors reported that the implicit model correlated well with the results provided by

the conventional formulations, when applied to testing data within the training range, certifying the great interpolative capacity of the neural network. However, considerable errors were observed in stress and strain curves when using testing data far off the limits of the training set, indicating the limited generalization capacity of the model.

Following a purely data-driven approach, several authors successfully applied very similar methodologies to train ANN-based constitutive models, using experimental data, to predict the flow behavior of different metals under hot deformation (i.e., compression, torsion). Many industrial and engineering applications require the hot deformation of materials which is associated with numerous metallurgic phenomena, affecting the structure of the material at the micro-scale. As such, several factors affecting the flow stress generate highly complicated and non-linear relationships, limiting the application range and accuracy of the conventional constitutive models. Li *et al.* [48] studied the high temperature flow characteristics of Ti-15-3 alloy for the determination of hot-forging processing parameters and used an ANN model to predict the flow stress, referring that the ANN was able to correctly reproduce the behavior in sampled and non-sampled data. Lin *et al.* [14] used an ANN to predict the flow stress of 42CrMo steel under hot compressive deformation tests, reporting that the predictions were in good agreement with the experimental results. Mandal *et al.* [49] stated that the ANN-based model was an efficient tool to evaluate and predict the deformation behavior of stainless steel type AISI 304L. Sun *et al.* [50] developed a constitutive relationship model for Ti40 alloy and indicated the predicted flow stress by the ANN-based model correlated well with experimental results. Li *et al.* [51] reported that an ANN-based model showed better performance and proved to be more accurate and effective in predicting the hot deformation behavior of modified 2.25Cr-1Mo steel than the conventional constitutive equations.

Neural network architectures and generalization capacity

The implicit approach to material modelling based in ANNs presents obvious advantages, however important choices regarding network architecture and the training process have to be taken into account in order to avoid limited predictive capabilities. For example, non-linear material behavior is highly path-dependent, making it difficult for ANNs to learn and generalize well the full spectrum of material behavior. The issue is accounted by Ghaboussi and coworkers [43] in their original work. Aiming to improve the generalization capacity of the ANN-based material models, Ghaboussi and Sidarta [27] later proposed a new neural network architecture: Nested Adaptive Neural Networks (NANNs). Their proposal is based on the fact that most data have an inherent structure which, in the case of material behavior, is a nested structure that can be observable in terms of:

- *Dimensionality* - where constitutive functions are taken as members of function spaces, each of which contained in a space of subsequently higher dimensions;
- *Path-dependency* - where a state of the material behavior represented with a given number of history points, is a subset of another state represented with a larger number of history points.

In line with this notion, the underlying concept of NANNs is to train a base module to represent the material behavior in the lowest function space and, subsequently, augment

it with additional modules representing higher function spaces (Figure 2.4). All the nodes in each layer of the new added module are connected to all the nodes in the next layer of the lower levels. Each module is a standard FFNN trained using adaptive evolution, that is, neurons are subsequently added to the hidden layers as network approaches its capacity. With new nodes, new connections are generated and the objective is for the new links to capture the knowledge that the old ones were not able to capture. As such, training is carried out for the new connections while the old ones are frozen. With this new technique, Ghaboussi and Sidarta [27] reported a significant error reduction when using high-level NANNs.

Figure 2.4: Nested Adaptive Neural Network, as idealized by Ghaboussi and Sidarta [27].

In more recent works, regarding the scope of the path-dependency of material behavior, several authors (Abueidda *et al.* [52], Heider *et al.* [53], Ghavamian and Simone [54], Mozaffar *et al.* [55] and Gorji *et al.* [56]) demonstrated that RNNs can be particularly useful for modelling path-dependent plasticity, reporting superior performance compared to conventional ANNs. Contrarily to the latter, RNNs are designed to handle time sequences [55,57] and are equipped with history-dependent hidden states, enabling them to carry information from previous inputs onto future predictions. These internal variables have the potential to emulate the role of objects such as plastic strains and back stresses in physics-based plasticity. Nevertheless, standard RNNs suffer from vanishing/exploding gradients that hinder the error backpropagation process while dealing with long sequences. Long Short-term Memory LSTM and GRUs are more robust derivations of the standard RNNs (Figure 2.5), proposed to avoid those problems.

Apart from generalization issues, a much more fundamental problem is emphasized by several authors [27,43,58,59]: the “black-box” nature of ANNs, does not guarantee the implicit material model to obey the conservation laws, symmetry and invariance requirements of conventional models. Nonetheless, if a neural network has been trained

Figure 2.5: Basic architectures of the most common topologies of RNNs: (a) the GRU and (b) the LSTM unit. The arrow lines indicate the flow of information through each unit; vector concatenation takes place in zones where two lines adjoin. The sum and multiplication operators refer to pointwise operations. Red and blue blocks represent sigmoid and hyperbolic tangent signal activations, respectively.

with a comprehensive dataset, it is reasonable to assume that it would be able to approximate the laws that the actual material obeys and use its generalization capability to appropriately predict stress-strain paths not included in the training data. However, building comprehensive datasets means acquiring large amounts of data, which the cost of acquisition is often prohibitive and models end up being built in a small data regime.

To tackle these issues, Raissi *et al.* [59] proposed a new type of neural network: Physics-informed Neural Networks (PINNs). The authors exploit the use of automatic differentiation to differentiate neural networks with respect to their input coordinates (i.e., space and time) and model parameters to obtain PINNs. The technique allows to constrain neural network models to respect symmetries, invariances, or conservation principles originating from the physical laws that govern the observed data. This type of information, encoded in such way into the neural network, acts as a regularization agent that greatly reduces the space of admissible solutions. The methodology was proven by the authors as able to tackle a wide range of problems in computational science, allowing the use of relatively simple FFNN architecture trained with small amounts of data. The general methodology proposed by Raissi and coworkers [59] was applied to constitutive modeling in a recent work by Masi *et al.* [58] through the proposal of Thermodynamics-based Artificial Neural Networks (TANNs), a subtype of PINNs. In TANNs, basic laws of thermodynamics are encoded directly in the architecture of the neural network. In the framework of material modelling, these thermodynamic constraints concern the stresses and the internal state variables and their relationship with the free-energy and the dissipation rate. Masi and coworkers [58] report the TANN-based models were able to deliver thermodynamically consistent predictions, both for seen and unseen data, achieving more accurate results than standard ANN material models. Moreover, the authors state that the inclusion of the laws of physics directly into the network architecture allows for the use of smaller training datasets,

given that the network already does not have to capture the underlying relationships from data.

Xu et al. [60], on the other hand, refer that even though these physical constraints allow for improved accuracy in stress predictions, the ANN-based constitutive models may still not yield a symmetric positive definite stiffness matrix. Therefore, nonphysical solutions and numerical instabilities arise when coupling the ANN-based models with FEM solvers. The authors propose Symmetric Positive Definite Neural Networks (SPD-NN) as a new architecture in order to deal with these issues. The neural network model is trained to predict the Cholesky factors of the tangent stiffness matrix, from which the stress is obtained. According to Xu et al. [60], the approach weakly imposes convexity on the strain energy function, satisfies the Hill's criterion and time consistency for path-dependent materials. The authors compared the SPD-NN with standard architectures in a series of problems involving elasto-plastic, hyper-elastic and multi-scale composite materials. The results showed that, overall, the SPD-NN was able to provide superior results, proving the effectiveness of the approach for learning path-dependent, path-independent and multi-scale material behaviour.

Integration in Finite Element Analysis

An ANN-based constitutive model can be used in a way similar to conventional material models in FEA to solve boundary value problems. An important disadvantage regarding the numerical implementation of ANN-based material models in FEA, was pointed out by Ghaboussi and Sidarta [27]. The issue is related to the fact that the ANN model already provides an updated state of stress, without the need for integration of the model's equations over the strain increment. Therefore, it's not possible to obtain an explicit form of the material's stiffness matrix. As a solution, the authors propose an explicit formulation of the material's stiffness matrix for the ANN-based material model, allowing for an efficient convergence of the finite element Newton-Raphson iterations.

Successful embedding of ANNs as material description in Finite Element (FE) codes were recorded by several authors. Usually, the ANN architecture is implemented in the software's subroutines as a set of matrices, containing the optimized weights obtained during training. Substantial gains in computational efficiency using ANNs have been reported due to the practically instantaneous mapping offered by the ANNs. Lefik and Schrefler [28] trained a simple ANN as an incremental non-linear constitutive model for a FE code and demonstrated that a well-trained, albeit simple, network model was able to reproduce the behavior from simulated material hysteresis loops.

Kessler *et al.* [61] developed an ANN-based constitutive model for aluminum 6061, based on experimental data for different temperatures, strains and strain rates. The authors implemented the model in Abaqus VUMAT and reported the ANN's superior ability to mirror the experimental results.

Jang *et al.* [18] proposed a constitutive model to predict elastoplastic behavior for J2-plasticity, where an ANN was implemented in Abaqus User MATerial (UMAT) to replace the conventional nonlinear stress-integration scheme, under isotropic hardening. The ANN was used only for nonlinear plastic loading, while keeping linear elastic loading and unloading to the physics-based model. The authors reported that the ANN-based model provided results in good agreement with those from the conventional model for single-element tensile test and circular cup drawing simulations.

Zhang and Mohr [62] rewrote a standard algorithm for von Mises plasticity such that the stress update was governed by a single non-linear function predicting the apparent modulus (i.e., the Young's modulus in case of elastic loading/unloading, and the elastoplastic tangent matrix in case of plastic loading). This function was then replaced by an FFNN and implemented as a user material subroutine in Abaqus/explicit. The authors demonstrated that a neural network with five hidden layers and 15 neurons per layer was able to "learn" the yield condition, flow rule and hardening law from data, providing highly accurate responses to the predictions of a J2 plasticity model, including the large deformation response for arbitrary multi-axial loading paths and reverse loading.

Indirect/inverse training

The vast majority of the approaches documented in the literature for implicit constitutive modelling consists on feeding the ANN with paired data (usually, stress and strain) during the training process, in order to assimilate the material behavior [63]. The process requires copious amounts of data and obtaining comprehensive stress-strain relationships, relying on the standard simple mechanical tests, poses a great challenge especially when dealing with anisotropic materials. Moreover, in a complex experiment certain variables such as stresses cannot be directly measured [64]. Therefore, the training process must be carried out in such a way that allows the ANN-based model to indirectly predict the stress using measurable data, e.g. displacements and global force, obtained from full-field measurements [64]. One of the first approaches to bypass these limitations was proposed by Ghaboussi et al. [47], consisting on an auto-progressive method to train an ANN to learn the behavior of concrete from experimental load-deflection curves. However, the method is inefficient due to the fact that FEM simulations are needed in order to compute the stress and strain.

The generalized SPD-NN architecture proposed by Xu *et al.* [60] was able to deal with both direct and indirect training procedures. For the latter, the authors used displacement and force data to indirectly train the SPD-NN-based model and predict the stress in an incremental form by coupling the ANN with a non-linear equation solver. Despite providing superior results compared to standard architectures, the authors point out the requirement of full-field data as the main limitation, especially for three-dimensional solid bodies.

Both Huang et al. [64] and Xu et al. [65] proposed a method to use an ANN to replace the constitutive model in a FEM solver in order to impose the physical constraints during training, enabling the ANN to learn material behaviour based on the experimental measurement. Nonetheless, the approach highly depends on a full-field data for force and displacements, while, in most experiments, only partially observed data is usually available, limiting its application to more complex three-dimensional bodies. A different method was reported by Liu *et al.* [63] who propose coupling an ANN with the FEM to form a coupled mechanical system, with the inputs and outputs being determined at each incremental step (Figure 2.6). With this, the ANN is able to learn the constitutive behavior based on partial force and displacement data. The authors applied the methodology to learn nonlinear in-plane shear and failure initiation in composite materials, achieving good models with results in excellent agreement with the analytical solutions. The main drawback is the need to write a FEM code based

on an automatic differentiation package (e.g. Pytorch or TensorFlow), making the FEA step very time-consuming. In order to overcome this limitation, Tao *et al.* [66] propose a similar approach to the one proposed by Liu, with the ANN model being coupled with FEA software Abaqus. However, the authors propose a modified set of backward propagation equations that enable the communication between Abaqus and the ANN, keeping the whole training process internally in Abaqus.

Figure 2.6: Coupled ANN-FEM model approach presented by Liu *et al* [67].

A similar approach to Liu *et al.* [67] is here proposed, however, instead of coupling the ANN with a FEM solver to enforce the physical constraints, the Virtual Field Method (VFM) is used to guarantee the global equilibrium (Figure 2.7). The VFM, first introduced by Grédiac [38], is known by its computational efficiency and does not require FEA in order to conduct any forward calculations [68]. The key elements behind the VFM are the Principle of Virtual Work (PVW) and the choice of virtual fields. According to the PVW, the internal virtual work must be equal to the external virtual work performed by the external forces and is written by [69]:

$$-\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dV + \int_{\partial V} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* dS = 0, \quad (2.8)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*$ is the virtual strain, \mathbf{u}^* is the virtual displacement and \mathbf{T} is the global traction vector. The virtual fields are mathematical test functions, which work as weights and can be defined independently of the measured displacements/strains. An infinite number of virtual fields can be used, nonetheless the following two conditions should be met [69, 70]: the chosen virtual fields should be kinematically admissible, that is, the displacement boundary conditions must be satisfied and the virtual fields should be zero or constant along the boundary where the force is applied. By coupling the VFM with the ANN model, one can use force and displacement data, numerically generated or coming from full-field measurements, to indirectly train the ANN. The strain components are easily obtained from the displacements and are fed as inputs to the neural network, which will provide the stress components. The virtual strains are obtained from the virtual displacements, such that:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* = \nabla \mathbf{u}^* + \nabla^T \mathbf{u}^*. \quad (2.9)$$

Then the stress equilibrium is evaluated globally by means of the PVW and the parameters (\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b}) are optimized until the equilibrium is respected, that is, by minimizing the loss:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{n_V} \sum_{i=1}^{n_V} \left(- \int_V \hat{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dV + \int_{\partial V} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* dS \right)^2, \quad (2.10)$$

where n_V represents the number of virtual fields. This methodology is illustrated in section 2.1.5.

Figure 2.7: Coupled ANN-VFM method for implicit constitutive modelling.

2.1.5 Application examples

This section present an example of each approach, showing the large potential of ML in material constitutive modelling.

Parameter identification

The parameters identification problem can be reduced to a curve-fitting problem if physical constraints would not be taken into account. However, most material constitutive models have physical constraints such as material parameter boundary values and mathematical relations between them, in order to guarantee the parameters have a physical meaning [71]. The formulation for the solution of the constitutive model parameters identification is as follows. First, a physical system with a behaviour that can be described by a numerical model and for which experimental results are available should be considered. A set of measurable variables that can be experimentally determined should also be considered. This set of variables can be defined as $\mathbf{Z}^T = [z_1, z_2, \dots, z_m]$. In the case where simple mechanical tests are considered, such as tensile and shear tests, these measurable variables would be the stresses or strains. Considering this information, then it is possible to formulate the solution of the identification problem as the minimization of a function that measures the difference between theoretical predictions \mathbf{Z}^{num} (obtained by the numerical model) and experimental data. This function is known as the objective function $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{A})$, and can be formulated as [71]:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{A}) = \sum_{q=1}^N \mathcal{L}_q(\mathbf{A}), \quad (2.11)$$

with $\mathcal{L}_q(\mathbf{A})$ computed as:

$$\mathcal{L}_q(\mathbf{A}) = \frac{1}{(t_1 - t_0)} \int_{t_0}^{t_1} [\mathbf{Z}^{\text{num}}(\mathbf{A}) - \mathbf{Z}^{\text{exp}}]^T \mathbf{D}_q [\mathbf{Z}^{\text{num}}(\mathbf{A}) - \mathbf{Z}^{\text{exp}}] dt, \quad (2.12)$$

where $\mathbf{A} = [A_1, A_2, \dots, A_r]^\top$ is the set of the $r \in \mathbb{N}$ constitutive model parameters and \mathbf{Z}^{exp} is a known experimental value of \mathbf{Z} in N experimental tests. Tuple of time points (t_0, t_1) is the time period of the generic test q . Also, \mathbf{D}_q is a given weight matrix associated to the test q . The optimization problem consists on finding the minima of $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{A})$, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{\mathbf{A}}{\text{minimize}} && \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{A}) \\ & \text{subject to:} && g_m(\mathbf{A}) \leq 0, && m = 1, \dots, M \\ & && h_l(\mathbf{A}) = 0, && l = 1, \dots, L \\ & && A_i^{\min} < A_i < A_i^{\max}, && i = 1, \dots, r, \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

where the M inequalities $g_m(\mathbf{A})$ and the L equalities $h_l(\mathbf{A})$ define the model constraints. The search-space is limited and, as a consequence, the optimization parameters should fit in it.

The previous classical methodology is indeed computationally expensive because an optimization problem must be solved. Therefore, ML techniques directly applied to solve the inverse problem without the need for iterative procedures can be beneficial. Additionally, the ML methodology is easier to implement and faster at obtaining results in comparison with the current state-of-the-art procedures, such as the VFM and FEMU methods. Considering that the parameters to be identified will be used in numerical FEA, the training phase can directly and accurately use a numerical FEA database. Even if the creation of this database is computationally time-consuming, it is less costly than an experimental database and it is done only once for each mechanical test. Then, the parameters are identified (i.e. predicted within the ML model) instantaneously and using one experimental test.

The example hereby presented is based in the work done in [72] and uses the biaxial cruciform test in order to generate data to train and identify the parameters for both the Swift's hardening law (parameters σ_0 , k and n) and the Hill48 anisotropic criterion (parameters r_0 , r_{45} and r_{90}). A Young's modulus $E = 210$ GPa and a Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.3$ are used to characterize the elastic response of the material. As in [72], synthetic images are used for comparison and validation purposes. The reference parameters for the plastic anisotropy coefficients r_α at 0° , 45° and 90° from the rolling direction are listed in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Plastic anisotropy coefficients r_α used for obtaining the reference cruciform biaxial test [72].

Hill'48 parameters	Reference Values
r_0	1.680
r_{45}	1.890
r_{90}	2.253

Training the ML using a biaxial cruciform test

The full geometry of the cruciform test specimen is depicted in Figure 2.8a, however only one-fourth is used. The solid geometry is discretized as shown in Figure 2.8b, using a mesh composed by a total of 114 combined CPS4 and CPS3R elements. Symmetry

boundary conditions are applied at $x = 0$ and $y = 0$ boundaries. A displacement condition $u_x = u_y = 2$ mm is applied along the x and y directions.

Figure 2.8: (a) Cruciform geometry [72] and (b) mesh for the parameter identification problem.

The range of the six constitutive parameters used to generate the database is shown in Table 2.2. Due to the large number of possible combinations, the Latin Hypercube Sampling method was used resulting in a total of 6000 samples.

Table 2.2: Input Space of constitutive parameters for the biaxial test.

Constitutive parameters	Input Space
σ_0 [MPa]	120-200
n	0.175-0.275
K [MPa]	480-570
r_0	1.0-2.5
r_{45}	1.0-2.5
r_{90}	1.0-2.5

The optimal ANN hyperparameters for the inverse model of the cruciform test were searched. The ideal architecture is listed in Table 2.3.

The input layer has 7203 input features since 21 times steps were considered for each test sample and, for each time step, the global Force and the strain tensor in all elements are used. Therefore, each sample has the following structure:

$$\left(\text{Force}, (\varepsilon_{xx}, \varepsilon_{yy}, \varepsilon_{xy})_{i=1, \dots, \text{elements}} \right)_{j=1, \dots, \text{times steps}} \quad (2.14)$$

The suggested learning rate $\alpha = 1.512 \times 10^{-5}$ was also found using the *Hyperband* approach.

In Figure 2.9 the learning curves are plotted, registering errors lower than 0.02 during training. The best result was achieved after 275 epochs with a MSE of 0.00083 and a MAE of 0.0072.

Figure 2.10 present the validation curves for the inverse cruciform test, where MSE curve show an exponential decay in the beginning and a final plateau with a very low error while the MAE slowly decays with large oscillations. Figure 2.11 shows the influence of the training set size in the MSE. Considering that a plateau was not

Table 2.3: ANN architecture for the biaxial test.

Layer	Neurons	Activation	Kernel_initializer
Input	7203	-	-
Dense 1	7000	tanh	Orthogonal
Dense 2	3000	tanh	Truncated normal
Dense 3	5000	tanh	Truncated normal
Dense 4	5000	selu	Variance scaling
Dense 5	6000	selu	Variance scaling
Output	6	-	-

Figure 2.9: MSE and MAE evolution during the training process.

Figure 2.10: Validation curves for Cruciform inverse model.

achieved, it can be concluded that further information should be given to the model to avoid underfitting. The lack of convergence can also be due to unrepresentative data (lack of quality).

Figure 2.11: Influence of the training set size in the training and validation phases for the inverse biaxial test model.

Prediction and comparison

In order to evaluate the performance of the ANN inverse model, three reference sets of material parameters were chosen (see reference values in Table 2.4) to create synthetic experimental data and used as test cases. Test case 2 uses the same parameters as in [72]. The predictions and corresponding errors are also depicted in Table 2.4. The smallest error was in test case 2, while the largest error was for the test case 3. This accuracy difference between test case 2 and 3 is expected, with the largest error seen for test case 3, where the reference parameters are outside the range of the training space. Furthermore, the error in test cases 1 and 2 are very low, which contrasts with the discussion in the training and validation phase.

Table 2.4: Predictions and corresponding errors for inverse cruciform test model.

		σ_0 [MPa]	n	K [MPa]	r_0	r_{45}	r_{90}
Test 1	Reference	120.00	0.18	530.00	1.01	1.24	1.73
	Predicted	120.98	0.18	536.69	1.06	1.25	1.71
	Error [%]	0.82	1.67	1.26	4.95	0.81	1.16
Test 2	Reference	160.00	0.26	565.00	1.68	1.89	2.253
	Predicted	160.34	0.26	565.60	1.69	1.88	2.27
	Error [%]	0.21	1.15	0.11	0.60	0.53	0.75
Test 3	Reference	220.00	0.30	620.00	2.52	2.67	2.95
	Predicted	202.61	0.24	558.54	2.36	2.30	2.74
	Error [%]	7.90	21.67	9.91	6.35	13.86	7.12

The force-displacement and strain-stress curves resulted from the obtained para-

meters can be seen in Figures 2.12a and 2.12b, where a quite perfect fit can be observed.

Figure 2.12: (a) Force-displacement and (b) stress-strain curves obtained with the predicted parameters for the cruciform test case 2.

The results obtained using an ANN approach were compared with the results using other approaches in [72]. The comparison, presented at Table 2.5, shows a minimal difference between the errors of the different approaches, meaning that the ANN is effective and can predict the parameters with the same precision as the other more established approaches. However, it should be noted that, although the identification took less than a second, the ANN approach required around 96 hours to complete the 6000 samples database in a CPU Intel i7-8700 computer. The VFM solution took less than 5 minutes for the required 15 optimization iterations [72].

Table 2.5: Comparison of the ANN approach with other approaches presented in [72] for the parameter identification using the biaxial cruciform test for the test case 2.

		σ_0 [MPa]	n	K [MPa]	r_0	r_{45}	r_{90}
	Reference	160.00	0.26	565.00	1.68	1.89	2.25
ANN approach (96 h)	Predicted	160.34	0.26	565.60	1.69	1.88	2.27
	Error [%]	0.21	1.15	0.11	0.60	0.53	0.75
VFM (< 5 min.)	Predicted	159.76	0.26	566.16	1.67	1.91	2.24
	Error [%]	0.15	0.44	0.25	0.16	1.11	0.26

Figure 2.13 shows the force-displacement and stress-strain curves obtained with the learned material parameters for the test cases 1 and 3. As seen for test cases, even if the errors are larger, the curves show an excellent fit. However, for the test case 3 a large error amplitudes are observed. This can be explained by the fact that the reference data was outside the training space, meaning the network needed to extrapolate the information to predict a result.

To test the robustness of the ANN parameter identification approach and to take into account possible errors coming from experimental measurements, the training dataset was polluted with random normal distribution noise (with a standard deviation of 1). Table 2.6 lists the predictions of the ANN after the training with the noise polluted data. The predictions attained presented a larger error demonstrating that this approach is influenced by the quality of the training data.

Figure 2.13: (a) Force displacement and (b) stress-strain curves for the cruciform test case 1. (c) Force displacement and (d) stress-strain curves for cruciform test case 3.

Table 2.6: Predictions with the ANN inverse cruciform model using the noise polluted dataset.

		σ_0 [MPa]	n	K [MPa]	r_0	r_{45}	r_{90}
Test 1	Reference	120.00	0.18	530.00	1.01	1.24	1.73
	Predicted	146.82	0.197	568.02	1.66	1.72	1.98
	Error	22.35	9.44	7.17	64.36	38.71	14.45
Test 2	Reference	160.00	0.26	565.00	1.68	1.89	2.25
	Predicted	152.79	0.23	558.82	1.66	1.72	1.98
	Error	4.51	10.00	1.09	8.93	8.47	18.77
Test 3	Reference	220.00	0.30	620.00	2.52	2.67	2.95
	Predicted	166.61	0.23	554.62	1.77	1.73	1.93
	Error	24.27	24.27	10.55	29.76	35.21	34.58

Remarks

This example shows the capabilities of a ML methodology applied to the calibration of numerical models of materials. Here, an easy to implement FFNN was trained as an inverse model with the aid of a large dataset generated from FEA numerical simulations. The ANN-based model was able to achieve its objectives and the results show that the network can predict material parameters, even though with some errors. It was also seen that the reliability of the ANN inverse model is highly dependent on the quantity and quality of the training data.

ML constitutive model using empirical known concepts

The selection of the features of the ML model can be done using the knowledge already gained in the last decades. Therefore, concepts such as isotropic and kinematic hardening can be used as output/input of the ML. These concepts and their values can be retrieved in real material mechanical curves obtained with classical homogeneous tests using the result's decomposition, as done in [25], and used for training purposes. Additionally, the differential formulation of the majority of the known material model can be also maintained in the development of an ML plasticity model. In classical plasticity or viscoplasticity models with mixed isotropic-kinematic hardening, the inputs are the stress tensor σ , the plastic (or viscoplastic) strain tensor ε^{VP} , the backstress tensor χ , the isotropic hardening R and the equivalent plastic strain p , which is a scalar value representing the overall plasticity level. This results in 11 inputs, which can be used in a FFNN architecture with one single hidden layer. The eight outputs are the differential values of the inputs, i.e. the set $\{\dot{\varepsilon}^{VP}, \dot{\chi}, \dot{p}, \dot{R}\}$. The stress tensor can be updated by a hypoelastic relation given as

$$\sigma = C (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^{VP}). \quad (2.15)$$

where C is the material stiffness matrix and ε is the total strain tensor. Generally, the formulation in Eq. 2.15 is used in incremental form due to the nonlinearity of the plastic behaviour.

In this section, the material constitutive behaviour of a metal is modelled using ML/ANN techniques and additional empirical concepts as the ones previously introduced. Then, this model is used in a finite element analysis. In this example, the material ML model has an artificial neural network (ANN) architecture and it is trained (fitted) using a virtual simulated material (as synthetic data). This virtual material has a *a priori* known behaviour, following the classical Chaboche elastoviscoplastic model. The advantage of knowing beforehand the behaviour is that allows evaluating the ML capabilities and competences in material constitutive modelling at least to replace classical models [40].

Creating the dataset for training

To train the ML/ANN model, it was artificially created a synthetic database representing the behaviour of a virtual material. Although a large set of analytical elastoplastic constitutive models could be chosen, in this work, the elasto-viscoplastic Chaboche model was selected due to the challenge of adding rate-dependent phenomena in the behaviour of the material. Plane stress conditions were applied. The viscoplastic strain

rate tensor and the plastic strain rate can be seen in Eq. 2.29. Additionally, the kinematic and isotropic hardening evolution are respectively defined by equations 2.31 and 2.32. The stress-strain states of the differential equations governing the behaviour depend also on elasto-plastic material properties (e.g. $E = 5000$ MPa, $\nu = 0.3$, $R_1 = 500$ MPa, $k = 0$, $K = 50$ MPa s⁻¹, $a = 7500$ MPa, $b = 0.6$, $c = 100$, $n = 3$).

The system of differential equations for two tensile tests (T_{xx} , T_{yy}) and one simple shear (S_{xy}) for three cyclic strain ranges of 0.05, 0.12 and 0.16 is solved using the Runge-Kutta method [73] and their results added to the virtual material database. The 9 virtually experimental results are created and represented by Figure 2.14. Each test is simulated with 1000 data points, as done in [40].

Figure 2.14: Normalized/scaled and adimensional values of the (generated) dataset used for training. (a) the scaled input data (σ , χ , ϵ^{vp} , R and p), is transformed into the (b) scaled differential output data ($\dot{\chi}$, $\dot{\epsilon}^{vp}$, \dot{R} and \dot{p}) by the virtual material model.

Training the ANN model

As supervised learning, the training finds the regression parameters to minimize the cost function. In this work, the best topology, activation functions and the optimization algorithm are found using a grid search function [74] and a 5-fold cross-validation scheme. For that purpose, (i) four topologies (four, ten, sixteen and twenty-two hidden neurons) for one hidden layer, (ii) three activation functions (logistic, tanh, ReLU), and (iii) three optimization algorithms (LBFGS, SGD, ADAM) were candidates. An automatic batch size of $\min(200, n^{\circ} \text{ training samples})$ and a learning rate of 0.001 were used. For the output layer, a linear activation function is used.

Figure 2.15 presents the grid search results, where (i) the LBFGS optimization algorithm is responsible for the best result for all activation functions and size of the hidden layer, (ii) the ReLU together with LBFGS seems to be the best combination for the training set. The validation curve [75] for the ANN size can be seen in Figure 2.16a, where it can be seen that the optimal value ($R^2 = 0.965$ for training and $R^2 = 0.964$ for cross-validation) is obtained for 16 neurons. The influence of the training database size was also analysed [75] using the 16-hidden nodes configuration. However, Figure 2.16b shows that the increase of the training samples database does not improve the model because both the training and cross-validation R^2 seemed to converge after 4000 training samples. The regularization term λ was also tuned using the same procedure [75]. It can be seen in Figure 2.16c that a regularization term lower than 10^{-2} should be used in

Figure 2.15: Combination of different optimization algorithms, activation functions and ANN hidden layer size used in a grid search approach. Topologies of (a) 4, (b) 10, (c) 16 and (d) 22 hidden neurons.

both training and cross-validation.

Figure 2.16: Analysis of (a) the ANN-model hidden layer size, (b) training sample database size and (c) regularization term λ .

Testing the trained model in an FEA simulation

The ANN model was implemented in the Abaqus standard (implicit) FEA code using a UMAT user routine. Although the UMATs are written in Fortran, here, a call for a python script was used. The advantage of using a differential ANN model is that the FEA time integration is straightforward. Nevertheless, small-time increments were used due to the non-use of a consistent stiffness matrix.

The goal of the ANN model is to be tested in a simulation environment. Therefore, for that purpose, a heterogeneous mechanical test named adapted butterfly specimen [76] and illustrated in Figure 2.17a is used. Although not represented in Figure 2.17b, a tool displacement of 9.6 mm is imposed on the top of the specimen. Symmetry conditions are considered in both x and y axis allowing to represent only 1/4 of the specimen. 2D 4-node bilinear elements (CPS4) are used with an element size of 0.75 mm, as can be seen in Figure 2.17c. A fixed increment size of 0.2 was used for a total time of 5 seconds.

This specimen has the advantage of producing heterogeneous stress fields, as seen in Figure 2.17d. Three points were selected to assess the accuracy of the ANN model and compared with the results obtained using the virtual material modelled by the Chaboche elasto-viscoplastic model. It must be noted that the ANN model was trained with the virtual material using only two tensile and one simple shear test.

Figure 2.17: Adapted butterfly specimen [40,77]: (a) CAD geometry (in mm), (b) loading conditions, (c) numerical mesh and (d) the von Mises equivalent stress distribution obtained at the end of the test using the ANN model. Localization of the selected point for analysis.

Table 2.7 compare the values of the stress and backstress tensors and isotropic hardening/drag stress for the three selected points of Figure 2.17d at the end of the test. Here, the experiment values correspond to the virtual material experiments. In general, the ANN model can reproduce fairly well the virtual material. However, although lower errors can be seen for σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} (16% and 0.75%) and their correspondent backstress in the first two points, higher errors were obtained for the shear stress component. Nevertheless, these results can be explained that, for this point, $\varepsilon = \{-0.0914, 0.2008, 0.0442\}$ and the ANN-model was never trained with so complex strain field and only with a maximum strain of 0.16. For points 2 and 3, the performance of the ANN model is better because the strain values are lower. It must be highlighted that the larger error for point 2 is 8%.

Table 2.8 compares the equivalent plastic strain and the viscoplastic strain tensor at the end of the test for the selected three points. Again, the performance of the ANN-model is fairly good, however, it is the shear strain that present the worst results (errors larger than 20%).

Table 2.7: Comparison between the ANN-model and the (virtual) experimental values at the end of the Butterfly test for selected points: stress comparison.

		σ_{xx}	σ_{yy}	τ_{xy}	χ_{xx}	χ_{yy}	χ_{xy}	R
		[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[MPa]
Point 1 ●	ANN	283.88	533.31	69.08	-100.18	101.41	3.49	81.97
	Experiment	243.42	537.35	37.83	-95.94	95.94	23.94	82.81
	Error [%]	16.62	0.75	82.61	4.42	5.7	85.42	1.01
Point 2 ▲	ANN	-29.96	180.21	0.96	-64.34	64.08	1.72	52.49
	Experiment	-25.78	180.33	1.05	-69.35	69.35	0.77	53.35
	Error [%]	0.16	0.07	8.57	7.22	7.60	0.01	1.61
Point 3 ★	ANN	0.62	163.06	7.47	-48.62	48.28	1.25	51.80
	Experiment	-0.66	168.67	6.61	-52.11	52.11	4.18	52.07
	Error [%]	193.94	3.33	13.01	6.7	7.35	70.1	0.52

The evolution of σ during the test for the selected points when using the ANN-model can be seen in Figure 2.18. The experimental evolution of the virtual material is also added for comparison purposes. Although it is observed that both σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} evolution reproduces well the behaviour of the virtual material, ANN- τ_{xy} fails to foresee the experimental curve. This fact can be attributed to the absence of complex shear states in the training data.

The other internal state variables were also assessed and compared. Figure 2.19 present the time evolution of the viscoplastic strain tensor, equivalent plastic strain, backstress tensor and the isotropic hardening/drag stress. In a general overview, it can be stated that the ANN-model curves can fit the virtual experiments. However, larger computational times ($> 20\times$) were observed in comparison with the reference model.

Table 2.8: Comparison between the ANN-model and the (virtual) experimental values at the end of the Butterfly test for selected points: strain comparison.

		ε_{xx}^{vp}	ε_{yy}^{vp}	ε_{xy}^{vp}	p
Point 1 ●	ANN	-1.162×10^{-1}	1.111×10^{-1}	8.266×10^{-3}	1.313×10^{-1}
	Experiment	-1.079×10^{-1}	1.079×10^{-1}	2.452×10^{-2}	1.262×10^{-1}
	Error[%]	7.69	2.97	66.29	4.04
Point 2 ▲	ANN	-9.948×10^{-3}	1.055×10^{-2}	1.798×10^{-4}	1.162×10^{-2}
	Experiment	-1.077×10^{-2}	1.077×10^{-2}	1.400×10^{-4}	1.244×10^{-2}
	Error[%]	7.63	2.04	28.43	6.59
Point 3 ★	ANN	-7.230×10^{-3}	7.836×10^{-3}	9.220×10^{-5}	8.538×10^{-3}
	Experiment	-6.630×10^{-3}	6.630×10^{-3}	5.400×10^{-4}	7.670×10^{-3}
	Error[%]	9.05	18.19	82.93	11.32

Figure 2.18: Stress-strain curves obtained for the selected point of the Butterfly test: (a) $\sigma_{xx} - \varepsilon_{xx}^t$, (b) $\sigma_{yy} - \varepsilon_{yy}^t$ and (c) $\tau_{xy} - \varepsilon_{xy}^t$ curves. Comparison between the ANN-model and (virtual) experimental values.

Figure 2.19: Evolution of the internal state variables for the selected points in the Butterfly test: (a) viscoplastic strain tensor ϵ^{VP} , (b) back stress tensor χ , (c) plastic strain p and (d) isotropic (hardening/drag) stress R . Comparison between the ANN-model and (virtual) experimental values.

Final remarks

In this section, it can be seen that an ML/ANN model can be used to model the behaviour of an elasto-viscoplastic material. Here, an ANN model was effectively trained using virtually created (synthetic) data of cyclic tensile-compression and shear tests. This was successfully reproduced for 2D (plane-stress) conditions, thus achieving the main objective.

Subsequently, the ANN model was applied in an FEA simulation of complex stress-strain states using a heterogeneous mechanical test denoted Butterfly test. Even knowing that the complexity of the stress-strain field used for analysis was not used for training, the ANN model quite was able to simulate the stress-strain evolution. In conclusion, the proposed ANN model, even with different combinations of strain never used in training, is capable of reproducing the material behaviour defined by the virtual material.

Moreover, the ANN implementation in the FEA code is straightforward and no integration problems were observed even in complex geometries. This example shows the capability of ML/ANN to model the material behaviour using some concepts already used in analytical models. Although this example used synthetic data, real experimental data could be used under the same conditions.

Implicit elastoplastic modelling using the VFM

The heterogeneous test developed by Martins *et al* [3] was used to generate numerical experimental data to train the ANN model. The configuration consists of a solid 3×3 mm² plate with a thickness $t = 0.1$ mm. The domain is discretized by 9 four-node bilinear plane stress elements. The initial mesh, geometry and boundary conditions are depicted in Figure 2.20. Symmetry boundary conditions are applied to the boundaries at $x = 0$ and $y = 0$, and a surface traction is defined at $x = 3$ mm. The traction follows a non-uniform distribution, composed by a single component along the x -direction, which varies linearly in the y -direction, according to: $f_x(y) = my + b$, where m and b respectively control the distribution.

Figure 2.20: Heterogeneous test: initial geometry, mesh and boundary conditions.

The numerical simulations were conducted using the commercial finite element code Abaqus. The model was built with CPS4R elements (bilinear reduced integration plane stress). The material was simulated employing a non-linear isotropic elasto-plastic model, with the isotropic hardening response obeying to the Swift's law, given by:

$$\sigma_y = K(\varepsilon_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}^P)^n, \quad (2.16)$$

where σ_y is the flow stress, K is a hardening coefficient, n is the hardening exponent, σ_0 is the yield stress and ε_0 the deformation at the yielding point, computed as:

$$\varepsilon_0 = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{K} \right)^{1/n}. \quad (2.17)$$

The elastic parameters were defined as $E = 210$ GPa and $\nu = 0.3$, while $\sigma_0 = 160$ MPa, $K = 565$ MPa and $n = 0.26$ were adopted for the Swift's hardening law.

Data generation and ANN training

To generate the training data, all simulations were performed using a small displacement formulation, with the time period set to 1 and using a fixed time increment $\Delta t = 0.005$. For each time increment, the deformation components at the centroid were extracted for all the elements and the global force was determined by means of computing the equilibrium of the internal forces, such that:

$$FL = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i A_i t, \quad (2.18)$$

where F is the global force, L is the length of the solid, A is the element's area and t is the thickness.

The training data was generated for different load distributions, keeping the slope fixed at $m = 10$ N/mm and varying the intercept parameter, such that: $b = \{50, 170, 270\}$ N. Prior to training and for each mechanical trial, the dataset was organized into batches of 9 elements per time increment and shuffled before being split into training (80%) and test data (20%). The input features were transformed in order to follow a normal distribution with zero mean and unit variance. Two models were trained and aimed at predicting the linear elastic and elasto-plastic responses of the material. Once trained, the models were validated with different mechanical trials using the following load distributions: $m = 12$, $b = 100$ for the elastic model and $m = 12$, $b = 200$ for the elasto-plastic model.

The neural network model consisted of a simple FFNN with one hidden layer, with 4 hidden neurons for the elastic case and 8 hidden neurons for the elasto-plastic case. In both cases the Parametric Rectified Linear Unit (PReLU) activation function [78] was used. The inputs given to the models were the deformation components in the current and previous time increments, ε^t and ε^{t-1} respectively, and the outputs were the stress tensor components at the current time increment, σ^t . The ADAM algorithm was used to optimize the network weights, with the initial learning rate set to 0.1, scheduled to be reduced using a multiplier of 0.2, if no improvement in the training loss was registered after 5 epochs. For the elastic model, the network was trained during 30 epochs and for the elasto-plastic model training was set to occur during a maximum of 150 epochs.

Results and discussion

The learning curves for both models are depicted in Figure 2.21. The plots show the loss decreasing during the training epochs with convergence being achieved earlier for the elastic model. In this case, four virtual fields were used during training, while for the elasto-plastic response model a total of six virtual fields were used. The complete set of virtual fields is presented in Table 2.9 and illustrated in the appendix ??.

Table 2.9: Virtual fields used to train both ANN models. Virtual fields 1 through 4 were used to train the elastic model, while the whole set was used to trained the elastoplastic model.

Virtual field	1	2	3	4	5	6
$u_1^{*(i)}$	$\frac{x}{L}$	$\sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{3L}\right)$	$\frac{\pi y^2}{L^2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi x}{L}\right)$	$\frac{y^2}{L^2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right)$	0	0
$u_2^{*(i)}$	0	0	$-\frac{2y}{L} \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right)$	$\frac{x^2}{L^2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{L}\right)$	$\sin\left(\frac{2\pi y}{3L}\right)$	$\frac{y}{L} \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right)$
$\varepsilon_{11}^{*(i)}$	$\frac{1}{L}$	$\frac{2\pi}{3L} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{3L}\right)$	$\frac{2\pi^2 y^2}{L^3} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi x}{L}\right)$	$\frac{\pi y^2}{L^3} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right)$	0	0
$\varepsilon_{22}^{*(i)}$	0	0	$-\frac{2}{L} \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right)$	$\frac{\pi x^2}{L^3} \cos\left(\frac{\pi y}{L}\right)$	$\frac{2\pi}{3L} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi y}{3L}\right)$	$\frac{1}{L} \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right)$
$\varepsilon_{12}^{*(i)}$	0	0	0	$\frac{2y}{L^2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right) + \frac{2x}{L^2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi y}{L}\right)$	0	$\frac{2\pi y}{L^2} \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right) \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{L}\right)$

Figure 2.21: Learning curves for (a) the elastic and (b) the elasto-plastic response models.

The validation results (Figures. 2.22) show that, in general, the ANN was able to learn both elastic and elasto-plastic behaviors. In the former case, the ANN provided near-excellent stress predictions, however with a higher error being registered for the stress component in the y -direction, for the element 9 (Figure 2.22c). In the latter case, the ANN provided overall excellent predictions for the stress response along the x -direction. Although the use of additional virtual fields slightly improves the shear stress response for the plastic model (Figure 2.22b and 2.22d), it seems the ANN has a noticeable lower sensitivity to the stress responses along y and xy . The issue may be due to fact that either the number of chosen virtual fields is not enough to capture the material behavior or the chosen set of virtual fields provides more weight to the stresses along x in detriment of the remaining components. Another factor at play is that the virtual fields were chosen manually. This strategy is often used for non-linear models

and is the easiest to implement, nonetheless it does not guarantee the chosen virtual fields produce the best results and is tied to the user's expertise [3]. Additionally, it may be possible that the mechanical test considered in this example may be too simple, thus not providing enough dissimilar behaviour data. Albeit with a wide margin for further improvements in the future, this application example has effectively proven that the new methodology works.

2.1.6 Appendices

Artificial neural networks

Basic principle and components

ANNs draw inspiration from the signal processing scheme used by the neural systems that constitute animal brains. In ANNs, the signal is transmitted between the neurons over links with an associated weight, providing strength to the connection. The greatest advantage of ANNs is their ability to learn from examples and describe complex non-linear, multi-dimensional relationships in a dataset, without any prior assumptions [49]. ANNs not only possess the ability to make decisions based on incomplete and disordered data, but are also able to generalize rules and apply them to new, previously unseen, data. Both the network architecture and the learning method adopted to train the ANN model have a significant impact in the accuracy of the model's predictions [57,79].

Network topology

Multi-layer neural networks are, in essence, perceptrons with more than one computational layer (Figure 2.23b) [80]. The input layer receives the data and the output layer sends the information out, while the hidden layers provide the required complexity for nonlinear problems [41,79]. The signal flows uniquely in one direction, therefore multi-layer networks are also referred to as Feedforward Neural Networks (FFNNs). FFNNs are commonly used for function approximation, defining a mapping of the type $y = f(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{W})$ in which the network will learn the value of the parameters w_{ij} that provide the best approximation [57]. FFNNs may be thought of as a composition of several different functions, connected in a chain structure of the form [41,57]:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = f^{(k)}(\dots f^{(2)}(f^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}))), \quad (2.19)$$

where, $f^{(1)}$ corresponds to the first layer, $f^{(2)}$ to the second layer and so on, for an arbitrary network with k layers [41,57]. The length of the chain provides the depth of the model, that is, the number of layers [41,57]. Each hidden layer is typically vector-valued and their dimensionality, given by the number of neurons, determines the width of the model. According to Cybenko [81] a neural network requires at most two hidden layers to approximate any function to an arbitrary order of accuracy and only one hidden layer to approximate a bounded continuous function to arbitrary accuracy. For this reason, neural networks are often referred to as universal function approximators [19]. In practice, however, the main issue is that the number of hidden units required to do so is rather large, which increases the number of parameters to be learned. This results

(d) Elastoplastic model - element #9: $m = 12$, $b = 200$

Figure 2.22: Stress-strain curves corresponding to the elements 1 and 9, for the ANN-based elastic and elastoplastic response models.

in problems in training the network with a limited amount of data. Deeper networks with a lower number of hidden units in each layer are often preferred [41].

Figure 2.23: Basic architectures of (a) the perceptron and (b) a multi-layer feedforward network.

Different network topologies were formulated as variants of FFNNs and became popular in the last two decades [82]: Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory Neural Networks (LSTMs). Typically, in CNNs, a convolutional layer moves across the data, similar to a filter in computer vision algorithms, requiring only a few parameters, as the convolving layer allows for effective weight replication [83]. LSTMs, a variation of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), offers specialized memory neurons with the purpose of dealing with the vanishing gradient problem. The latter, often leads to sub-optimal local minima especially as the number of neuronal layers increases [82].

Mathematical representation

Consider a case where each training instance of a given dataset has the form (\mathbf{x}, y) , where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is an input vector containing the set of input features $[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ and y is the observed value, obtained as a part of the training data. Given a FFNN of arbitrary architecture, as shown in Figure 2.24, the dimensionality of the feature vector \mathbf{x} dictates the number of neurons in the input layer [41]. These inputs are mapped to the next layers with m neurons, triggering a set of activations $\mathbf{a}^{(k)} = \{a_1^{(k)}, \dots, a_m^{(k)}\} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, with $a_m^{(k)}$ denoting the activation of the m^{th} neuron in the network's k^{th} layer. The activation potential from layer $(k - 1)$ to layer k is controlled by a matrix of parameters $\mathbf{W}^{(k)} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ and computed as the weighted sum of the output values $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ from the incoming connections. A function $g(\cdot)$ is then applied to this weighted sum, leading to the activations of the k^{th} layer being computed as:

$$\mathbf{a}^{(k)} = g\left(\mathbf{W}^{(k)}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}^{(k)}\right). \quad (2.20)$$

A set of biases $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is added as the weight of a link, which in practice means incorporating a bias neuron that conventionally transmits a value of 1 to the output

Figure 2.24: Multi-layer feedforward neural network with one output and n inputs.

node [41]. In essence, in a FFNN, the n -dimensional input vector \mathbf{x} is transformed into the outputs using the following recursive relations [41, 84]:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{a}^{(1)} = g(\mathbf{W}^{(1)}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}^{(1)}) & \text{input to hidden layer} \\ \mathbf{a}^{(p+1)} = g(\mathbf{W}^{(p+1)}\mathbf{a}^{(p)} + \mathbf{b}^{(p+1)}) \quad \forall p \in \{1, \dots, k-1\} & \text{hidden to hidden layer} \\ \mathbf{o} = g(\mathbf{W}^{(k+1)}\mathbf{a}^{(k)} + \mathbf{b}^{(k+1)}) & \text{hidden to output layer} \end{cases} \quad (2.21)$$

In the above expressions, $g(\cdot)$ is an activation function, a mathematical entity that receives the output of the weighted sum as an input and converts that into the final output of a node [41, 57]. There are several different types of activation functions and their selection is an important part of the design process of a neural network. The most common activation functions [41, 84] are shown in Figure 2.25. Worthy of note is the fact that all the activation functions shown are monotonic. Moreover, other than the identity function, most of them saturate at large absolute values of the argument. The use of nonlinear activation functions greatly increases the modelling capabilities of a neural network [41, 57].

Figure 2.25: Most commonly used activation functions: (a) sigmoid, (b) hyperbolic tangent and (c) rectified linear unit (ReLU).

Historically, both the sigmoid and \tanh functions have been the popular choices to

incorporate non-linearity in the neural network. However, in recent years, the preference has been directed towards a family of piecewise linear functions, such as the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) and its variations. Due to their simplicity, these functions are easier to differentiate, thus providing a faster training process [41].

Learning paradigms and training procedures

The training of an ANN is accomplished through a learning procedure, during which sample data is fed to the network and a learning algorithm is in charge of modifying a set of parameters, in order for the ANN to provide the best possible prediction [12]. There are essentially two learning paradigms: unsupervised learning and supervised learning [57]. Unsupervised learning is concerned with finding patterns in unlabeled datasets containing many features. Supervised learning is the most widespread method to train ANNs and uses labeled datasets, where each training sample is linked to a label [57, 84]. The process is similar to a standard fitting procedure, accompanied by the selection of a learning algorithm that is used to fit target value [12, 57]. The main task relates to data generation and preparation in order to ensure the dataset is both accurate and consistent. The main dataset is split into various subsets, mainly a training and a test set. Additionally, a validation set, different from the latter ones may be used to optimize the hyper-parameters [12]. The following step is concerned with translating the raw information into meaningful features that can be used as inputs for the ANN. Finally, the model is trained by optimizing its performance, that is, finding the set of parameters (\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b}) that minimizes a given loss function [12]. For regression tasks, the Mean Squared Error (MSE) is commonly employed, being written as:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b}) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=0}^m \left(\mathbf{y}^{(i)} - \hat{\mathbf{y}}^{(i)} \right)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i=1}^{s_k} \sum_{j=1}^{s_{k+1}} (\mathbf{W}_{ji}^{(k)})^2, \quad (2.22)$$

where m is the total number of training instances, k is the number of layers, s_k is the number of neurons on the k^{th} layer and s_{k+1} is the number of neurons on the $(k+1)^{\text{th}}$ layer. There is a wide variety of optimization algorithms available to minimize $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b})$. A gradient-based algorithm (e.g. gradient descent or Adaptive moment estimation (ADAM)) is normally used to minimize the loss, by subsequently moving in the direction of the negative gradient [41].

The parameters' update is driven by first taking the partial derivatives of $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{b})$, such that [57]:

$$d\mathbf{W}^{(k)} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{W}^{(k)}}, \quad (2.23)$$

$$d\mathbf{b}^{(k)} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \mathbf{b}^{(k)}} \quad (2.24)$$

and repeatedly apply [57]:

$$\mathbf{W}^{(k)} := \mathbf{W}^{(k)} - \alpha d\mathbf{W}^{(k)}, \quad (2.25)$$

$$\mathbf{b}^{(k)} := \mathbf{b}^{(k)} - \alpha d\mathbf{b}^{(k)}, \quad (2.26)$$

until convergence is achieved, with $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ being the learning rate, a hyper-parameter controlling how quickly the model is adapted to the problem [57]. Small learning rates

slowdown training and can cause the optimizer to premature convergence. Larger learning rates speed up training and require fewer training epochs, however the model can overshoot the minimum, fail to converge or even diverge [41, 57]. More complex algorithms have the ability to subsequently adapt the learning rate on each iteration.

An important challenge to overcome during neural network training is overfitting. The phenomenon happens when a particular model perfectly fits the available data, but lacks the generalization power necessary to make predictions from unseen data [42]. A model's propensity to overfit can be controlled by changing its capacity, which is determined by the number of learnable parameters of the neural network (e.g. the number of layers and the number of neurons per layer) [41, 42]. Generally speaking, increasing the number of training instances may improve the generalization power of the model, whereas increasing the capacity of the model often reduces its generalization power [42]. Weight regularization is commonly used to prevent overfitting and consists on adding a penalty of the form $\lambda \|\mathbf{W}^p\|$ to the loss function, with λ being a regularization parameter. Depending on the value of p there are two types of regularization [41]:

- *L1 regularization*: the penalty is proportional to the L1 norm of the weighting coefficients;
- *L2 regularization*: the penalty is proportional to the L2 norm of the weighting coefficients.

An example of L2 regularization can be seen in the last part of Equation 2.22, where the penalty has the value of p set to 2.

Viscoplasticity

In viscoplasticity, the time-dependent effect of viscous forces is unified with the plastic deformation via a viscoplastic term, such that [25, 33, 85]:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^e + \varepsilon^p + \varepsilon^v = \varepsilon^e + \varepsilon^{vp}, \quad (2.27)$$

where ε^v and ε^{vp} are, respectively, the viscous and viscoplastic strains. The Chaboche's model is a popular viscoplastic model in which the viscoplastic potential is written in terms of a power function of f , from Equation 2.5 [85]. The model takes into account both kinematic and isotropic hardening effects, under stationary temperature conditions. The viscoplastic strain rate tensor $\dot{\varepsilon}^{vp}$ and the plastic strain rate \dot{p} are defined as follows [33, 85]:

$$\dot{\varepsilon}^{vp} = \frac{3}{2} \dot{p} \frac{\boldsymbol{\sigma}' - \boldsymbol{\chi}'}{J(\boldsymbol{\sigma}' - \boldsymbol{\chi}')}, \quad (2.28)$$

$$\dot{p} = \left\langle \frac{J(\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \boldsymbol{\chi}) - R - k}{K} \right\rangle^n, \quad (2.29)$$

where k , R , K and n are the initial yield stress, isotropic hardening and two material constants, respectively, whereas $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$ and $\boldsymbol{\chi}'$ are the deviatoric parts of the stress and backstress tensors [33, 85]. The $J(\boldsymbol{\sigma}' - \boldsymbol{\chi}')$ invariant is computed through the following formula:

$$J(\boldsymbol{\sigma}' - \boldsymbol{\chi}') = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}' - \boldsymbol{\chi}') : (\boldsymbol{\sigma}' - \boldsymbol{\chi}')}. \quad (2.30)$$

The kinematic hardening rate $\dot{\chi}$ is defined by means of a partial differential equation, given as:

$$\dot{\chi} = \frac{2}{3} a \dot{\epsilon}^{\text{VP}} c \chi \dot{p}, \quad (2.31)$$

while the isotropic hardening rate is calculated from:

$$\dot{R} = b(R_1 - R)\dot{p}. \quad (2.32)$$

The variables a , b , c and R_1 are material parameters, which must be identified for each material.

2.2 Final remarks

This paper presents and discusses the recent advances and applications of ML, particularly ANNs, in metal forming processes, from which the following points can be highlighted:

- ANNs provide an opportunity for a complete change of paradigm in the field of constitutive modelling. Their powerful capabilities allow to devise material models without the need to formulate complicated symbolic expressions that, conventionally, require extensive parameter calibration procedures;
- Nevertheless, even in calibration/parameter identification procedures, the power and potential of ANN can still be used. This paper showed that an ANN can be trained as an inverse model for parameter identification.
- ANNs are paving the way for the development of implicit material models capable of reproducing complex material behavior purely from data. Additionally, the network architectures themselves can be designed based on the structure of existing well-known constitutive models;
- A great number of methodologies employ ANNs as “black boxes” that are not guaranteed to respect the basic laws of physics governing the dynamics of the systems, thus requiring large amounts of training to do so. This is, an important issue due to the cost of data acquisition being often prohibitive and time-consuming;
- Considerable efforts have been done to improve the generalization capacity of the ANN-based implicit constitutive models, either by the development of new architectures, more robust training procedures or through the augmentation of the datasets. The use of NANNs, for example, is an interesting approach to capture the full material response, but does not solve the underlying dependency on large datasets. On the other hand PINNs, particularly, TANNs have the potential to leverage the knowledge obtained from training data, through the direct encoding of basic thermodynamic laws in the neural network, thus resulting in models able to perform very well on low data regimes. The SPD-NN goes a step further by imposing time consistency, strain energy function convexity and the Hill’s criterion, thus solving numerical instabilities derived from coupling standard ANN-based models with FEM solvers;

- Another powerful attribute of implicit constitutive models is the ease of implementation within FE subroutines. The architecture of ANNs can be stored in the code via matrices with the appropriate dimensions, containing the optimized weights obtained during training. The ANN operations are reduced to a sequence of matrix operations that provide an almost instantaneous mapping between input and output values, providing substantial gains in computational efficiency;
- A major part of the ANN-based methodologies to implicit constitutive modelling rely on labeled data pairs (strain and stress) to train the network. However, the stress tensor is not measurable in complex experimental tests, thus requiring the ANN-based model to be trained indirectly, using only measurable data, such as displacements and global force;
- Indirect training approaches for ANN-based constitutive modelling reported in the literature resort to coupling with FEA software, in order for the numerical solver to impose the necessary physical and boundary constraints, while also allowing to take advantage of full-field data;
- A new disruptive methodology to train an ANN-based implicit constitutive model was proposed using the VFM. The new approach allows an ANN to learn both linear elastic and elastoplastic behaviors, through the application of the PVW, using only measurable data, e.g. displacements and global force, to feed the training process. An interesting advantage of this new approach is that it does not require the FEM for further calculations.

2.3 Author contributions

The author made significant contributions across multiple domains in this work. The author had a key role on conceptualizing the study, designing the test methodology and implementing it using software tools such as Abaqus and Python. The author also played a key role in the investigation process, including data analysis, result validation, and the creation of figures and charts. In addition to drafting the original manuscript, the author actively participated in revising and refining it based on feedback from the co-authors.

Chapter 3

RNN-based constitutive modelling with the Virtual Fields Method

The possibility of integrating the VFM with neural network training was shown in the previous Chapter in a very foundational state. Despite its purely academic nature, the work allowed to identify many key areas of improvement, effectively laying the foundation for a more solid approach using a robust architecture, which is now presented.

This Chapter is based on the following published paper:

R. Lourenço, P. Georgieva, E. Cueto, A. Andrade-Campos. An indirect training approach for implicit constitutive modelling using recurrent neural networks and the virtual fields method. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 425 (2024) 116961. doi: [10.1016/j.cma.2024.116961](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2024.116961)

3.1 An indirect training approach for implicit constitutive modelling using recurrent neural networks and the virtual fields method

Accurate material description is crucial to achieve high-quality results in computational analysis software. Phenomenological constitutive laws generalize the material behavior observed in simple mechanical tests. The resulting empirical expressions contain parameters that need to be calibrated through an inverse optimization process. Advancements in Digital Image Correlation (DIC) techniques have enabled the extraction of non-uniform multi-axial displacement fields, facilitating the development of heterogeneous mechanical specimens and unlocking access to richer material behavior data. Despite these advancements, constitutive models are still limited by mathematical formulations and biases due to simplifying assumptions. Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), as universal function approximators, could potentially drive a paradigm shift in the field. ANNs do not require explicit pre-formulations, hence avoiding the need for identifying unknown parameters. Moreover, ANNs are able to implicitly learn patterns

purely from data, allowing to circumvent the biases induced by the simplifying assumptions of first-order principles. However, the training of ANNs for implicit constitutive modelling is not straightforward, given the impossibility of obtaining direct measurements of stress. This paper explores the integration of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) with the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) for material modeling. This approach uses global force and displacement data to indirectly train the neural network, with the equilibrium being evaluated globally through the VFM loss function. The proposed method is (i) computationally efficient by not requiring Finite Element Analysis (FEA), (ii) compatible with both full-field measurements and numerically generated data, and (iii) able to handle experimental boundary conditions.

3.1.1 Introduction

The widespread adoption of computational analysis software in engineering, in particular Finite Element Analysis (FEA) software, has reinforced the need for precise material data, hence drawing an increased attention to the material characterization [1,2]. Traditionally, constitutive laws are derived from phenomenological observations and physical knowledge and, therefore generalize the behavior observed in basic mechanical tests [86,87]. The developed expressions contain empirical parameters that require calibration through an inverse optimization process, aimed at minimizing the discrepancy between experimental tests and numerical simulations [87]. For decades, constitutive parameter identification was limited to one-dimensional homogeneous deformation data, due to the restrictions imposed to the specimens' shapes and loading settings and the lack of high-resolution measurement equipment. In such conditions, an extensive number of experiments were often required to calibrate more complex models, which made the process expensive and time-consuming [3]. In recent years, the introduction of Digital Image Correlation (DIC) techniques allowed to extract non-uniform multi-axial displacement fields at a large number of measurement points, unlocking the development of heterogeneous mechanical specimens capable of yielding richer material behavior data (e.g. [5–8], among others). Additionally, the ability to directly link the full-field data to the FEA's discretized fields, enabled more sophisticated approaches for the identification of constitutive parameters, such as: the Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) [88] and the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) [69]. Despite the previously mentioned advancements, phenomenological constitutive models are still constrained by their mathematical formulation and are generally biased, due to the simplifying assumptions of first-order principles [10]. Moreover, a given model cannot guarantee good results in different settings from those used to calibrate it [11].

The emergence of Big Data and the exponential increase in computer processing power led to an unprecedented growth in various fields of Artificial Intelligence (AI), notably Machine Learning (ML) [12]. Among a plethora of ML algorithms, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have risen to prominence as universal function approximators [19], offering superior modelling performance across a broad spectrum of applications. ANNs have the potential to lead a paradigm shift in constitutive modelling [13]. A key advantage is that these do not require to postulate explicit formulations, eliminating the need to identify unknown constitutive parameters [14]. Furthermore, ANNs can effectively leverage vast amounts of data from full-field measurements, learning patterns implicitly and, hence, mitigating the biases inherent to conventional constitutive

models, given sufficient data and model capacity [10]. The applicability of ANNs for constitutive modelling was first explored by Ghaboussi et al. [43], who demonstrated promising results with a Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN) trained to capture the cyclic behavior of concrete. This laid the foundations for subsequent developments and the expansion to other materials, with an early application to metal behavior attributed to Furukawa and Yagawa [25], who extended the concept to viscoplasticity using a state-space representation. Notable foundational contributions also include the implementation of an ANN material into a FEA code [28] and the introduction of an analytical tangent stiffness matrix for ANN-based material models [89]. Advancements in computational resources enabled to explore more sophisticated architectures, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). RNNs are well suited for implicit constitutive modelling due to built-in memory cells that capture path-dependency effects [90].

Most approaches reported in the literature for ANN-based material modelling fall within the standard supervised learning paradigm. The training process relies on labelled data pairs, with strain tensors typically provided as input features to predict the corresponding stress state. Depending on the problem, internal variables of the traditional constitutive model (e.g. accumulated plastic strain, isotropic or kinematic hardening, or others) may additionally be used, either as features or outputs. However, these internal variables exist only numerically, lacking real experimental meaning. Moreover, stress is impossible to be measured from complex heterogeneous mechanical specimens. Even from simple uni-axial homogeneous tests, stress is obtained from indirect calculations and assumptions, such as theoretical boundary conditions. In a context where real experimental data is used to train the ANN model, such limitation imposes the training process to be carried out indirectly. Therefore, the training dataset must be composed of measurable variables only, such as displacements and/or strains and global force. During training, the variable of interest, usually the stress, is not directly taken into account in the computation of the loss function and it may be indirectly obtained from intermediate calculations. Within the framework of indirect training, this paper proposes an innovative approach by coupling the VFM with a RNN for material modelling. This allows the use of global force and displacement data to indirectly train the neural network, with the equilibrium being evaluated globally through the VFM loss function. The main advantages of this approach are: (i) the computational efficiency gained from the non-use of FEA, (ii) the compatibility with both full-field measurements and numerically generated data and (iii) the independence of the boundary conditions.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 3.1.2 provides an introduction to RNNs with gated recurrent units (GRUs) and the corresponding mathematical background. In Section 3.1.3, the VFM is introduced as well as its theoretical background. The coupled RNN-VFM indirect training methodology is also presented. Section 3.1.4 provides details about numerical implementation, data generation and training procedures. Finally, in section 3.1.5, the indirect training methodology is validated against the standard supervised approach. Results from the RNNs inference on the validation data and the corresponding FEA implementations as material models are presented and discussed.

3.1.2 GRU-based RNNs

Introduction

Modelling path dependent plasticity using ANNs is a challenging task due to the history dependency effect [90]. Standard feed-forward architectures are unable to capture the phenomenon, as there is no mechanism to establish a relationship between the inputs in the current time step with the outputs from previous time steps [56,91]. The interplay between past and present states is a suitable use case for RNNs. These networks have cyclic connections that allow to maintain a memory of previous inputs (see Figure 5.2b), making them ideal for tasks involving sequential or time-dependent data [92], in which material behavior modelling is included. Within this scope, using strain sequences with a history of k length, up to the current time step t , a RNN can capture temporal dependencies, allowing it to predict the corresponding stress state accurately. These capabilities have resulted in a slew of works reported in the field [53–56,90,91,93].

Mathematical formulation

To take advantage of RNNs for implicit constitutive modelling, in the present work a variant known as Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) is employed. GRUs are a streamlined version of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) units, designed to capture dependencies in sequential data efficiently, while mitigating some of the computational complexity [94]. As observed in Figure 5.2a, a basic GRU cell comprises the following key components [94,95]:

1. **Update gate** (\mathbf{z}_t) - determines how much is retained from the previous hidden state and how much it should be updated with new information:

$$\mathbf{z}_t = \text{sig}(\mathbf{W}_{xz}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xz} + \mathbf{W}_{hz}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hz}) \quad (3.1)$$

2. **Reset gate** (\mathbf{r}_t) - specifies which information from the previous hidden state should be forgotten:

$$\mathbf{r}_t = \text{sig}(\mathbf{W}_{xr}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xr} + \mathbf{W}_{hr}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hr}) \quad (3.2)$$

3. **New gate** (\mathbf{n}_t) - computes a new candidate hidden state based on the input and previous hidden state:

$$\mathbf{n}_t = \tanh(\mathbf{W}_{xn}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xn} + \mathbf{r}_t \odot [\mathbf{W}_{hn}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hn}]) \quad (3.3)$$

4. **Final state** (\mathbf{h}_t) - combines the previous hidden state and the new memory content, controlled by the update gate:

$$\mathbf{h}_t = (1 - \mathbf{z}_t) \odot \mathbf{n}_t + \mathbf{z}_t \odot \mathbf{h}_{t-1} . \quad (3.4)$$

The variables \mathbf{h}_t and \mathbf{x}_t are, respectively, the hidden state and the input at time t , while $\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}$ is the hidden state at time $t - 1$, or the initial hidden state at $t = 0$. The entities sig and tanh are, respectively, the sigmoid and the hyperbolic tangent activation functions and the operator \odot is the Hadamard product. The weight matrices \mathbf{W} and bias vectors \mathbf{b} are appended with double indices identifying the mapping between the

different components of the GRU cell. A deeper description of these mathematical entities and their corresponding dimensions, in the context of the present work, is provided in Table 5.1.

The hidden state \mathbf{h} is the key element behind the flow of information relating previous time steps and future predictions. In a way analogous to the internal variables of classical constitutive laws, \mathbf{h} carries the information about the current plastic state of the material [93]. The GRU cells can be combined with layers of different types in order to build specific architectures.

Figure 3.1: Schematic representation of (a) a standard GRU cell and (b) an unrolled recurrent neural network.

Table 3.1: Mathematical entities, and corresponding dimensions, for a GRU-based RNN, where: n is the batch size, k the sequence length, n_{cells} the number of GRU cells, s_{in} the input size, s_{out} the output size and s_{hid} the hidden size.

Component	Entity	Dimensions	Description
Input	\mathbf{x}_t	$(n \times k \times s_{\text{in}})$	Strain sequences
Previous state	\mathbf{h}_{t-1}	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time $t - 1$
Final state	\mathbf{h}_t	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time t
Output	$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_t$	$(n \times s_{\text{out}})$	Stress tensor at time t
Update gate	$\mathbf{W}_{x(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{in}})$	Input to hidden weights of 1st GRU cell
Reset gate or		$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input to hidden weights of i -th GRU cell
New gate	$\mathbf{b}_{x(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input to hidden bias
$(\mathbf{z}_t \mathbf{r}_t \mathbf{n}_t)$	$\mathbf{W}_{h(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden to hidden weights
	$\mathbf{b}_{h(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden to hidden bias

3.1.3 The virtual fields method

Introduction

The Virtual Fields Method (VFM) is a state-of-the-art technique employed in the inverse identification of phenomenological material models. First introduced by Grédiac [38], the VFM is renowned for its computational efficiency [3], with the main advantage of not requiring the Finite Element Method (FEM) for any forward calculations, avoiding the modelling of boundary conditions and the specimen's geometry [68,96]. The method is based on the Principle of Virtual Work (PVW), which states the internal virtual work, as a result of the internal forces, must be equal to the external virtual work performed by the external forces in the surface S , in the absence of body forces, such that [69,97]:

$$-\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dV + \int_{\partial V} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* dS = 0, \quad (3.5)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*$ is the virtual strain, \mathbf{u}^* is the virtual displacement, V is the volume of the solid and \mathbf{T} is the vector of loading tractions. The virtual displacements are mathematical test functions, with no real physical meaning and independent of the measured displacements, that satisfy the equilibrium from Equation 5.16 [97]. The equilibrium holds for any virtual displacement \mathbf{u}^* as long as it is continuous, piece-wise differentiable over the specimen's body and kinematically admissible, in order to satisfy the displacement boundary conditions. The virtual strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*$ are derived from the virtual displacements \mathbf{u}^* using the strain-displacement relationship [69]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* = \frac{1}{2} \left(\nabla \mathbf{u}^* + \nabla \mathbf{u}^{*\top} \right). \quad (3.6)$$

Besides the requirements previously enumerated, there are no specific rules for the choice of virtual fields, rendering the user with an infinity of fields to choose from [96]. Nevertheless, it is convenient to find an expression such that the virtual displacement \mathbf{u}^* would vanish or be constant along the boundary of prescribed displacements [68,69]. The reason behind the simplification is the fact that the traction distribution is often unknown and only the resultant force \mathbf{F} is available from the load cell. By doing so, the set of possible choices for the virtual fields are narrowed down and the computation of the external virtual work $\mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^*$ is simplified, such that [9]:

$$\mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^* = \mathbf{u}^* \int_{\partial S} \mathbf{T} dS \approx \mathbf{u}^* \cdot \mathbf{F}. \quad (3.7)$$

Worthy of note, it is the fact that the strain measurements from full-field techniques are only available at the surface of the specimen. Thus, an assumption for the through-thickness behavior of the material is necessary [96]. Since thin specimens are often employed in mechanical testing, it is common to reduce the problem to two dimensions by assuming a plane stress state, although different assumptions are possible. In that case, for a thin specimen of thickness h , Equation 5.16 may be modified into [68]:

$$-h \int_S \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dS + h \int_{\partial S} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* dL = 0, \quad (3.8)$$

where S and ∂S are, respectively, the surface and the boundary of the specimen. In full-field measurements the displacements are captured using DIC techniques in a very large number points or subsets, as such, the integral in Equation 5.19 may be approximated as a discrete sum for any time stage t . Keeping that in mind and assuming a suitable set of virtual fields is used, the identification process is carried out by minimizing a loss function with respect to the constitutive parameters \mathbf{x} defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \varepsilon) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{VFs}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{n_t} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_{pts}} \sigma^j(\mathbf{x}, \varepsilon) \cdot \varepsilon^{*j(i)} \cdot S^j - \mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^* \right)^2 \right], \quad (3.9)$$

where S^j is the area of the j -th element and n_{VFs} , n_t , n_{pts} are the numbers of virtual fields, time stages and measurement points, respectively. The choice of virtual fields constitutes a key point of the VFM with a great impact in the final solution. These virtual entities are often user-defined, nonetheless, systematic procedures are available to automatically define them, namely: the stiffness-based and the sensitivity-based virtual fields [68]. It is important to refer that the User-Defined Virtual Fields (UDVFs) are tied to the user's own expertise and intuition and do not evolve in time.

Sensitivity-based virtual fields

The concept behind the sensitivity-based virtual fields is to apply a perturbation to each of the model's parameters in order to obtain a stress sensitivity and its temporal evolution [68]. The stress field is the only quantity that depends directly on the constitutive parameters in the VFM, so the stress sensitivity maps highlight areas that strongly depend on a given parameter [98]. The spatial sensitivity of stress to each model parameter may be computed as:

$$\delta \sigma^{(i)}(\mathbf{x}, \varepsilon, t) = \sigma(\varepsilon, \mathbf{x}, t) - \sigma(\varepsilon, \mathbf{x} + \delta x_i, t), \quad (3.10)$$

with i being the i -th term of the constitutive model parameters \mathbf{x} and t the time stage. The virtual displacements \mathbf{u}^* are found solving the following system of equations applied to a virtual mesh [98]:

$$\delta \sigma^{(i)} = \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u}^{*(i)}, \quad (3.11)$$

where \mathbf{B} is the global strain-displacement matrix, used to map the virtual displacements at the nodes to every virtual strain. Considering a virtual mesh of bi-linear quadrilateral elements, \mathbf{B} results from the assembly:

$$\mathbf{B} = \bigwedge_{e=1}^{n_e} \mathbf{B}^e, \quad (3.12)$$

where n_e is the number of elements in the mesh and \mathbf{B}^e is the element strain-displacement matrix, defined through the spatial derivatives of the standard bi-linear nodal shape

functions \mathbf{N}^e in the coordinate space (x, y) , such that [99]:

$$\mathbf{N}^e = \begin{bmatrix} N_1(x, y) \\ N_2(x, y) \\ N_3(x, y) \\ N_4(x, y) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{4} \begin{bmatrix} (1-x)(1-y) \\ (1+x)(1-y) \\ (1+x)(1+y) \\ (1-x)(1+y) \end{bmatrix}, \text{ thus} \quad (3.13)$$

$$\mathbf{B}^e = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} & 0 & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial x} & 0 & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial x} & 0 & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial x} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial y} & 0 & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial y} & 0 & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial y} & 0 & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3.14)$$

If the displacement is prescribed at the boundaries, the traction is unknown and, as such, the displacements must be set to zero. On the other hand, if the traction distribution is unknown but the resultant force is known, a constant virtual displacement is set at the boundaries. By applying these constraints, a modified global strain-displacement matrix \mathbf{B} is obtained and the virtual displacements \mathbf{u}^* can finally be computed as follows [68]:

$$\mathbf{u}^{*(i)} = \text{pinv}(\mathbf{B})\delta\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(i)}, \quad (3.15)$$

with $\text{pinv}(\mathbf{B})$ being the pseudo-inverse of the modified strain-displacement matrix. The virtual strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*$ are then computed as:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*(i)} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}^{*(i)}. \quad (3.16)$$

The identification process is carried out, with the virtual fields $\mathbf{u}^{*(i)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*(i)}$ being updated multiple times in order to minimize the loss resulting from enforcing the PVW, within an infinitesimal strain framework, as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{VFS}} \left[\frac{1}{(\boldsymbol{\alpha}^{(i)})^2} \sum_{t=1}^{n_t} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_{pts}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^j(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}, t) \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*j(i)}(t) \cdot S^j - \mathbf{W}_{ext}(t) \right)^2 \right], \quad (3.17)$$

with S^j being the surface area of the j -th measurement point and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^{(i)}$ the scaling factor of the i -th virtual field, employed to guarantee similar magnitudes between different virtual fields.

Coupled RNN-VFM for indirect training

Within the framework of indirect training only a handful of works were reported in the literature. For example, Xu et al. [60] proposed a symmetric positive definite neural network (SPD-NN) to predict the Cholesky factors of the tangent stiffness, with the stress tensor being computed in an incremental form from intermediate steps. Although the method provides numerically stable solutions, it applies exclusively to the non-linear

segment of the material response and plasticity has to be identified through a transition function, relying on an estimate of the yield stress given by the user. Both Huang et al. [64] and Xu et al. [65] proposed a method using an ANN to replace the constitutive model in a FEA solver. The solver imposes the physical constraints during training, enabling the ANN to learn material behaviour. Similarly, Liu et al. [67] proposed integrating an ANN with FEA to form a coupled mechanical system, with inputs and outputs being determined at each incremental step. These approaches work in a way similar to the FEMU method and, while the physical correctness of the network's predictions is guaranteed, the first drawback is the need to write a FEM code based on an automatic differentiation package (e.g., Pytorch or TensorFlow), making the FEA step time-consuming. A second drawback, is the need to run multiple FEA simulations run per epoch, rendering the ANN training computationally demanding. In the domain of hyperelasticity, Huang et al. [64] proved that an ANN could be made thermodynamically consistent by predicting the hyperelastic energy instead of the stress tensor, which was computed by automatic differentiation. A similar earlier approach was shown by Man and Furukawa [26] using an energy-based loss function to indirectly train an ANN. Thakolkaran et al. [86] used an ensemble of Input Convex Neural Networks (ICNNs) to successfully learn the constitutive response of a set of well-known hyperelastic constitutive models, resorting only to full-field data. Still in the framework of hyperelasticity, in a recent work by Jeong et al. [100] an ensemble of four independent Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) was employed to extract the material behavior from full-field data, with physical constraints being encoded within a multi-objective loss. Despite the promising results and generalization capacity shown from the last two approaches, both resort to training several independent neural network models, which adds complexity. On another recent work in the domain of hyperplasticity, Franke et al. [101] employ an advanced energy-momentum scheme for time discretization to improve the performance of a Physics-Augmented Neural Network (PANN) in dynamical simulations, ensuring energy and momentum conservation. The authors report excellent results, however it is not clear their approach is applicable to real experimental data. Finally, notable contributions by Flaschel et al., aimed at the unsupervised discovery of an explicit closed form expression of the yield surface of a certain category of materials [102] and its extension to a general class of materials [103]. These approaches ensure physically consistent solutions, however, the authors still resort to several assumptions about the existence of internal history variables and the explicit formulations of the models.

In the current work a novel approach is proposed by coupling the VFM with a single GRU-based RNN model (Figure 5.1). By doing so, one can use force and displacement data to indirectly train the neural network. The strains can be obtained from the spatial gradient of the displacements and fed as inputs to the RNN material model \mathcal{M} , which will provide the stress components. Then, during training, the equilibrium can be evaluated globally by the application of the PVW. The network's parameters are searched until the gap between the internal and the external parts of the virtual work is minimized. This methodology benefits from all the advantages of the VFM, while being compatible with experimental data coming from full-field measurements and allows to predict the full elastoplastic material response employing only one RNN model. The possibility of integrating the VFM with neural network training had previously been shown by the authors in a very foundational state on a limited-page conference

paper [13]. Despite the purely academic nature, the work allowed to identify many key areas of improvement, effectively laying the foundation for a more solid approach, which is now hereby presented.

Figure 3.2: Coupled RNN-VFM indirect training method for implicit constitutive modelling, using sensitivity-based virtual fields.

3.1.4 Materials and methods

Numerical DIC database

Synthetic data to train the RNN models was gathered from a set of FEA simulations of a displacement-driven heterogeneous biaxial test, using a cruciform specimen with a thickness $h = 1$ mm and dimensions specified in Figure 5.4b [9]. Due to geometric symmetries only one fourth of the specimen was modelled. Symmetry boundary conditions were defined at the edges $y = 0$ and $x = 0$, with displacements being prescribed at each arm of the specimen, as depicted in Figure 5.4c. Several virtual experiments were generated with displacements of different magnitudes (in mm) being prescribed in paired combinations from the set:

$$(u_x, u_y) \in \{0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0\}. \quad (3.18)$$

The FEA simulations were carried out with Abaqus Standard software, assuming plane stress conditions and a small strain formulation. Regarding the material behavior, isotropic hardening was considered, with the flow stress evolving according to the Swift's law:

$$\sigma_y = K(\varepsilon_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}^P)^n, \text{ with} \quad \varepsilon_0 = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{K}\right)^{1/n} \quad (3.19)$$

where σ_y is the flow stress, $\bar{\varepsilon}^P$ the equivalent plastic strain, σ_0 the initial yield stress, K and n are material-specific hardening parameters. For the purpose, a soft steel material was considered, characterized by the set of constitutive parameters listed in Table 5.3.

The geometry was discretized using CPS4R elements and the mesh was refined according to a convergence study, from which an average element size of 0.52 mm was

chosen, resulting in a total of 2121 elements. Similar refinement levels are cited in the literature for this type of specimen ([9, 104], among others). The reduced integration elements were chosen in order to simulate DIC subsets from full-field measurements, thus, all the necessary field output variables were extracted at the centroid of the element. For each time step, the strain and stress tensors were extracted for all the elements and the resultant force applied at each of the specimen's arms was computed from the equilibrium of the internal forces, through the following:

$$Fl = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i A_i h, \quad (3.20)$$

where F is the global force, l the length of the specimen, n is the number of elements, A is the area of the element and h the thickness.

Table 3.2: Constitutive parameters for the soft steel material.

E [GPa]	ν	σ_0 [MPa]	K [MPa]	n
210	0.33	160	565	0.26

Figure 3.3: Biaxial test virtual experiment setup: (a) general dimensions of the cruciform specimen, (b) set of applied boundary conditions and (c) chosen mesh density.

From the generated dataset, a total of 36 virtual experiments were randomly selected and split in half, such that one part was used for training and the remaining part for validation. The training set was split such that 80% of the included virtual experiments were used for training and the remaining 20% for testing. Scaling of the deformation input data was performed by first computing the mean and variance of each component of the strain tensor, in the training dataset, and then applying the following transformation (i.e. mean normalization):

$$\varepsilon' = \frac{\varepsilon - \boldsymbol{\mu}}{\mathbf{s}}, \quad (3.21)$$

where ε' is the scaled strain tensor, $\boldsymbol{\mu} = [\mu_{\varepsilon_{xx}} \ \mu_{\varepsilon_{yy}} \ \mu_{\varepsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of mean values and $\mathbf{s} = [s_{\varepsilon_{xx}} \ s_{\varepsilon_{yy}} \ s_{\varepsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of variances of the strain tensor components,

respectively. The statistical variables μ and \mathbf{s} were saved in order to later apply the same transformation to the test set and during inference on the validation set, prior to organizing the data into strain sequences. For each virtual experiment, the inputs have dimensions $[n_{\text{pts}} \times n_t \times k \times 3]$, where n_{pts} is the number of measurement points, i.e. the number of elements, n_t is the number of time stages, k the RNN sequence length and the last dimension is the number of strain components.

ANN architecture

An implicit material model was developed based on a RNN consisting of an array of two GRU layers, followed by a fully-connected hidden layer with 32 neurons. The recurrent architecture processes strain data in the form of time sequences, unfolded using a sliding window of width $k = 4$ time steps. Each sequence took into account the strain components of the last three time stages up to, and including, the current stage t . For each mechanical test, a padding of zeros was prepended to the initial time stage, allowing the strain sequencing to be initiated from that point in order to avoid loss of information for the first four time steps. A schematic representation of the architecture is depicted in Figure 5.3.

Figure 3.4: GRU-based RNN architecture for material behavior modelling. Sequences of length $k = 4$ of the components from the scaled strain tensor $\varepsilon' = [\varepsilon'_{xx} \ \varepsilon'_{yy} \ \varepsilon'_{xy}]$ are taken as input features and mapped to the stress tensor $\sigma = [\sigma_{xx} \ \sigma_{yy} \ \tau_{xy}]$, obtained as output. The green rectangular block represents a linear fully-connected (FC) layer.

Training procedure

Two GRU-based RNN models with identical architectures and hyperparameters were trained in a Python environment using the PyTorch library. A first model (Dir-RNN) was trained employing a standard supervised learning approach, with labelled data. A second model (Ind-RNN) was trained employing the indirect training methodology based on the VFM. The transfer learning approach was initially used to validate the indirect training methodology and check the correct implementation of the VFM workflow. By doing so, it is expected that the Ind-RNN model to show faster convergence and lower error [105], benefiting from prior knowledge gained from direct training. More importantly, the loss should not degenerate if the integration of the VFM proves suitable for RNN training. For the Ind-RNN, the set of user-defined virtual fields from Table 5.4 was selected. For each virtual field, the variables W and H represent the width

and the height of the specimen, respectively, while X and Y are the material coordinates in the reference configuration. According to [9], the first two virtual fields allow to isolate each component of the external virtual work, along the x - and y -direction, thus enabling the use of the corresponding components of global force acting on each arm of the specimen. The third virtual field allows to activate all the components of stress when calculating the internal virtual work, while discarding the contribution of the external virtual work. A graphical representation of these virtual fields is available in Figure 3.5.

Table 3.3: Set of user-defined virtual fields selected to train the Ind-RNN model.

Virtual field (i)	1	2	3
$u_{xx}^{*(i)}$	$\frac{X}{W}$	0	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$u_{yy}^{*(i)}$	0	$\frac{Y}{H}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\varepsilon_{xx}^{*(i)}$	$\frac{1}{W}$	0	$\frac{\pi}{W}\cos\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\varepsilon_{yy}^{*(i)}$	0	$\frac{1}{H}$	$\frac{\pi}{H}\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\cos\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\varepsilon_{xy}^{*(i)}$	0	0	$\frac{1}{2}\left[\frac{\pi}{H}\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\cos\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right) + \frac{\pi}{W}\cos\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)\right]$

Figure 3.5: Contour maps for the components $u_{xx}^{*(i)}$ and $u_{yy}^{*(i)}$ of the selected set of user-defined virtual displacements.

Training was carried out using the Adam optimizer with a weight decay factor of 10^{-3} . A linear warmup scheduler was employed in order to increase the learning rate from an initial value of 10^{-3} up to 5×10^{-3} within the first five epochs. From that point onward, a gradual decay was applied according to a cosine annealing scheduler defined as [106,107]:

$$\eta_t = \eta_{\min} + \frac{1}{2}(\eta_{\max} - \eta_{\min}) \left(1 + \cos \left(\frac{T_{\text{cur}}}{T_{\text{max}}} \pi \right) \right), \quad (3.22)$$

where η_t is the current learning rate, η_{\min} and η_{\max} are the minimum and maximum learning rates, T_{cur} and T_{max} are the current iteration and the maximum number of iterations, respectively. The maximum learning rate η_{\max} was set to 5×10^{-3} and the minimum learning rate η_{\min} to 10^{-3} . Before each epoch, the order by which the virtual experiments were processed was shuffled. The corresponding input data was also shuffled along the first dimension and fed into the network in the form of small mini-batches of size $[66 \times n_t \times k \times 3]$ due to GPU memory limitations. The training process was set to run during a maximum of 10000 epochs, nonetheless, an early-stopping criterion was defined in order to prevent overfitting, such that training would be interrupted if no further improvement was registered in the test loss function \mathcal{L} after 500 epochs. For the Dir-RNN model the loss was based on the mean squared error between the RNN predicted stress, $\hat{\sigma} = \mathcal{M}(\theta, \varepsilon)$ and the target stress σ , defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}(\theta, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{\sigma}(\theta, \varepsilon) - \sigma)^2, \quad (3.23)$$

where n is the number of training samples. For the Ind-RNN model, the loss function from Equation 5.20 was slightly adapted for the context of implicit constitutive modelling with RNNs, where the set of trainable parameters θ can be seen, in a way, analogous to the classical model parameters \mathbf{x} , such that:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \varepsilon) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{VFs}}} \left[\sum_{t=1}^{n_t} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_{\text{pts}}} \hat{\sigma}^j(\theta, \varepsilon) \cdot \varepsilon^{*j(i)} \cdot S^j - \mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^* \right)^2 \right]. \quad (3.24)$$

According to Martins et al. [9] the VFM-based loss should be normalized by the external virtual work. However, the virtual field 3 does not contain that contribution, hence, the loss has to be normalised by the maximum value of the internal virtual work.

UMAT implementation

A second step to validate the trained RNN models, involved incorporating them as material constitutive models in the FEA program Abaqus Standard, through a custom user material subroutine (UMAT). The language of choice for the UMAT development was C++ due to the existence of an official C++ implementation of PyTorch (LibTorch). The latter offers most of the functionality of its Python counterpart while maintaining a high-level syntax, which made it easier to deal with the ANN-related operations in the C++ environment. The architecture and data flow for the UMAT implementation are described in the flowchart of Figure 5.9.

Figure 3.6: Flowchart of the UMAT-RNN implementation.

The PyTorch-based RNN models had to be converted to a serializable format in order to work in a Python-independent environment. All the RNN-related operations were kept separate from the UMAT subroutine (`umat.cpp`) and implemented in a function deployed as a dynamic-link library (DLL) (`annlib.dll`). The UMAT works as the interface between Abaqus Standard and the latter, essentially dealing with the input/output of the necessary variables and updating the strain history, which is stored as a state variable to be used on the next time step. The DLL function is invoked in the UMAT code and receives the strain history, the mean and the variance of the training data as input arguments. Within the DLL function, the strain history is converted to tensor format and scaled to have zero mean and unit variance. The RNN model is loaded persistently into memory in the code's first execution. The scaled strain history is then fed as input to the RNN in order to predict the stress tensor, which is returned as an output back to the UMAT, along with the stiffness matrix. For the latter, the user could either use the elastic stiffness matrix, provided a sufficiently small time-step during the simulation, or it could be easily computed from the RNN outputs, via an autodifferentiation method available in LibTorch. If this is the case, it should be noted that the computed jacobian may not be a symmetric positive definite matrix, which most likely would cause instabilities and convergence problems. The UMAT implementation for the ANN-based material models was validated with one-element tests, specifically uniaxial traction along x - and y -directions and a shear test.

3.1.5 Results and discussion

Learning curves

Regarding the Dir-RNN model (Figure 3.7a), both train and test losses sharply decrease during the first 50 to 100 epochs, followed by a gradual evolution for the remaining epochs of training. The oscillations exhibited by both curves reveal a certain difficulty in achieving convergence. Nonetheless, the early-stopping was triggered after 1383

epochs, saving the model state at this point with a train and test loss of 1.3182 MPa^2 and 2.2190 MPa^2 , respectively. For the Ind-RNN model (Figure 3.7b), both train and test losses show similar behavior, however the initial loss is several orders of magnitude lower and the training was interrupted much earlier, with the early-stopping criteria being triggered after only 30 epochs. The model state was saved at this point, with a train and test loss of $8.830 \times 10^{-10} \text{ J}^2$ and $2.248 \times 10^{-9} \text{ J}^2$, respectively. Although the loss functions for both models were measured in different units, the faster training and overall lower loss values of the Ind-RNN were to be expected due to the parameter transfer from the Dir-RNN model. In both cases, the gap between the train and test loss is not significant, indicating the RNNs did not overfit. Regarding the Ind-RNN model, the loss did not degenerate confirming the suitability of the integration of the VFM for RNN training.

RNN inference on validation data

To infer the quality of the RNNs predictions using unseen data, a virtual experiment with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5 \text{ mm}$ was chosen as an example from the validation dataset. Here, both the global and local stress responses are presented, with the latter being evaluated at the centroid of element no. 10. For both cases, the RNN model predictions are compared against the FEA solution and the corresponding absolute difference is shown.

Regarding the global stress response, Figures 3.8 and 3.9 show the contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 124$) of the virtual experiment. One can observe that the Dir-RNN model approximates the FEA solution quite well, exhibiting low absolute errors across the specimen, with the highest error magnitudes corresponding to key regions around the fillets near the central hole and on the lower-left corner. The Ind-RNN model shows similar levels of performance, however, its predictions are bound to higher absolute errors that spread to wider regions of the specimen, albeit with maximum magnitudes kept within reasonable levels. This model also has a slight tendency to underestimate the stress in specific regions around the central hole of the specimen, as denoted by the white blobs seen around those areas.

Looking at the results corresponding to the local stress response, Figures 3.10 and 3.11 show the stress curves predicted by the Dir-RNN and Ind-RNN models, respectively, for the whole duration of the virtual experiment. The results show the predicted curves are a near-perfect match of the FEA solution, with both models showing similar levels of performance. This is supported by the corresponding absolute error curves that register very low mean and maximum values. Nonetheless, the Ind-RNN model shows, in general, slightly higher deviations for all the stress components. This was to be expected for the indirectly-trained model. For both RNN models, the error curves appear smooth, with the exception of sharp peaks, that show around the yield transition region (aprox. $n_t \in [20, 30]$), corresponding to the highest error magnitudes. The results successfully attest the capacity of the developed GRU-based RNN models on capturing the full elastoplastic response of the material.

Figure 3.7: Learning curves for (a) the Dir-RNN model and (b) the Ind-RNN model based on the VFM.

UMAT validation

Figures 3.12 and 3.13 show the uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves obtained for the one-element tests with the UMAT implementation of the Dir-RNN and the Ind-RNN models, respectively. The curves are compared with the FEA solution and with the RNNs' inferred predictions. The corresponding absolute errors along the time stages are also shown. The results show the Dir-RNN model is capable of predicting the uniaxial behavior very well at both rolling (RD) and transverse (TD) directions with overall low absolute errors, however some numerical instabilities were detected with the test along the x -direction (RD), resulting in slight oscillations towards the final segment of the stress curve. The lowest errors are exhibited for the uniaxial traction along the y -direction (TD), especially for the UMAT-version of the Dir-RNN model. Higher deviations were registered for the shear response. Regarding the Ind-RNN model, it can be seen that its predictions provide identical results, however, high discrepancies are observed with its UMAT implementation. Once again, the lowest errors are shown for the y -direction (TD), nonetheless the model seems unable to predict the initial state correctly. The highest instabilities seem to occur for the test along the x -direction (RD). Although these results are not perfect, it is interesting to see that the RNNs were able to capture the material behavior from the biaxial experiments in such a way that they are still capable of performing relatively well in a completely different setting. The source of the instabilities is essentially of numerical nature induced by spurious predictions interfering with the equilibrium iterations. Taking this into account, although the feasibility of the proposed indirect training methodology is confirmed, it certainly would benefit of the application of constraints.

3.2 Final remarks

Figure 3.8: Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_t = 124$ of the virtual experiment with boundary conditions $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm. Comparison between the FEA solution and the Dir-RNN model predictions, with corresponding absolute difference.

Figure 3.9: Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_t = 124$ of the virtual experiment with boundary conditions $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm. Comparison between the FEA solution and the Ind-RNN model predictions, with corresponding absolute difference.

Figure 3.10: Local stress evaluated at element 10, for the virtual experiment with boundary conditions $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm. Comparison with FEA solution and Dir-RNN inference, with corresponding absolute error.

Figure 3.11: Local stress evaluated at element 10, for the virtual experiment with boundary conditions $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm. Comparison with FEA solution and Ind-RNN inference, with corresponding absolute error.

Figure 3.12: Uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves. Comparison between the FEA solution based on the Swift's law (Equation 5.26) and the UMAT implementation of the Dir-RNN model, with the corresponding absolute error along the time stages.

Figure 3.13: Uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves. Comparison between the FEA solution based on the Swift's law (Equation 5.26) and the UMAT implementation of the Ind-RNN model, with the corresponding absolute error along the time stages.

3.3 Concluding remarks

A new methodology using the VFM to indirectly train RNNs for implicit constitutive modelling was presented. The novel method was compared against the standard supervised learning approach, applied to a GRU-based RNN architecture. The purpose of the comparison was two-fold: to check the suitability of the VFM implementation when applied to neural network training and to validate the novel implementation, both as an isolated model and when incorporated in a FEA software. It was shown that the VFM-based approach using user-defined virtual fields was suitable for the context of RNN training. The predicted stress curves and contour maps from model inference confirmed that the indirectly trained model was capable of the same level of performance as the standard labelled training approach, when transfer learning was employed. Further validation studies were conducted with one-element tests, taking into consideration the incorporation of the models here presented into a FEA software. In this context, the standard model performed the best and has shown to be more stable, while the VFM-based model response was hindered by spurious predictions. These problems are expected to be solved with constrained optimization procedures in future works. However, the focus of the present paper was aimed at validating the VFM-based training methodology, which is deemed suitable for the purpose. Future analyses will also be aimed at evaluating the capabilities of the VFM-based training method, without transfer learning and further extension of the analysis with sensitivity-based virtual fields.

3.4 Author contributions

The author made significant contributions across multiple domains in this work, having played a key role on conceptualizing the study, designing the test methodology, implementing software tools in Python to automate model training and validation, developing user-material subroutines in C++ that integrate the trained RNN-based models with a FEA solver. The author also played a key role in the investigation process, including data analysis, result validation, and the creation of figures and charts. In addition to drafting the original manuscript, the author actively participated in revising and refining it based on feedback from the co-authors.

Chapter 4

Constraints and validation KPI for data-driven constitutive modelling

In the previous Chapter, the feasibility of coupling the VFM with a GRU-based RNN to indirectly learn the material behaviour was effectively proven. Nevertheless, this was demonstrated using transfer learning, which helped the indirect training model. Considering the limitations of ANNs in providing consistent physical solutions, training the RNN with unlabelled from scratch would require the use of physics-based constraints to ensure physical consistency and improve the final accuracy of the model. Moreover, the innovative character of the method required new validation procedures in order to properly select the models, assess their predictive accuracy and physical correctness, beyond the standard error metrics which don't provide all the information.

This Chapter is based on the following submitted paper:

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4.1 On the use of physics-based constraints and validation KPI for data-driven elastoplastic constitutive modelling

Constitutive modelling based on machine learning (ML) approaches has surged in last couple of decades due to novel and more robust model architectures and computational power. The dependency of these models on large amounts of training data can be mitigated by imposing some phenomenological knowledge as constraints, which also helps maintain the quality of learning. This paper highlights the importance of physics-based constraints in elastoplasticity data-driven constitutive modelling and focuses on model validation methods. Specifically, seven constraints applied to elastoplastic behaviour are identified that can be used during the model training process. To study the effects of these constraints, a set of recurrent neural network (RNN) models is trained using data from virtual mechanical experiments, based on a biaxial cruciform specimen. The models' ability to accurately learn and predict the fundamental constitutive behaviour

is then assessed using the different validation checkpoints, which include (i) statistical metrics, (ii) tests on previously unseen data, from virtual experiments based on different heterogeneous mechanical specimens, (iii) external key performance indicators (KPI) and (iv) single-element finite element analysis (FEA) tests. It was observed that the benefits of adding constraints to the training process were three-fold, resulting in (i) improved model predictive capacity, as well as (ii) enhanced extrapolation capabilities when tested on different mechanical specimens and (iii) overall improved training speed and stability. The use of independent validation KPI for data-driven constitutive modelling is highlighted and suggested as standard practice in future researches in the field.

4.1.1 Introduction

The complex behaviour of metals is related to a combination of their microstructural characteristics and the mechanisms governing their deformation and failure [33, 108]. Along the years, many constitutive laws have been proposed to model these behaviours. Conventional constitutive models are developed based on first-order principles and theoretical principles derived from empirical observations, involving many assumptions. As a result, a set of laws is translated into mathematical expressions relying on a variety of empirical parameters, which need be calibrated. Parameter calibration ensures the compatibility between the experimental and the numerically simulated response [16, 30]. As model complexity grows, the number of parameters increases requiring extensive experimental campaigns, which are expensive and time-consuming [3]. The phenomenological nature of such models means the adjacent explicit form is generally biased, due to the simplifying assumptions of first-order principles [10]. Moreover, a given model is not guaranteed to provide good results in different settings from those used to calibrate it [11].

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) have the potential to lead a paradigm shift in the field of constitutive modelling [13]. A key advantage is that ANNs do not require any assumptions about the explicit form of the model, effectively eliminating the need to identify unknown constitutive parameters [14]. As such, ANNs are able to learn patterns implicitly purely from data allowing to mitigate the biases inherent to conventional constitutive models, given sufficient data and model capacity [10]. The first attempt to explore the use of ANNs for implicit constitutive modelling is attributed to Ghaboussi et al. (1991) [43]. The authors trained a feedforward neural network (FFNN) to capture the biaxial and cyclic behaviour of concrete, reporting promising results. A pioneering application to metal behaviour was led by Furukawa and Yagawa (1998) [25], who extended the concept to viscoplasticity. The authors tested the model with experimental data and found it to be highly accurate with negligible errors. Hashash et al. (2004) [89] contributed with the development of an explicit formulation for the consistent material stiffness matrix for ANN-based constitutive models.

Modelling path-dependent plasticity using ANNs is challenging due to the history dependency effect. Simple feedforward architectures are unable to capture the phenomenon, as there is no mechanism that relates the inputs in the current time step with the outputs from previous time steps [56, 91]. In earlier works, the process involved feeding stress and strain tensors from previous time steps, along with additional in-

ternal variables of the model, as input features into a FFNN to predict the material response [25, 109, 110]. The approach resulted in added network complexity and the use of internal variables meant that some sort of assumption had to be made about the explicit form of the constitutive law. Moreover, internal variables have no real physical meaning, exist purely in a numerical sense, and are not accessible in a real experiment. Further advancements in computational resources, allowed for the development of more sophisticated network architectures, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). Contrary to FFNNs, RNNs are particularly robust for implicit constitutive modelling due to built-in memory cells that capture the effects of path-dependent behaviour [90]. Using sequences of strain tensors that spanning from a number of time stages in the past up to the current time stage t , a RNN can capture the temporal dependencies, allowing it to predict the corresponding stress state accurately. Such capabilities have resulted in a variety of works reported in the field [54–56, 91, 93, 111–113].

In general, ANN-based models require a large amount of training data in order to obtain accurate predictions. In the context of material modelling, it often involves generating large synthetic or experimental datasets. Nonetheless, a well-trained ANN is still a black-box model, which is not easy interpretable and may originate spurious non-physical responses. The issue is addressed encoding physics-based information, either by modifying the original architecture or adding extra residual terms to the loss function. The approach allows to improve both interpolation and extrapolation accuracy, helps to avoid overfitting and allows for faster training [114]. Within this context, Raissi et al. (2019) [59] firstly introduced physics-informed neural networks (PINNs), allowing the model to respect symmetries, invariances and conservation laws governing the observed data. In more recent work, Borkowski et al. (2022) [115] used regularization techniques to maintain a non-negative plastic power density throughout the loading history to maintain thermodynamic consistency. Similarly, Weber et al. (2023) [2] used constrained neural network models for elastoplasticity by incorporating material stationarity, stability, symmetry and normalization in an optimization algorithm. The results have shown improved predictive accuracy, convergence and stability. Thermodynamic principles have also been incorporated as physics-based knowledge into model architectures during training to enhance accuracy [53, 58, 116, 117]. A wide variety of studies applied to hyperelastic materials have also been presented with a strong focus on the subject. Linka et al. (2021) [118] developed an ANN model to capture the behaviour of hyperelastic materials, which were then implemented in finite element analysis (FEA) solver. The authors were able to train the model in a low-data regime through the incorporation of material knowledge from continuum mechanics into the training process. Recent studies employed an unsupervised model discovery framework called EUCLID for hyperelastic materials [86, 103, 119]. Here, physics-based constraints are implemented in the loss function as regularization penalty to train the model without access to stress labels. Weber et al. (2021) [120] demonstrated that introducing constraints based on energy conservation, normalization and material symmetries for hyperelastic materials leads to improved learning behaviour, particularly when dealing with noisy data or smaller datasets. Kalina et al. (2022) [121] also introduced an ANN-based approach for the automated modelling of hyperelastic materials. The authors trained the ANN using plane stress synthetic data and applied a thermodynamically consistent correction to the model weights to obtain highly accurate results for the simulation of three-dimensional samples. Similarly, As'ad et al. (2022) [122] proposed a methodo-

logy to train mechanics-informed ANNs by adding physical constraints like consistency, objectivity and stability conditions to the loss function. According to the authors, the additions enhanced the model robustness outside the training domain and reduced the sensitivity to noise. Tac et al. (2022a) [123] replaced explicit hyperelastic models with ANNs to predict the strain energy and its derivatives with respect to strain invariants. The authors also designed a loss function to enforce polyconvexity of the strain energy as a constraint to ensure material stability in FEA simulations. Additional studies in the same field also include those of Liu et al., (2020) [67]; Klein et al. (2022) [124] and Tac et al. (2022b) [125]. This slew of works shows the popularity of hyperelastic materials for ANN-based constitutive modelling. The related papers are also heavily focused on model constraints. Hyperelastic families of models are particularly suitable for ANN modelling due to their energy-based formulations. This allows for the effective application of physics-based constraints and for the straightforward calculation of stress via automatic differentiation. In contrast, path-dependent elastoplastic material formulations involve yield criteria, plastic flow rules and hardening laws, which are more complex to encode into an ANN framework. To address these challenges, this paper aims to identify various physics-based relationships that can potentially be used as constraints when training an ANN-based elastoplastic constitutive model.

Model validation is a crucial step in the data-driven modelling workflow. Besides providing an unbiased evaluation of the model's performance, ensuring it can handle new inputs effectively, it also serves as a benchmark to compare different modelling approaches. In the context of data-driven constitutive modelling, where it is imperative to guarantee physically consistent solutions, the importance validation step is even more relevant. Here, the standard error metrics alone are insufficient to discern between models and may hide certain effects. According to Fuhg et al. (2024) [126], it is crucial to adopt validation tests using different experiments that encompass loading paths that were not included in the original dataset. It is also important to adopt additional metrics, as a complement to the standard error statistics, that provide a more in-depth assessment of the model's performance. As such, this paper also explores four different validation approaches to evaluate developed data-driven constitutive models. First, model performance is evaluated based on the usual statistical metrics using the validation dataset, under different loading conditions. Second, the predictive accuracy is evaluated on additional heterogeneous mechanical specimens, different from those used for training. Additionally, external key performance indicators (KPI) are used to further assess the accuracy of the data-driven constitutive models. Finally, various single-element tests are conducted to evaluate the integration of the developed models into a FEA solver.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 4.1.2, introduces the theoretical background related to general elastoplastic behaviour and provides an overview of the requirements for constitutive equations that can potentially be used as constraints for model training. In Section 4.1.3, RNNs with gated recurrent units (GRUs) are introduced along with the corresponding mathematical background. The chosen RNN architectures, as well as the data generation and training procedures, are detailed in Section 4.1.4. In Section 4.1.5, the importance of validation within the general data-driven modelling workflow is highlighted and new validation checks aimed at data-driven constitutive modelling, in particular, are also proposed and described in detail. Finally, in Section 4.1.6, results showing the effects of the addition of physics-based constraint

for model training are presented. The trained RNN-based models' performance is evaluated based on the previously proposed validation methodology.

4.1.2 Material modelling

Elastoplasticity

A material under load undergoes plastic deformation starting at the uniaxial yield stress σ_0 , beyond which hardening phenomena take place. Reversing the load at a given strain ε , plastic deformation ceases to increase and stress starts to linearly decrease with strain, with a gradient equal to the Young's modulus, E [33]. Once the stress reaches zero, the strain remaining in the material is the plastic strain ε^P , whereas the recovered strain ε^e is the elastic strain, such that [33]:

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon^e + \varepsilon^P. \quad (4.1)$$

The constitutive relation maps the elastic strain to the stress through the tangent stiffness tensor \mathbf{C} as [108]:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}\varepsilon^e. \quad (4.2)$$

There are plenty of developed yield criteria, with the most commonly used in engineering practice being that of von Mises. The criterion relies on the knowledge of an equivalent stress σ_{vM} , the von Mises stress, defined in tensor notation as [33]:

$$\sigma_{vM} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}' : \boldsymbol{\sigma}')}, \quad (4.3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$ is the deviatoric stress tensor. Similarly, an effective plastic strain rate \dot{p} can be established, such that:

$$\dot{p} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}(\dot{\varepsilon}^P : \dot{\varepsilon}^P)}. \quad (4.4)$$

The yield function, thus, assumes the following representation [33]:

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, p) = \sigma_{vM}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}) - \sigma_Y(p), \quad (4.5)$$

which is written as a function of the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and accumulated plastic strain p , such that:

$$p = \int \dot{p} dt. \quad (4.6)$$

The performance of the material thus depends on the previous states of stress and strain, that is, plasticity is path-dependent [25]. In this case, the plastic range can be characterized by two internal variables: the back stress tensor \mathbf{X} , representing kinematic hardening, and/or the drag stress R , representing isotropic hardening. The yield function is, therefore, modified as [33]:

$$f = J(\boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbf{X}) - R - k \leq 0, \quad (4.7)$$

where k is a material constant and J is a distance in the stress space. The plastic flow follows the normality condition [28,32]:

$$d\varepsilon^P = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \quad (4.8)$$

which states that the increment in the plastic strain tensor occurs in the direction normal to the tangent to the yield surface at the load point [31]. The plastic multiplier $d\lambda$ is derived from the hardening rule after employing the consistency condition [32] $f = df = 0$. The constitutive relation from Eq. 5.3 can then be rewritten in the general form [60]:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}} = \mathbf{H}\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{C}\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} & \text{if } f < 0 \\ \left[\mathbf{C} - \frac{\left(\mathbf{C}\frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}\right)\left(\mathbf{C}\frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}\right)^T}{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}\right)^T\left(\mathbf{C}\frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}\right)} \right] \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} & \text{if } f = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (4.9)$$

where \mathbf{H} is a general tangent stiffness tensor that degenerates into the elastic tangent stiffness \mathbf{C} under elasticity. In FEA, the constitutive model is responsible for updating not only the stress according to the current stress-strain state and strain increment, but also the material stiffness, which is obtained iteratively by means of the Newton-Raphson method. This phenomenological approach has been successfully used in FEA software for decades, however, model calibration still poses as an open problem and shows limitations when applied to complex material behaviours, due to its predefined mathematical formulation and lack of flexibility.

Requirements for constitutive equations

Laws of thermodynamics

The laws of thermodynamics impose two restrictions on stress-strain relationships. The first law requires that the work done by stress must either be stored as recoverable internal energy in the solid or dissipated as heat [108]. As such, a local entropy generation, or intrinsic dissipation in the material is defined, such that:

$$\gamma_{\text{loc}} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \theta \dot{\eta} + \dot{E}, \quad (4.10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ the strain rate tensor, θ the absolute temperature, η the entropy per unit volume and E the internal energy per unit volume. The second law of thermodynamics requires that, if a sample of material is subjected to a cycle of deformation, starting and ending with identical strain and internal energy, the total work must be positive or zero, such that [2, 108, 127]:

$$\gamma_{\text{loc}} \geq 0. \quad (4.11)$$

The thermodynamic consistency for a constitutive model is ensured through the Clausius-Duhem inequality, which may be weakly defined as [127, 128]:

$$D^o = \oint \boldsymbol{\sigma} : d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \geq 0. \quad (4.12)$$

Considering that the stress update is based on the increment of total strain from $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^n$ to $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{n+1}$, a closed path could be constructed such that a second step is performed back to $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^n$ (see Fig. 4.1), that is:

$$D^o = \frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^n + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{n+1}) \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 + \frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{n+1} + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^*) \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 \geq 0. \quad (4.13)$$

Given that $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1 = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{n+1} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^n$ and $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_2 = -\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_1$, the above relationship can be simplified to:

$$D^o = \frac{1}{2}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}^n - \boldsymbol{\sigma}^*) : \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \geq 0, \quad (4.14)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^*$ is the stress response after returning to the origin of the path at $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^n$. Although this inequality is weaker than the one defined in Eq. 5.7, it can be easily implemented in the context of ANN-based constitutive modelling. Nonetheless, it requires evaluating the model response at an additional fictitious step in the strain space [2, 127].

Figure 4.1: Dissipated energy D^o , after two consecutive steps $\Delta\varepsilon$ and $-\Delta\varepsilon$ in the strain space.

Another requirement that stems from the second law of thermodynamics is that the plastic power must be non-negative, i.e. [115]:

$$\dot{w}^P = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^P \geq 0. \quad (4.15)$$

A negative plastic dissipation would imply a decrease in temperature as a result of inelastic deformation, which would be non-physical. From here, it naturally follows that the accumulated plastic work

$$w^P = \int_0^t \dot{w}^P dt, \quad (4.16)$$

should be non-decreasing [115].

Drucker's postulate

The Drucker's postulate states that the work done by the tractions through the displacements is positive or zero [2, 108], such that:

$$\Delta\boldsymbol{\sigma} : \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \geq 0. \quad (4.17)$$

The condition is not a thermodynamic law and it does not have a physical meaning. Nonetheless, it is required to be fulfilled to ensure the uniqueness of the boundary value problem.

Tangent stiffness symmetry

For a general material in a three-dimensional stress state, the tangent stiffness \mathbf{C} is a symmetric fourth order tensor with 21 independent components. If the material is orthotropic, it gets reduced to nine independent components and the general mapping between the elastic strain and stress may be expressed in matrix form as [33]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & & & \\ & C_{22} & C_{23} & & & \\ & & C_{33} & & & \\ & & & C_{44} & & \\ & & & \text{symm} & C_{55} & \\ & & & & & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{zz} \\ 2\varepsilon_{yz} \\ 2\varepsilon_{xz} \\ 2\varepsilon_{xy} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4.18)$$

The major symmetries of \mathbf{C} mean that the physically correct state of stress is the one that maximizes the plastic dissipation for a given plastic strain rate [2]. When the material undergoes plastic deformation, a general tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} may be considered as in Eq. 5.5, which remains symmetric. Additionally, when strain hardening effects are present, \mathbf{H} is positive definite, to ensure that the strain energy is positive and weakly convex [60, 129]. The latter is also a sufficient condition for the uniqueness of the elastoplastic boundary value problem [60].

In the context of ANN training, the symmetry condition could be applied either as a loss penalty, forcing the equality between the matrix components, or as a hard constraint. For the latter, Jekel et al. [129] proposed a transformation layer, without learnable parameters, to map a vector input to a symmetric positive definite matrix. The transformation is based on the Cholesky factorization of a real symmetric matrix \mathbf{C} , expressed as:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}^T, \quad (4.19)$$

where \mathbf{L} is a real-valued lower triangular matrix, defined as:

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{11} & & & & & \\ L_{21} & L_{22} & & & & \\ L_{31} & L_{32} & L_{33} & & & \\ & & & L_{44} & & \\ & & & & L_{55} & \\ & & & & & L_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4.20)$$

with the diagonal elements kept positive, to force the output matrix to be symmetric positive definite. The positiveness of the diagonal elements is enforced with a suitable

activation function (e.g. ReLU). Xu et al. [60], on the other hand, propose obtaining \mathbf{L} directly through the ANN output.

Time-consistency

A consistent material law maps a state of zero strain onto a state of zero stress, such that [2, 60]:

$$\lim_{\Delta\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = 0. \quad (4.21)$$

Stress triaxiality and Lode angle parameter

The stress triaxiality and the Lode angle parameter are two dimensionless quantities that can characterize a mechanical state. The stress triaxiality represents the distribution of stress in the three orthotropic axes and is defined as:

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{\sigma_h}{\sigma_{vM}} \quad \text{with} \quad \sigma_h = \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}), \quad (4.22)$$

where σ_h the hydrostatic stress and σ_{vM} the von Mises equivalent stress. Triaxiality range is $-\infty \leq \mathcal{T} \leq +\infty$, however, for a two-dimensional plane stress state, the range reduces to $-2/3 \leq \mathcal{T} \leq 2/3$. A negative value of triaxiality, indicates a compressive stress state, while a positive value corresponds to a tensile state.

The Lode angle θ , or the Lode parameter L , relates the third invariant J_3 of the deviatoric stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$ with the von Mises equivalent stress σ_{vM} [130], such that:

$$L = -\cos(3\theta) = -\left(\frac{J_3}{\sigma_{vM}}\right)^3 \quad \text{with} \quad J_3 = \det(\boldsymbol{\sigma}'). \quad (4.23)$$

The Lode angle range is $0 \leq \theta \leq 1$ and the Lode parameter range is $-1 \leq L \leq 1$. The Lode angle θ can be normalized as follows:

$$\bar{\theta} = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \arccos\left(\frac{J_3}{\sigma_{vM}}\right). \quad (4.24)$$

For a plane stress state, the Lode angle θ and the stress triaxiality \mathcal{T} are related through the following:

$$\theta = \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}(1 - \bar{\theta})\right) = -\frac{27}{2}\mathcal{T}\left(\mathcal{T}^2 - \frac{1}{3}\right). \quad (4.25)$$

Requirements implemented as constraints

Table 4.1 lists all the previously described requirements and the corresponding formulation to encode them as constraints in the training stage of the data-driven material model. The simplest form of implementation is to add the constraints to the loss function as penalty terms, which are listed in the second column of Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Formulation of the loss penalty terms for different constitutive requirements.

Condition	Loss penalty
Clausius-Duhem	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CD}} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU} \left(-\frac{1}{2} (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(k)} - \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{(k)}^*) : \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(k)} \right)^2$
Plastic power	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Wp}} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU} \left(-\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(k)} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{(k)}^{\text{p}} \right)^2$
Drucker's postulate	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Drucker}} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU} \left(\Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(k)} : \Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{(k)} \right)^2$
Tangent symmetry	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{TS}} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 \left(C_{ij(k)} - C_{ji(k)} \right)^2$
Time-consistency	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Cons}} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \left(\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{0})_{i(k)} \right)^2$
Stress triaxiality	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Triax}} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU} \left(- \mathcal{T}_{(k)} + \frac{2}{3} \right)^2$
Lode angle	$\mathcal{L}_{\theta} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU} \left(- \theta_{(k)}^- + 1 \right)^2$

4.1.3 GRU-based RNNs

Introduction

The history-dependent behaviour in plasticity is challenging to model with ANNs [90]. Feedforward architectures are unable to capture the phenomena, as there is no mechanism to relate the inputs in the current time step with the outputs from previous time steps [56, 91]. This interdependency between past and present states makes material behaviour data time-dependent, effectively transforming the modelling task into a time-series problem. This scenario constitutes an ideal use-case for RNNs, which allow to maintain a memory of previous inputs using cyclic connections (see Figure 5.2b) [92]. Using strain sequences with a history of k length, up to the current time step t , a RNN can capture temporal dependencies, allowing it to predict the corresponding stress state accurately.

Mathematical formulation

In this paper a RNN architecture based on Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) is employed. GRUs are a streamlined version of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) units, designed to capture dependencies in sequential data efficiently, while mitigating some computational complexity [94]. As observed in Figure 5.2a, a basic GRU cell comprises the following key components [94, 95]:

1. **Update gate** (\mathbf{z}_t) - determines how much is retained from the previous hidden state and how much it should be updated with new information, defined as:

$$\mathbf{z}_t = \text{sig}(\mathbf{W}_{xz}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xz} + \mathbf{W}_{hz}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hz}); \quad (4.26)$$

2. **Reset gate** (\mathbf{r}_t) - specifies which information from the previous hidden state should be forgotten, i.e.:

$$\mathbf{r}_t = \text{sig}(\mathbf{W}_{xr}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xr} + \mathbf{W}_{hr}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hr}); \quad (4.27)$$

3. **New gate** (\mathbf{n}_t) - computes a new candidate hidden state based on the input and previous hidden state, written as:

$$\mathbf{n}_t = \tanh(\mathbf{W}_{xn}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xn} + \mathbf{r}_t \odot [\mathbf{W}_{hn}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hn}]); \quad (4.28)$$

4. **Final state** (\mathbf{h}_t) - combines the previous hidden state and the new memory content, controlled by the update gate, through the following relationship:

$$\mathbf{h}_t = (1 - \mathbf{z}_t) \odot \mathbf{n}_t + \mathbf{z}_t \odot \mathbf{h}_{t-1}. \quad (4.29)$$

The variables \mathbf{h}_t and \mathbf{x}_t are, respectively, the hidden state and the input at time t , while $\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}$ is the hidden state at time $t - 1$, or the initial hidden state at $t = 0$. The entities sig and tanh are, respectively, the sigmoid and the hyperbolic tangent activation functions and the operator \odot is the Hadamard product. The weight matrices \mathbf{W} and bias vectors \mathbf{b} are appended with double indices identifying the mapping between the different

components of the GRU cell. A deeper description of these mathematical entities and their corresponding dimensions, in the context of the present work, is provided in Table 5.1. The hidden state \mathbf{h} is the key element behind the flow of information relating previous time steps and future predictions. In a way analogous to the internal variables of classical constitutive laws, \mathbf{h} carries the information about the current plastic state of the material [93].

Figure 4.2: Schematic representation of (a) a standard GRU cell and (b) an unrolled recurrent neural network.

Table 4.2: Mathematical entities, and corresponding dimensions for a GRU-based RNN where n is the batch size, k the sequence length, n_{cells} the number of GRU cells, s_{in} the input size, s_{out} the output size and s_{hid} the hidden size.

Component	Entity	Dimensions	Description
Input	\mathbf{x}_t	$(n \times k \times s_{\text{in}})$	Strain sequences
Previous state	\mathbf{h}_{t-1}	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time $t - 1$
Final state	\mathbf{h}_t	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time t
Output	$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_t$	$(n \times s_{\text{out}})$	Stress tensor at time t
Update gate	$\mathbf{W}_{x(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{in}})$	Input to hidden weights of 1st GRU cell
Reset gate or		$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input to hidden weights of i -th GRU cell
New gate	$\mathbf{b}_{x(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input to hidden bias
$(\mathbf{z}_t \mathbf{r}_t \mathbf{n}_t)$	$\mathbf{W}_{h(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden to hidden weights
	$\mathbf{b}_{h(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden to hidden bias

4.1.4 Materials and methods

RNN architecture

Two RNN architectures were considered, with the following base components: two GRU cells followed by a fully-connected layer with 32 hidden units. One configuration predicts the stress tensor in vector form, while the other outputs the material tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} , given the addition of an SPD layer as proposed by Jekel et al. [129] (see Section 5.1.2), adapted here to the context of an isotropic material under plane stress. Both RNNs process strain sequences of length $k = 4$. A schematic representation of both architectures is depicted in Fig. 5.3.

Figure 4.3: GRU-based RNN architectures for material modelling. Sequences of length $k = 4$ of the scaled strain tensor $\varepsilon' = [\varepsilon'_{xx} \ \varepsilon'_{yy} \ \varepsilon'_{xy}]$ are taken as input and (a) mapped to the stress tensor $\sigma = [\sigma_{xx} \ \sigma_{yy} \ \tau_{xy}]$ or (b) to the material tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} through the inclusion of an SPD layer. The green block represents a linear fully-connected (FC) layer.

Training database

Synthetic data to train the RNN models was gathered from a set of FEA simulations of a heterogeneous biaxial test based on a cruciform specimen with a thickness $h = 1$ mm and dimensions specified in Figure 5.4b [9]. Symmetry boundary conditions were defined at the edges $y = 0$ and $x = 0$, with displacements being prescribed at each arm of the specimen, as depicted in Figure 5.4c. Several virtual experiments were generated with displacements of different magnitudes (in mm), being prescribed in pairs (u_x, u_y) as detailed in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Paired combinations of displacements (u_x, u_y) prescribed to the arms of the cruciform specimen.

		u_y					
		0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
u_x	0.5	(0.5,0.5)	(0.5,1.0)	(0.5,1.5)	(0.5,2.0)	(0.5,2.5)	(0.5,3.0)
	1.0	(1.0,0.5)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.5)	(1.0,2.0)	(1.0,2.5)	(1.0,3.0)
	1.5	(1.5,0.5)	(1.5,1.0)	(1.5,1.5)	(1.5,2.0)	(1.5,2.5)	(1.5,3.0)
	2.0	(2.0,0.5)	(2.0,1.0)	(2.0,1.5)	(2.0,2.0)	(2.0,2.5)	(2.0,3.0)
	2.5	(2.5,0.5)	(2.5,1.0)	(2.5,1.5)	(2.5,2.0)	(2.5,2.5)	(2.5,3.0)
	3.0	(3.0,0.5)	(3.0,1.0)	(3.0,1.5)	(3.0,2.0)	(3.0,2.5)	(3.0,3.0)

The simulations were carried out with Abaqus Standard software, assuming plane stress conditions and a small strain formulation. The material behaviour was considered isotropic, with the flow stress evolving according to the Swift's law:

$$\sigma_y = K(\varepsilon_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}^P)^n \quad \text{with} \quad \varepsilon_0 = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{K}\right)^{1/n}, \quad (4.30)$$

where σ_y is the flow stress, $\bar{\varepsilon}^P$ the equivalent plastic strain, σ_0 the initial yield stress, K and n are material-specific hardening parameters. The complete set of constitutive parameters is listed in Table 5.3.

The geometry was discretized using CPS4R elements with an average size of 0.52 mm, resulting in a total of 2121 elements. Similar refinement levels are cited in the literature for this type of specimen ([9, 104], among others). Reduced integration elements were chosen in order to simulate DIC subsets from full-field measurements, thus, field output variables were extracted at the centroid of the element. For each time stage, the strain and stress tensors were extracted at all the measurement points and the resultant force applied at each of the specimen's arms was computed from the equilibrium of the internal forces, through the following:

$$Fl = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i A_i h, \quad (4.31)$$

where F is the global force, l the length of the specimen, n is the number of elements, A is the area of the element and h the thickness.

Table 4.4: Constitutive parameters for the soft steel material.

E [GPa]	ν	σ_0 [MPa]	K [MPa]	n
210	0.33	160	565	0.26

The generated dataset consisted of a total of 36 virtual experiments. These were posteriorly shuffled and split in half, such that one part was used for training and the remaining part for validation. The training set was then split such that 80% of the included virtual experiments were used for training and the remaining 20% for testing. The full training domain is shown on the scatter plot from Figure 5.5. In terms of major and minor strains, most of the points are under uniaxial tension with a small portion experiencing a slight shear, induced by the prescribed displacements of different magnitudes, resulting in a maximum equivalent plastic strain of 0.329. Concerning the yield locus, most of the stress points evolve towards the first quadrant.

The input data was scaled to have zero mean and unit variance, as follows:

$$\varepsilon' = \frac{\varepsilon - \boldsymbol{\mu}}{\mathbf{s}}, \quad (4.32)$$

where ε' is the scaled strain tensor, $\boldsymbol{\mu} = [\mu_{\varepsilon_{xx}} \ \mu_{\varepsilon_{yy}} \ \mu_{\varepsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of mean values and $\mathbf{s} = [s_{\varepsilon_{xx}} \ s_{\varepsilon_{yy}} \ s_{\varepsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of variances of the strain tensor components, respectively. The statistical variables $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and \mathbf{s} were saved for later usage. For each virtual experiment, the inputs have dimensions $[n_{\text{pts}} \times n_t \times k \times 3]$, where n_{pts} is the number of measurement points, i.e. the number of elements, n_t is the number of time stages, k the RNN sequence length and the last dimension is the number of strain components.

Figure 4.4: Biaxial test virtual experiment setup: (a) general dimensions of the cruciform specimen and (b) set of applied boundary conditions.

Training procedure

For the purpose of this work, four GRU-based RNN models were trained and given the nomenclature specified in Table 4.5, based on the applied constraints. The models

Figure 4.5: Principal strain and yield locus diagrams for the complete set of virtual experiments used for training, taken from the material points at all the time stages. The yield locus is normalized by the yield stress σ_Y .

were trained using PyTorch library, following a standard supervised learning approach with labelled data. Training was carried out using the Adam optimizer with a weight decay factor of 10^{-3} . A linear warmup scheduler was employed in order to increase the learning rate from an initial value of 10^{-3} up to 5×10^{-3} within the first five epochs. From that point onward, a gradual decay was applied according to a cosine annealing scheduler defined as [106, 107]:

$$\eta_t = \eta_{\min} + \frac{1}{2}(\eta_{\max} - \eta_{\min}) \left(1 + \cos \left(\frac{T_{\text{cur}}}{T_{\text{max}}} \pi \right) \right), \quad (4.33)$$

where η_t is the current learning rate, η_{\min} and η_{\max} are the minimum and maximum learning rates, T_{cur} and T_{max} are the current iteration and the maximum number of iterations, respectively. The maximum learning rate η_{\max} was set to 5×10^{-3} and the minimum learning rate η_{\min} to 10^{-3} . At the start of each epoch the feeding order of the virtual experiments was shuffled. The corresponding input data was also shuffled along the first dimension and fed to the network as mini-batches due to GPU memory limitations. An early-stopping criterion was defined in order to prevent overfitting, such that training would be interrupted if no further improvement was registered in the test loss after 300 epochs. The data loss was based on the mean squared error between the RNN predicted stress, $\hat{\sigma} = \mathcal{M}(\theta, \varepsilon)$ and the target stress σ , defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}(\theta, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{\sigma}(\theta, \varepsilon) - \sigma)^2, \quad (4.34)$$

where n is the number of training samples. The physics-based constraints were enforced by adding penalty terms to the data loss, resulting a total loss equivalent to a multi-objective loss with the general form:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \varepsilon) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i \mathcal{L}_i, \quad (4.35)$$

where the constants λ_i are the pre-factors used to balanced the different terms in the loss function, \mathcal{L}_i is the i -th objective loss to minimize and k is the total number of conflicting objectives. The pre-factors λ_i can be found through trial and error or through laborious grid-search methods, which may become intractable depending on problem's dimension. As such, an automated scheme to dynamically choose the pre-factors λ_i is preferable. For the purpose, the Relative Loss Balancing with Random Lookback algorithm, introduced by Bischof and Kraus (2021) [131], is employed in the present work. The algorithm dynamically adapts the pre-factors λ_i based on a moving average and a random lookback mechanism. At each iteration the pre-factors are computed as follows:

$$\lambda_i^j = \alpha \left(\beta \lambda_i^{j-1} + (1 - \beta) \hat{\lambda}_i^{j;0} \right) + (1 - \alpha) \hat{\lambda}_i^{j;j-1}, \quad (4.36)$$

where λ_i^j is the prefactor for the i -th loss term at iteration j , α is the moving average parameter and β a Bernoulli random variable with a value close to 1. A term $\hat{\lambda}_i^{j;j'}$ is responsible for computing the scalings based on the relative improvements of each loss between iterations j and j' , such that:

$$\hat{\lambda}_i^{j;j'} = k \cdot \frac{\exp \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i^j}{\tau \mathcal{L}_i^{j'} + \epsilon} - \max \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i^j}{\mathcal{L}_i^{j'}} \right) \right)}{\sum_{m=1}^k \exp \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_m^j}{\tau \mathcal{L}_m^{j'} + \epsilon} - \max \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_m^j}{\mathcal{L}_m^{j'}} \right) \right)}, \quad (4.37)$$

with k being the total number of loss terms, \mathcal{L}_i^j and $\mathcal{L}_i^{j'}$ the values of the i -th loss term at iterations j and j' , respectively, τ is a hyperparameter that controls the amplitude of the scalings and ϵ a small number. The parameter α controls the weight given to past scalings in relation to the scalings from the current iteration, while β allows the model to occasionally look back until the start of training. For the present work, a simple grid search study confirmed the optimal values for these parameters were: $\alpha = 0.999$, $\beta = 1.0$ and $\tau = 0.001$.

Table 4.5: Constraints used for each of the RNN-based models and respective identifiers.

Model	Constraints
Baseline	None
SPD-RNN	SPD layer
Wp-RNN	Plastic power penalty
SPDw-RNN	SPD layer and plastic power penalty

4.1.5 The importance of validation

In data-driven constitutive modelling, there is no standardized validation procedure to evaluate the performance of the trained models. Conventionally, model validation in ML is ensured by partitioning the dataset into training and validation sets (unseen data). The predictive quality of the model is then evaluated based on the latter, according to different statistical metrics (e.g. mean squared error, root mean squared error, among others). Nonetheless, in addition to these metrics, objective indicators should be used to assess whether the resulting data-driven model is able to reproduce the behaviour of material under analysis and to what degree its results should be trusted. This may be achieved by conducting tests based on experiments that generate loading paths that were not included in the original dataset. Regarding the numerical behaviour and its robustness, it is essential to assess how the data-driven constitutive model integrates with a numerical solver. This includes evaluating the possibility of obtaining a consistent tangent matrix and the overall convergence and numerical stability of the model. To address these challenges, this paper explores four different validation approaches to evaluate the quality of the developed RNN-based constitutive models. First, the base performance is evaluated using statistical metrics to predict material responses on previously unseen datasets, under various loading conditions. Second, the model's robustness is assessed using tests based on heterogeneous mechanical specimens, different from the one used for training. Additionally, a set of potential key performance indicators (KPI) that can be used to further validate the performance of data-driven constitutive model are shown. Finally, various single-element tests are conducted and evaluated after integrating the developed model into a user material subroutine (UMAT) of the FEM numerical solver.

Validation database and procedure

From the data generation phase, 18 virtual experiments based on the cruciform specimen were kept separate for the validation set. This set of experiments had different prescribed displacements than the ones used for training. From the validation set, the virtual experiment with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm was chosen for further analysis. Three additional heterogeneous mechanical specimens, documented in the literature for constitutive model calibration, have also been considered for validation purposes, each of which exhibiting increasing levels of geometric complexity within the respective regions of interest (ROI): the S specimen [132], the Sigma specimen [133] and the D specimen [134]. For further details on each specimen's configuration, the reader is invited to refer to the corresponding original works. An uniaxial external load along the y -direction is normally applied to each specimen. The complex shapes induce multiaxial heterogeneous stress states, despite the loading being uniaxial. For the purpose of the present work, a displacement u_y is prescribed at the top-surface of each specimen with magnitude 2.0 mm for the D specimen and 1.5 mm for the S and Sigma specimens. The corresponding geometries, principal strain distributions, yield locus and equivalent plastic strain field are described in are detailed in Figures 5.6 and 5.7, respectively.

Figure 4.6: Geometric definition of the three heterogeneous mechanical specimens chosen for model validation: (a) S specimen, (b) Sigma specimen and (c) D specimen.

Error statistics

For the validation dataset, based on the cruciform specimen, model performance was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE), a standard benchmark metric in ML to assess the accuracy of predictive models. A lower RMSE indicates higher accuracy. RMSE quantifies the average magnitude of errors between the predicted and observed values as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{\sigma} - \sigma)^2}, \quad (4.38)$$

where, $\hat{\sigma}$ is the predicted stress, σ the actual stress and N the number of observations. Additionally, the absolute error, i.e.:

$$\delta = |\hat{\sigma} - \sigma| \quad (4.39)$$

was used to compare the predicted stress fields and stress-strain curves with the reference FEA solution.

Validation KPI: reconstructed axial force ratio

The reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR), introduced by Peshave et al. [135] was also employed to evaluate the performance of the RNN-based constitutive models. The RAFR exploits the fact that in uniaxial tensile tests, the load applied by the testing machine F_a is known. Moreover, the horizontal average of the stress multiplied by the cross-sectional area F_c^i should be equal to the applied load at any cross-section (see Fig. 5.8). For a given cross-section i , the reconstructed force F_c^i is computed by integrating the axial stress σ_{yy} , as follows:

$$F_c^i = \int_{S_c} \sigma_{yy} dS_c, \quad (4.40)$$

Figure 4.7: Major and minor strain distributions, normalized yield locus and equivalent plastic strain at the last time stage for (a) the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, (b) the S specimen (c) the Sigma specimen and (d) the D specimen. The grey colour highlights material points in the elastic regime.

where S_c is the surface of that particular cross-section of the mechanical specimen. Assuming constant stress through the thickness, the surface integral reduces to:

$$F_c^i = h \int_{l_c} \sigma_{yy} dl_c, \quad (4.41)$$

where h is the specimen's thickness. Considering a regular grid of measurement points with sufficiently high spatial density, the line integral can be approximated as:

$$F_c^i = h S_t \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \sigma_{yy}^j, \quad (4.42)$$

where N_i is the number of evaluation points at the cross-section i and S_t is the step size. The RAFR is then computed as:

$$\text{RAFR} = \frac{F_c^i}{F_a}. \quad (4.43)$$

The metric is used to evaluate how well the section-averaged stress field matches the applied force at each cross-section. Any deviation from the ideal value of 1 indicates problems with the approximation of the stress field.

Figure 4.8: Schematic of RAFR calculation. The force acting at the i -th cross-section is reconstructed by integrating the corresponding axial stress σ_{yy}^i along the cross-section length l_i and multiplying it by the thickness h .

UMAT implementation

Another step taken to validate the trained RNN models, involved incorporating them as material constitutive models in a FEA solver (here, Abaqus Standard), through a custom user material subroutine (UMAT). The code was developed in C++ and made use of the official C++ implementation of PyTorch (LibTorch). The architecture and data flow for the UMAT implementation are described in the flowchart of Figure 5.9.

The Python-based RNN models were converted to an appropriate format in order to work in the Python-independent environment. All the RNN operations were implemented as a function in a dynamic-link library (DLL) (annlib.dll). The UMAT is the interface between Abaqus Standard and the DLL, dealing with the inputs/outputs and updating the strain history. The DLL function is invoked in the UMAT code and receives the strain history, the mean and the variance of the training data as input arguments. Within the DLL function, the strain history is scaled to have zero mean and unit variance. The RNN model is loaded persistently into memory in the code's first execution. The scaled strain history is fed as input to the RNN in order to predict the stress tensor, which is returned as an output back to the UMAT, along with the stiffness matrix. The UMAT implementation was used to validate the RNN-based material models performance on one-element tests, specifically uniaxial traction along x - and y -directions and a shear test. Within this validation step, numerical issues, such as stability, convergence and efficiency can also be evaluated.

Figure 4.9: Flowchart of the UMAT-RNN implementation.

4.1.6 Results

Learning curves and the effect of constraints

Regarding the baseline model (Fig. 4.10a), both train and test losses sharply decrease during the initial 50 to 100 epochs, followed by a gradual evolution for the remaining epochs of training. The oscillations exhibited by the loss curves reveal a certain difficulty in achieving convergence. Nonetheless, the early-stopping triggered at epoch 1383, saving the model state at this point with a train and test loss of 1.3182 MPa² and 2.2190 MPa², respectively. The learning curves for the SPD-RNN model (Fig. 4.10b) exhibit a similar learning pattern, however with notably fewer oscillations, suggesting improved stability and training convergence. The early-stopping was triggered at epoch 848, corresponding to a train loss of 0.951 MPa² and a test loss of 1.723 MPa². The Wp-RNN model also exhibits similar behaviour (Fig. 4.10c) with the loss curves showing slightly less noise when compared to the baseline model. The early-stopping was triggered after 901 epochs, corresponding to a train and test loss of 1.588 MPa² and 2.249 MPa², respectively. The SPDw-RNN learning curves (Fig. 4.10d) follow the general learning pattern, albeit with considerably less noise. Additionally, the model was faster to train, with the early-stopping being triggered after 444 epochs, corresponding to a train and test loss of 1.015 MPa² and 1.777 MPa², respectively. For all the models, the gap between the train and test losses is not significant, indicating the RNNs did not overfit.

For the Wp-RNN model, the plastic power penalty term (Fig. 4.11a) sharply increases at the beginning of training, from 10^{-4} J.s⁻¹ to 10^{-2} J.s⁻¹, approximately, followed by a rapid decrease which is tied to the overall learning pattern of the Wp-RNN model. At the early-stopping point, a lower value of 2.85×10^{-5} J.s⁻¹ was registered. The sharp increase at the beginning of training is due to the fact that the stresses predicted by the RNN are initially small in magnitude, resulting in a low value of plastic power. As the training evolves, the predicted stresses get progressively higher in magnitude, causing the plastic power to increase up to a certain point, from which it starts to decrease due to further improvements in the prediction quality. The loss pre-factors were continuously adjusted during training in order to balance both terms of the loss function, oscillating within a narrow range from 0.96 to 1.06. In contrast, for the SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 4.11b) the plastic power penalty appears smooth and sharply increases from a residual value of approximately 10^{-13} J.s⁻¹ at the beginning of training to quickly saturate at around the final value of 1.79×10^{-5} J.s⁻¹ at the early-stopping point. The loss balancing terms follow a similar pattern to the Wp-RNN model, oscillating within the same range.

Figure 4.10: Learning curves for the trained RNN-based material models. Effect of the physics-based constraints on the training and test losses.

(a) Wp-RNN

(b) SPDw-RNN

Figure 4.11: Plastic power penalty loss \mathcal{L}_{W_p} and loss balancing pre-factors for (a) the Wp-RNN and (b) the SPDw-RNN models during training.

Model validation with different mechanical specimens

Mechanical test with cruciform specimen

The von Mises stress contours for the cruciform specimen corresponding to the four RNN models under analysis are shown in Fig. 4.12. The stress distribution for this particular specimen ranges from 71.483 to 357.858 MPa, with high stress concentrations located at the inner regions of the central hole. Results show the stress field predicted by the baseline RNN model (Fig. 4.12a) closely follows the reference, albeit small discrepancies are visible near the smaller radii. The absolute error ranges from 0.002 to 5.817 MPa, with a mean error of 0.433 MPa. The SPD-RNN model (Fig. 4.12b) demonstrates higher predictive accuracy compared to the baseline model, as it closely matches the reference results. The overall error for this model ranges from 0.006 to 2.131 MPa, with a mean error of 0.289 MPa. There is a significant reduction in the maximum error compared to the baseline model, the lower mean error further highlights its superior predictive capability and generalization. Concerning the Wp-RNN model (Fig. 4.12c), predictions have only slightly improved upon the baseline. The absolute error for the Wp-RNN ranges from 0.011 to 3.587 MPa, with a mean error of 0.415 MPa. The SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 4.12d) results are on par with the SPD-RNN, albeit with slightly worse mean and median errors. The absolute error ranges from 0.016 to 2.437 MPa.

Table 4.6: RMSE statistics for the validation set based on the cruciform specimen.

Model	RMSE validation set			
	Min.	Mean	Median	Max.
Baseline	0.7228	1.4464	1.2441	2.8477
SPD-RNN	0.6593	1.2801	1.0834	2.6489
Wp-RNN	0.6923	1.4341	1.2285	2.8264
SPDw-RNN	0.6903	1.3080	1.0959	2.6522

Mechanical test with S specimen and RAFR KPI

The von Mises stress contours for the S specimen corresponding to the four RNN models under analysis are shown in Figure 4.13. The stress distribution ranges from 8.233 to 336.823 MPa, with the higher stress concentrations occurring at the narrower areas near the notches' roots. The Baseline model results (Fig. 4.13a) show the predicted stress field closely matches the reference results, although some discrepancies are registered mainly along the linear areas of the notches. The absolute error varies between 0.017 and 77.833 MPa, with a mean error of 1.885 MPa. Concerning the SPD-RNN model (Fig. 4.13b), results have improved compared to the baseline model, with mean absolute error being reduced to 1.642 MPa and the overall error ranging between 0.003 and 88.672 MPa. The Wp-RNN model (Fig. 4.13c) also shows an improvement in prediction accuracy compared to the baseline. The maximum absolute error decreases to 50.579 MPa and the minimum absolute error slightly increased to 0.027 MPa, while the mean error is the lowest among the four models, at 1.541 MPa. The error statistics show the Wp-RNN model is particularly effective at minimizing discrepancies, however

Figure 4.12: Cruciform specimen: contour maps of von Mises equivalent stress at time stage $n_t = 124$ for (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models. Comparison with the FEA solution and corresponding absolute difference.

with the SPD-RNN those are much more localized. The SDPw-RNN model (Fig. 4.13d) results are similar to that of the SPD-RNN, however with higher median and maximum absolute errors. The error ranges from 0.003 to 116.799 MPa.

Fig. 4.14 shows the RAFR metric calculated for the four RNN-based models. Large discrepancies are observed at lower loads for both the baseline and Wp-RNN models, except for the SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN which achieved a relatively flat curve, suggesting that those models are able to output time-consistent solutions. For larger loads, all the models produce similar results, the curves are smoother near the edges of the specimen with a slight scatter visible at the regions between the notches, where the stress state is more complex. The three models behave well within the $\pm 10\%$ grey area, nonetheless the Wp-RNN model seems to be prone to higher deviations.

Mechanical test with Sigma specimen and RAFR KPI

The von Mises stress contours for the Sigma specimen corresponding to the four RNN models under analysis are shown in Fig. 4.15. The stress distribution ranges from 0.537 to 238.012 MPa, with higher stress concentrations around the curved features of the specimen, located at the centre and near the top and bottom regions. The baseline RNN model (Fig. 4.15a) approximates the reference results relatively well, however with notable discrepancies over the top half of the specimen. The minimum and maximum absolute error are 0.022 MPa and 101.132 MPa respectively, with a mean absolute error of 3.995 MPa. Regarding the SPD-RNN (Fig. 4.15b), the full-field plots show a significant degradation of the results, with the white blobs showing that the model tends to underestimate the stress on those regions. The statistics show higher maximum and the mean absolute errors, calculated at 452.666 and 5.88 MPa respectively. Nonetheless, the error regions are narrower and the significantly lower median error suggests an overall improvement in prediction accuracy. The Wp-RNN model's (Fig. 4.15c) predictions are slightly better than the baseline and SPD-RNN model. The absolute error ranges from 0.012 to 77.286 MPa, with a mean absolute error of 3.827 MPa. The SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 4.15d) approximates the reference results quite well with no visible degradation, in contrast with the SPD-RNN. Compared to the latter, although the discrepancies are less localized, the overall results have improved achieving significantly lower mean and maximum errors. The absolute error ranges from 0.001 to 175.072 MPa.

Fig. 4.16 shows the RAFR metric calculated for the four RNN-based models. Similarly to the S specimen, large discrepancies are still present at lower loads for both the baseline and Wp-RNN models. An exception is made for the SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN models, which achieved a relatively flat curve, once again suggesting that the SPD hard constraint allows the models to achieve time-consistent solutions. For larger loads, the RAFR metric improves for all the models, with the baseline and the Wp-RNN originating similar curves. Significant scatter is evident for these models towards the last time stages, slightly exceeding the $\pm 10\%$ error. Worthy of note is the robustness of the SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN models, originating relatively flat curves with only a slight scatter near the radial features of the specimen. Nonetheless, punctual but significant deviations going beyond the error zone are registered for the SPD-RNN on the last time stage. For the SPDw-RNN the deviations are always kept inside the $\pm 10\%$ error zone. For all the models, these discrepancies appear to happen at the coordinates of the regions consistent with the error maps from Fig. 4.15.

Figure 4.13: S specimen: contour maps of von Mises equivalent stress at time stage $n_t = 120$ for (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models. Comparison with the FEA solution and corresponding absolute difference.

Figure 4.14: Use of a validation KPI to assess the material model. Reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR) for the coordinates along the length (in mm) of the S specimen, for the trained RNN-based models. The ideal value $RAFR = 1$ is denoted by the dashed horizontal line. The vertical dashed lines indicate the location of each notch root. The greyed-out area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$.

Figure 4.15: Sigma specimen: contour maps of von Mises equivalent stress at time stage $n_t = 120$ for (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models. Comparison with the FEA solution and corresponding absolute difference.

Figure 4.16: Use of a validation KPI to assess the material model. Reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR) for the coordinates along the length (in mm) of the Sigma specimen, for the trained RNN-based models. The ideal value $RAFR = 1$ is denoted by the dashed horizontal line. The greyed-out area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$.

Mechanical test with D specimen and RAFR KPI

The von Mises stress contours for the D specimen corresponding to the four RNN models under analysis are shown in Fig. 4.17. The stress distribution ranges from 0.145 to 326.129 MPa, with stress concentrations located around the inner and corner curved regions as well as on the vertical member of the specimen. The baseline RNN model (Fig. 4.17a) manages to approximate the reference results, however some discrepancies are evident. The minimum and maximum absolute error are 0.00 and 113.485 MPa respectively, with a mean absolute error of 3.1 MPa. Regarding the SPD-RNN (Fig. 4.17b), there is an evident degradation of the results in the top and bottom corners of the inner cutout, with the white blobs showing a slight tendency for the model to underestimate the stress on those areas. The maximum and the mean absolute errors are also higher than the baseline model, calculated at 1528.155 and 4.54 MPa, respectively. However, the median error is of similar magnitude, indicating that there is not a significant degradation on the overall prediction accuracy and the highest errors are present only on those very narrow regions. Regarding the Wp-RNN model (Fig. 4.17c) error statistics seem to indicate that the prediction accuracy has improved upon the baseline and SPD-RNN models. The absolute error ranges from 0.004 to 94.075 MPa, with a mean absolute error of 2.8 MPa. Nonetheless, for the Wp-RNN model the error is spread over a wider region. For the SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 4.17d), degradation was reduced compared to the SPD-RNN, albeit it is still present at the top and bottom corners of the inner cutout. The maximum absolute error has improved, nonetheless the median has slightly increased. The absolute error ranges from 0.0 to 719.054 MPa.

Fig. 4.18 shows the RAFR metric calculated for the four RNN-based models. Large discrepancies are still present at lower loads for both the baseline and Wp-RNN models, albeit with lower magnitude. The SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN models show a mostly flat curve. For larger loads, the metric improves for all the models with the baseline and Wp-RNN models showing a similar behaviour. A significant deviation is evident for these models at the lower-half of the specimen towards the last time stages, nonetheless still within the $\pm 10\%$ error area. Once again, the SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN models show robustness, originating mostly flat curves with only a slight discrepancy at the lower-half of the specimen, which is consistent with the errors shown in Fig. 4.17.

One-element tests

The uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves obtained for the one-element tests performed with the UMAT implementations of the four RNN models under analysis and the corresponding absolute error along the time stages are shown in Figs. 5.22 and 4.20, respectively. The curves are compared with the FEA solution and with the RNNs' inference predictions.

The results show that, in general, all the models were capable of predicting the uniaxial behaviour very well at both rolling (RD) and transverse (TD) directions with overall low absolute errors. All the models show similar error profiles along the time stages for the x -direction (RD) and the y -direction (TD). However, for the SPD-RNN, the Wp-RNN and the SPDw-RNN models, the error profile shows a small spike reaching a maximum of approximately 6.5 MPa at time stage 24 which onset of yielding. Numerical instabilities were detected with the baseline model for the test along the x -direction (RD),

Figure 4.17: D specimen: contour maps of von Mises equivalent stress at time stage $n_t = 142$ for (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models. Comparison with the FEA solution and corresponding absolute difference.

Figure 4.18: Use of a validation KPI to assess the material model. Reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR) for the coordinates along the length (in mm) of the D specimen, for the trained RNN-based models. The ideal value $RAFR = 1$ is denoted by the dashed horizontal line. The greyed-out area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$.

Table 4.7: Overview of the error statistics for the stress fields predicted by each model for each of the heterogeneous mechanical specimens.

	Specimens	Model absolute error [MPa]			
		Baseline	SPD-RNN	Wp-RNN	SPDw-RNN
Min.	Cruciform	0.002	0.006	0.011	0.016
	S	0.017	0.003	0.027	0.003
	Sigma	0.022	0.0	0.012	0.001
	D	0.0	0.0	0.004	0.0
Mean	Cruciform	0.433	0.289	0.415	0.383
	S	1.885	1.602	1.541	1.711
	Sigma	3.995	5.88	3.827	3.59
	D	3.1	4.54	2.8	4.469
Median	Cruciform	0.311	0.204	0.338	0.296
	S	0.882	0.732	0.688	1.015
	Sigma	1.018	0.48	1.148	0.469
	D	0.505	0.543	0.582	0.758
Max.	Cruciform	5.817	2.131	3.587	2.437
	S	77.833	88.672	50.579	116.799
	Sigma	101.132	452.666	77.286	175.072
	D	113.485	1528.155	94.075	719.054
Std. deviation	Cruciform	0.463	0.335	0.381	0.370
	S	5.026	4.227	3.241	5.621
	Sigma	11.169	31.043	9.497	15.181
	D	8.119	41.965	7.126	29.580

resulting in oscillations towards the final segment of the stress curve.

Regarding the shear response, all the models struggle to approximate the reference curve to some degree, with SPD-RNN and the SPDw-RNN models showing higher levels of degradation, while the baseline and the Wp-RNN models were capable of more stable responses. It is interesting to see that the RNNs were able to capture the material behaviour from the biaxial experiments in such a way that they are still capable of performing relatively well in a completely different setting. The source of the instabilities for the baseline mode is essentially of numerical nature induced by spurious predictions interfering with the equilibrium iterations. As evidenced by the results of the SPD-RNN, Wp-RNN and SPDw-RNN models, the introduction of constraints mitigated those issues. The degradation seen on the shear response curves suggests the training data based on the cruciform specimen is not rich enough in shear states, and it would benefit from the addition of information from that regions of the strain space.

Figure 4.19: Uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves. Comparison between the FEA solution based on the Swift's law (Eq. 5.26) and the UMAT implementations of (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models.

Figure 4.20: Absolute error along the time stages corresponding to the uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves, for the UMAT implementations of (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models.

4.1.7 Final remarks

The importance of validation KPI and physics-based constraints for data-driven constitutive modelling was acknowledged. Within the framework of elastoplasticity, a variety of constitutive requirements were identified, as well as the corresponding theoretical development and possible implementation formulas for use as loss penalty terms in the training process. The importance of the validation stage within the data-driven constitutive modelling workflow was highlighted due to the strict physical requirements. Within this context, it was addressed that the standard error metrics are not sufficient to discern between models and the corresponding predictive accuracy. Therefore, an improved validation routine is proposed, which includes (i) the usual statistical metrics, (ii) tests on unseen data from virtual experiments based on different heterogeneous mechanical specimens, (iii) external KPIs, such as the reconstructed axial force ratio and (iv) single-element FEA tests.

In order to test the effects of different physics-based constraints, and bring into practice the improved validation methodology, four RNN-based models were trained with labelled data to predict the stress tensor based on strain sequences. In general, the results have shown that the addition of constraints improved the models' predictive capacity and extrapolation power as well as faster training times. Moreover, the constrained models also showed improved numerical accuracy and stability when incorporated into a numerical solver. In this context, the SPD-RNN architecture offers an advantage as the model outputs the tangent stiffness matrix directly, bypassing the need to derive it. The formulation acts as a hard constraint and resulted in more accurate and time-consistent solutions when compared to the baseline and the Wp-RNN model with the plastic power constraint. Some constraints were not tested due to time restrictions, however, the corresponding formulation as a penalty terms is still provided in the paper.

The proposed validation methodology not only allowed to effectively evaluate the trained models' performance in a wide range of cases beyond the training domain, but also to deeply analyse the physical consistency of the trained models, especially through the RAFR KPI and the numerical one-element tests.

4.2 Author contributions

The author made significant contributions across multiple domains in this work, having played a key role on conceptualizing the study, designing the test methodology, implementing software tools in Python to automate model training and validation, as well as KPI calculations. The author also played a key role in the investigation process, including data analysis, result validation, and the creation of figures and charts. In addition to drafting the original manuscript, the author actively participated in revising and refining it based on feedback from the co-authors.

Chapter 5

Data-driven constitutive modelling with indirect training

The paper presented in Chapter 4 provided new insights about the training and validation workflows and effectively proved that the standard error metrics are too shallow to evaluate the models. With the findings previously gathered it is clear which direction should be taken, both in terms of model architecture and physics-based constraints when trying to train the RNN with unlabelled data, from scratch.

In this Chapter, the methodology introduced in Chapter 3 is revisited. A new RNN architecture is employed, using residual connections for improved gradient flow. The modelling workflow is also improved with the knowledge gained from Chapter 4, through the application of physics-based constraints during training and employing the new validation routine, based on external KPI and different heterogeneous tests. The RNN is coupled with the VFM and trained with unlabelled data from scratch, without relying on transfer learning. An extensive hyperparameter tuning is performed to optimize a set of hyperparameters and a sensitivity analysis is conducted to determine the influence of the number and quality of the virtual fields on the predictive accuracy training dynamics.

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5.1 Data-driven elastoplastic constitutive modelling with physics-informed RNNs using the Virtual Fields Method for indirect training

The increasing demand for accurate material behaviour data in engineering simulations has exposed the limitations of traditional constitutive models. Although recent advances in full-field measurement techniques provide more detailed material char-

acterization, conventional approaches still heavily rely on explicit assumptions and labour-intensive experimentation. This paper revisits the indirect training methodology introduced by the authors [111], which integrates Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) with Gated-Recurrent Units (GRUs) and the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) to model material behaviour without labelled data. The earlier study demonstrated the feasibility of training a GRU-based RNN using only global force and strain data through the VFM. Building on those findings, this work presents a more robust approach featuring an improved network architecture, with residual connections to enhance gradient flow and training stability, while also incorporating physics-based constraints. Extensive hyperparameter tuning was conducted to optimize the model and a sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the impact of the virtual fields on the accuracy and training dynamics. The models were validated using additional heterogeneous mechanical tests and the Reconstructed Axial Force Ratio (RAFR), as a key performance indicator, to further assess the physical correctness. The results show enhanced predictive accuracy and improved force reconstruction when larger sets of virtual fields are employed. Additionally, normalizing the VFM loss contributed to more consistent predictions and force reconstruction across all time stages. Stress contour plots further confirm the model's ability to accurately predict stress distributions, which are in good agreement with the reference, with low median and average absolute errors.

5.1.1 Introduction

The widespread adoption of numerical simulation software in the engineering field has increased the need for precise material behaviour data [1,2]. In Finite Element Analysis (FEA) software, the material behaviour is implemented in a constitutive model. Conventionally, these models are derived from physical knowledge and phenomenological observations. However, the behaviour observed in simple one-strain-state mechanical tests is often generalized [86,87]. Moreover, the resulting constitutive equations contain empirical parameters that need to be calibrated [87].

In the past, the calibration process was limited to homogeneous deformation data due to the lack of high-resolution measurement equipment and restrictions to the specimens' geometries. As such, complex models often required an extensive number of experiments, making the whole process expensive and time-consuming [3]. In recent years, those limitations were overcome with the introduction of Digital Image Correlation (DIC) techniques, allowing the extraction of heterogeneous multi-axial displacement fields at numerous measurement points. Such capabilities unlocked the development of new mechanical specimens able to generate material behaviour data with higher levels of heterogeneity (e.g. [5–8], among others), and opening the door to the so-called Material Testing 2.0 (MT2.0) paradigm [4]. DIC also enabled more sophisticated approaches for the inverse identification of constitutive parameters, such as the Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) [88] and the Virtual Fields Method (VFM) [69]. Despite these advancements, constitutive parameter identification remains difficult and very model-dependent. Moreover, the phenomenological nature of the conventional constitutive models means their explicit form is fundamentally biased due to the simplifying assumptions of first-order principles [10]. Therefore, these models will always be constrained by their mathematical formulations.

The unprecedented growth recently experienced in the various domains of Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) has led to the growing adoption of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) across a wide variety of fields. Within the field of material modelling ANNs can potentially lead to a paradigm shift in the sense that they do not require any assumptions about an explicit form, effectively eliminating the need for parameter identification [13,14]. Furthermore, ANNs can handle the high volumes of data obtained from full-field measurements and are able to learn patterns implicitly, thus mitigating the biases inherent to conventional constitutive laws [10]. ANN-based constitutive modelling was first explored by Ghaboussi et al. [43], who demonstrated promising results with a Feed-Forward Neural Network (FFNN) trained to capture the cyclic behaviour of concrete. An early application to metal behaviour is attributed to Furukawa and Yagawa [25], who extended the concept to viscoplasticity using a state-space representation. Notable foundational works also include the implementation of an ANN material into a FEA solver [28] and the introduction of an analytical tangent stiffness matrix for ANN-based material models [89].

Plasticity is hard to model with ANNs due to history-dependent phenomena. Simple architectures are unable to capture them, as there is no mechanism that relates the inputs in the current time step with the outputs from previous time steps [56,91]. In earlier applications, the issue was somewhat circumvented by supplying stress and strain tensors from previous time steps, with additional internal variables of the constitutive model, as input features to a FFNN to predict the material response [25,109,110]. The approach resulted in added complexity and the reliance on internal variables meant resorting to assumptions about the explicit form of the constitutive law. Moreover, internal variables exist purely in a numerical sense, have no physical meaning, and are not accessible in a real experiment. Further advancements in computational resources, allowed the development of more sophisticated network architectures, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). Contrary to FFNNs, RNNs are particularly robust for implicit constitutive modelling due to built-in memory cells that capture the effects of path-dependent behaviour [90]. Using sequences of strain tensors spanning from a number of time stages in the past up to the current time stage t , a RNN can capture the temporal dependencies, allowing to predict the corresponding stress state accurately. Such capabilities had resulted in a variety of works reported in the field [54–56,91,93,111–113].

Most works reported on ANN-based constitutive modelling follow a supervised learning paradigm that relies on labelled data pairs, usually strain and stress. However, the latter is not measurable in experiments based on complex heterogeneous mechanical specimens. Even from simple uni-axial homogeneous tests, stress is obtained from indirect calculations and assumptions, such as theoretical boundary conditions. In a context where real experimental data is used to train the ANN model, the training process must be carried out indirectly. This reality imposes that the training dataset must contain measurable variables only, such as displacements and/or strains and global force. During training, the variable to predict is indirectly obtained from intermediate calculations.

Within the framework of indirect training a few contributions have been found in the literature. Xu et al. [60] proposed predicting the Cholesky factors of the tangent stiffness, with the stress tensor being computed from intermediate steps. The model provided numerically stable solutions, albeit only for to the non-linear segment of the material

response. Both Huang et al. [64] and Xu et al. [65] proposed to replace the constitutive model in a FEA solver by an ANN, and imposed physical constraints during training. Similarly, Liu et al. [67] proposed a coupled mechanical system through the integration of an ANN with FEA. These approaches are analogous to FEMU and, while the physical correctness of the ANN solutions is guaranteed, the drawbacks are (i) the need to write a FEA code based on an automatic differentiation package (e.g., Pytorch or TensorFlow), making the finite element step time-consuming; (ii) multiple FEA simulations have to be run per epoch, making the training computationally demanding. In the domain of hyperelasticity, Huang et al. [64] showed that an ANN could be made thermodynamically consistent by predicting the hyperelastic energy instead of the stress tensor, which was computed via automatic differentiation. In an earlier work, Man and Furukawa [26] also used an energy-based loss function to indirectly train an ANN. Thakolkaran et al. [86] opted for an ensemble of Input Convex Neural Networks (ICNNs) to learn the constitutive response of a set of well-known hyperelastic constitutive models, resorting only to full-field data. Still in the framework of hyperelasticity, in a recent work by Jeong et al. [100], an ensemble of four independent Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) was employed to extract the material behaviour from full-field data, with physical constraints being encoded within a multi-objective loss. Despite promising results shown from the last two approaches, training multiple ANN models concurrently makes the process harder, computationally demanding and adds complexity to model selection tasks (e.g. hyperparameter tuning). On another recent work in the domain of hyperplasticity, Franke et al. [101] employed an advanced energy-momentum scheme for time discretization to improve the performance of a Physics-Augmented Neural Network (PANN) in dynamical simulations, ensuring energy and momentum conservation. The authors reported excellent results, however it is not clear their approach is applicable to real experimental data. Finally, notable contributions by Flaschel et al. were aimed at the unsupervised discovery of the explicit form of the yield surface of a certain category of materials [102] and its extension to a general class of materials [103]. These approaches ensure physically consistent solutions, however, the authors still resort to several assumptions about the existence of internal history variables and the explicit formulations of the models.

In a previous paper, the authors proposed an innovative indirect training methodology which involved coupling the VFM with a GRU-based RNN model for material modelling [111]. The method allows using the global force and strain data to indirectly train the neural network, with the equilibrium being evaluated globally through the VFM loss function. The key advantages highlighted by the authors were (i) the computational efficiency gained from bypassing the use of FEA, (ii) the compatibility with both full-field measurements and numerically generated data and (iii) the independence of the boundary conditions. The possibility of using the VFM to train an ANN was then proven to be feasible through transfer learning. In the current paper, the authors revisit the proposed indirect training method, (i) employing a new RNN model, with a more robust architecture, (ii) trained from scratch using user-defined virtual fields and (iii) a mixture of soft and hard constraints based on general constitutive requirements. A more streamlined validation procedure is also adopted, based on different heterogeneous mechanical specimens, an external key performance indicator (KPI) and one-element tests obtained with the implementation of the trained RNN model in a FEA solver.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 5.1.2 introduces the theoretical background related to general elastoplastic behaviour and provides an overview of the requirements for constitutive equations that were implemented as constraints for ANN training. In Section 5.1.3, the VFM is introduced as well as its theoretical background. The coupled RNN-VFM indirect training methodology is also presented. In Section 5.1.4, RNNs with gated recurrent units (GRUs) are introduced along with the corresponding mathematical background. The chosen network architecture, as well as the data generation, training and validation procedures, are detailed in Section 5.1.5. Finally, in Section 4.1.6, results from hyperparameter tuning are presented, as well as, the influence of different virtual fields on the training dynamics is explored. The results obtained with the best model on validation data and the corresponding FEA implementation are also discussed.

5.1.2 Material modelling

Elastoplasticity

The classical constitutive laws governing elastoplasticity feature a transition between elastic and plastic regimes. A material undergoes elastic deformation until the initial yield stress σ_0 is reached, beyond which irreversible plastic deformation takes place along with hardening phenomena. The transition is governed by a yield function:

$$f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, p) \leq 0, \quad (5.1)$$

which depends on the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and the accumulated plastic strain p . Under plasticity, the stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ remains on the yield surface ($f = 0$) due to the hardening parameters, while $f \leq 0$ under elastic deformation. Hence, the strain can be assumed to be additively decomposed as follows [33]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p. \quad (5.2)$$

The hypoelastic constitutive relation maps the elastic strain to the stress through the tangent stiffness tensor \mathbf{C} as [108]:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e. \quad (5.3)$$

The plastic flow follows the normality condition [28,32]:

$$d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^p = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}, \quad (5.4)$$

forcing the increment in the plastic strain to occur in the normal direction to the tangent of the yield surface at the load point [31]. The plastic multiplier $d\lambda$ is derived from the hardening rule after employing the consistency condition $f = df = 0$ [32]. The constitutive relation from Eq. 5.3 can then be rewritten in the general form [60]:

$$\dot{\sigma} = \mathbf{H}\dot{\epsilon} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{C}\dot{\epsilon} & \text{for } f < 0 \\ \left[\mathbf{C} - \frac{\left(\mathbf{C}\frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma}\right)\left(\mathbf{C}\frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma}\right)^T}{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma}\right)^T\left(\mathbf{C}\frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma}\right)} \right] \dot{\epsilon} & \text{for } f = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (5.5)$$

where \mathbf{H} is a general tangent stiffness tensor that degenerates into the elastic tangent stiffness \mathbf{C} under elasticity.

Requirements for constitutive equations

Laws of thermodynamics

The laws of thermodynamics impose two constraints on stress-strain relationships. The first law requires that the work done by stress must either be stored as recoverable internal energy in the solid or dissipated as heat [108]. As such, a local entropy generation, or intrinsic dissipation in the material is defined, such that:

$$\gamma_{\text{loc}} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} + \theta \dot{\eta} + \dot{E}, \quad (5.6)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ the strain rate tensor, θ the absolute temperature, η the entropy per unit volume and E the internal energy per unit volume. The second law of thermodynamics requires that, if a sample of material is subjected to a cycle of deformation, starting and ending with identical strain and internal energy, the total work must be positive or zero, such that [2, 108, 127]:

$$\gamma_{\text{loc}} \geq 0. \quad (5.7)$$

A requirement that stems from the second law of thermodynamics is that the plastic power must be non-negative, i.e. [115]:

$$\dot{w}^P = \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}^P \geq 0. \quad (5.8)$$

A negative plastic dissipation would imply a decrease in temperature as a result of inelastic deformation, which would be non-physical. From here, it naturally follows that the accumulated plastic work

$$w^P = \int_0^t \dot{w}^P dt, \quad (5.9)$$

should be non-decreasing [115]. The plastic power condition can be easily implemented as a penalty during ANN training to weakly impose the second law of thermodynamics.

Tangent stiffness symmetry

For a general orthotropic material the tangent stiffness \mathbf{C} is a symmetric fourth order tensor with 9 independent components. thus the general mapping between the elastic strain and stress may be expressed in matrix form as [33]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & & & \\ & C_{22} & C_{23} & & & \\ & & C_{33} & & & \\ & & & C_{44} & & \\ & & & \text{symm} & C_{55} & \\ & & & & & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{xx} \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \varepsilon_{zz} \\ 2\varepsilon_{yz} \\ 2\varepsilon_{xz} \\ 2\varepsilon_{xy} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.10)$$

The symmetries of \mathbf{C} ensure the physically correct state of stress is the one that maximizes the plastic dissipation for a given plastic strain rate [2]. Under plastic deformation, a general tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} may be considered as in Eq. 5.5, which remains symmetric. When strain hardening effects are present, \mathbf{H} is also positive definite, to ensure that the strain energy is positive and weakly convex [60, 129]. The latter is also a sufficient condition for the uniqueness of the elastoplastic boundary value problem [60]. The condition also guarantees time-consistent solutions.

In the context of ANN training, the symmetry condition could be applied either as a loss penalty, forcing the equality between the matrix components, or as a hard constraint. For the latter, Jekel et al. [129] proposed a transformation layer, without learnable parameters, to map a vector input to a symmetric positive definite matrix. The transformation is based on the Cholesky factorization of a real symmetric matrix \mathbf{C} , expressed as:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}^T, \quad (5.11)$$

where \mathbf{L} is a real-valued lower triangular matrix, defined as:

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{11} & & & & & \\ L_{21} & L_{22} & & & & \\ L_{31} & L_{32} & L_{33} & & & \\ & & & L_{44} & & \\ & & & & L_{55} & \\ & & & & & L_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.12)$$

with the diagonal elements kept positive, to force the output matrix to be symmetric positive definite. The positiveness of the diagonal elements can be enforced with a suitable activation function (e.g. ReLU). Xu et al. [60], on the other hand, weakly impose the symmetric positive definiteness of the tangent stiffness by obtaining \mathbf{L} directly through the ANN output.

Stress triaxiality

The stress triaxiality represents the distribution of stress in the three orthotropic axes and is defined as [136]:

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{\sigma_h}{\sigma_{vM}} \quad \text{with} \quad \sigma_h = \text{tr}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}), \quad (5.13)$$

where σ_h the hydrostatic stress and σ_{vM} the von Mises equivalent stress. A negative value of triaxiality, indicates a compressive stress state, while a positive value corresponds to a tensile state. The ranges of stress triaxiality for each state are a requirement for a constitutive model and are specified as follows: $-\infty \leq \mathcal{T} \leq +\infty$, for a general 3D stress state and $-2/3 \leq \mathcal{T} \leq 2/3$ for a 2D plane stress state.

Lode angle parameter

The Lode angle θ , or the Lode parameter L , relates the third invariant J_3 of the deviatoric stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\sigma}'$ with the von Mises equivalent stress σ_{vM} , such that [130,136]:

$$L = -\cos(3\theta) = -\frac{27}{2} \frac{J_3}{\sigma_{vM}^3} \text{ with } J_3 = \det(\boldsymbol{\sigma}'). \quad (5.14)$$

The Lode angle θ can be normalized as follows:

$$\bar{\theta} = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \arccos\left(\frac{J_3}{\sigma_{vM}^3}\right). \quad (5.15)$$

The Lode angle range is $0 \leq \theta \leq 1$, while the Lode parameter range is $-1 \leq L \leq 1$.

5.1.3 The Virtual Fields Method

Theoretical development

The Virtual Fields Method (VFM) is a state-of-the-art technique used in the inverse identification of constitutive parameters [38]. A key advantage of the VFM is that it does not resort to the Finite Element Method (FEM), resulting in increased computational efficiency [3]. Moreover, it also avoids having to model the boundary conditions and the specimen's geometry [68,96]. The VFM is based on the Principle of Virtual Work (PVW) represented, in the absence of body forces, by the equilibrium [69,97]:

$$-\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dV + \int_{\partial V} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* dS = 0, \quad (5.16)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*$ is the virtual strain, \mathbf{u}^* is the virtual displacement, V is the volume of the solid, \mathbf{T} is the vector of loading tractions and S is the surface with applied tractions. The virtual displacements are mathematical functions independent of the measured displacements. The equilibrium from Eq. 5.16 holds for any virtual displacement \mathbf{u}^* as long as it is continuous, piece-wise differentiable over the specimen's body and kinematically admissible, in order to satisfy the displacement boundary conditions. The virtual strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^*$ are derived from the virtual displacements \mathbf{u}^* by taking the gradient of the displacements, that is [69]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* = \frac{1}{2} \left(\nabla \mathbf{u}^* + \nabla \mathbf{u}^{*\top} \right). \quad (5.17)$$

Besides the referred requirements, there are no specific rules for the choice of virtual fields. Nevertheless, it is convenient to find expressions such that the virtual displacement \mathbf{u}^* would be constant along the boundary of prescribed displacements [68, 69]. This is due to the fact that the traction distribution is often unknown and only the resultant force \mathbf{F} is available from the load cell, allowing to simplify the calculation of the external virtual work $\mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^*$, as follows [9]:

$$\mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^* = \mathbf{u}^* \int_{\partial S} \mathbf{T} dS \approx \mathbf{u}^* \cdot \mathbf{F}. \quad (5.18)$$

Given that full-field measurements are only available at the surface of the specimen, an assumption for the through-thickness behaviour of the material is necessary [96]. Thin specimens are often employed in mechanical testing, as such it is common to assume a plane stress state, resulting modification of Eq. 5.16, for a specimen with thickness h [68]:

$$-h \int_S \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^* dS + h \int_{\partial S} \mathbf{T} \cdot \mathbf{u}^* dL = 0, \quad (5.19)$$

where S and ∂S are, respectively, the surface and the boundary of the specimen. In full-field measurements, the displacements are captured using DIC techniques in a large number points or subsets, as such, the integral in Equation 5.19 can be approximated as a discrete sum for any time stage t . Assuming a suitable set of virtual fields is used, the identification process is carried out by minimizing a loss function with respect to the constitutive parameters \mathbf{x} defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_t} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{VF}}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{pts}}} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^j(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{*j(i)} \cdot S^j - \mathbf{W}_{\text{ext}}^* \right)^2, \quad (5.20)$$

where S^j is the area of the j -th element and N_{VF} , N_t , N_{pts} are the number of virtual fields, time stages and measurement points, respectively. Although any kinematically admissible virtual fields could be used, their choice is a key step of the VFM with great impact in the final solution. The virtual fields are often user-defined, nonetheless, systematic procedures are available to automatically define them, namely: the stiffness-based and the sensitivity-based virtual fields [68]. It is important to refer that the User-Defined Virtual Fields (UDVFs) are tied to the user's own expertise and intuition and do not evolve in time.

Coupled RNN-VFM indirect training

In the current work, the authors revisit the indirect training methodology presented in a previous paper [111]. The method consists on coupling the VFM to indirectly train a GRU-based RNN model (Figure 5.1) in order to learn the unified elastoplastic response a material. During training, the strains, obtained from the spatial gradient of the measured displacements, are fed as inputs to the RNN material model \mathcal{M} which predicts the stress components. Then, the equilibrium can be evaluated globally by means of the PVW. The network's parameters are searched until the gap between the internal and the external components of the virtual work is minimized.

Figure 5.1: Coupled RNN-VFM indirect training method for implicit constitutive modelling, using sensitivity-based virtual fields [111].

5.1.4 GRU-based RNNs

In plasticity, the path-dependency phenomena cause an interdependency between past and present states, hence the material behaviour is time-dependent [90]. This characteristic is challenging to model with basic ANN architectures, without a mechanism to relate the inputs in the current time step with the outputs from previous time steps [56, 91]. Indeed, material behaviour modelling can be laid out as a time-series problem, the ideal use-case for RNNs, which allow to maintain a memory of previous inputs through the use of cyclic connections (see Figure 5.2b) [92]. Using sequences of strain tensors, spanning a number of time stages into the past, a RNN is able to capture the temporal dependencies and predict the corresponding stress tensor accurately.

In the current paper, RNNs based on Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) are employed. A basic GRU cell is composed of the following key components: an update gate, a reset gate, a new gate and the final state (see Fig. 5.2a). The update gate (\mathbf{z}_t) determines how much of the previous hidden state is to be retained and how much it should be updated with new information and is defined by the mapping:

$$\mathbf{z}_t = \text{sig}(\mathbf{W}_{xz}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xz} + \mathbf{W}_{hz}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hz}). \quad (5.21)$$

Analogously, the reset gate (\mathbf{r}_t) is defined such that:

$$\mathbf{r}_t = \text{sig}(\mathbf{W}_{xr}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xr} + \mathbf{W}_{hr}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hr}), \quad (5.22)$$

and specifies which information from the previous hidden state should be forgotten. The new gate (\mathbf{n}_t) computes a new candidate hidden state based on the input and previous hidden state, such that:

$$\mathbf{n}_t = \tanh(\mathbf{W}_{xn}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xn} + \mathbf{r}_t \odot [\mathbf{W}_{hn}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hn}]). \quad (5.23)$$

Finally, the final state (\mathbf{h}_t) combines the previous hidden state and the new memory content, controlled by the update gate, through the following:

$$\mathbf{h}_t = (1 - \mathbf{z}_t) \odot \mathbf{n}_t + \mathbf{z}_t \odot \mathbf{h}_{t-1}. \quad (5.24)$$

The variables \mathbf{h}_t and \mathbf{x}_t are, respectively, the hidden state and the input at time t , while $\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}$ is the hidden state at time $t - 1$, or the initial hidden state at $t = 0$. The entities sig and tanh are, respectively, the sigmoid and the hyperbolic tangent activation functions and the operator \odot is the element-wise product. The weight matrices \mathbf{W} and bias vectors \mathbf{b} are appended with double indices identifying the mapping between the different components of the GRU cell. A deeper description of these mathematical entities and their corresponding dimensions, in the context of the present work, is provided in Table 5.1 [111]. The hidden state \mathbf{h} is the key element behind the flow of information relating previous time steps and future predictions. In a way analogous to the internal variables of classical constitutive laws, \mathbf{h} carries the information about the current plastic state of the material [93,111].

Figure 5.2: Schematic representation of (a) a standard GRU cell and (b) an unrolled recurrent neural network.

Table 5.1: Mathematical entities, and corresponding dimensions for a GRU-based RNN where n is the batch size, k the sequence length, n_{cells} the number of GRU cells, s_{in} the input size, s_{out} the output size and s_{hid} the hidden size.

Component	Entity	Dimensions	Description
Input	\mathbf{x}_t	$(n \times k \times s_{\text{in}})$	Strain sequences
Previous state	\mathbf{h}_{t-1}	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time $t - 1$
Final state	\mathbf{h}_t	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time t
Output	$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_t$	$(n \times s_{\text{out}})$	Stress tensor at time t
Update gate	$\mathbf{W}_{x(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{in}})$ $(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input to hidden weights of 1st GRU cell Input to hidden weights of i -th GRU cell
Reset gate or New gate	$\mathbf{b}_{x(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input to hidden bias
$(\mathbf{z}_t \mathbf{r}_t \mathbf{n}_t)$	$\mathbf{W}_{h(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden to hidden weights
	$\mathbf{b}_{h(z r n)}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden to hidden bias

5.1.5 Materials and methods

RNN architecture

The RNN architecture chosen for this work is depicted in Fig. 5.3 and an overview of the corresponding constituent modules is provided in Table 5.2. The input consists of strain sequences with length $k = 4$, which are first processed by two GRU cells. The information is then forwarded through the three fully-connected (FC) layers. The network predicts the material tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} by the inclusion of a SPD layer, as proposed by Jekel et al. [129] (see Section 5.1.2), albeit adapted here to an isotropic material under plane stress. A dropout layer features between the GRU modules with a probability $p = 0.1$, i.e. at each iteration 10% of the connections are randomly deactivated in order to prevent overfitting by discouraging individual neurons from relying too much on other specific neurons [137]. Residual connections are added to the outputs of layers FC2 and FC3, allowing the temporal information encoded by the GRU modules to be “remembered” at those points on the forward pass. These connections greatly improve the gradient flow during backpropagation and help stabilize the training process [138]. The residuals are scaled by a learnable parameter θ_i to prevent them from overwhelming the outputs of the FC layers. The residuals with unmatched dimensions are passed through a linear layer in order to ensure dimensional compatibility during the addition. The sigmoid-weighted linear unit (SiLU), a smooth approximation of the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), was chosen as activation function. For more details on the SiLU, the reader is invited to refer to 5.1.7.

Figure 5.3: GRU-based RNN architecture for material modelling. Sequences of length $k = 4$ of the scaled strain tensor $\varepsilon' = [\varepsilon'_{xx} \quad \varepsilon'_{yy} \quad \varepsilon'_{xy}]$ are mapped to the material tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} due to the inclusion of a SPD layer. The green blocks depict linear fully-connected (FC) layers. Residual connections are drawn with solid black lines, while the dash dotted pattern depicts residuals transformed to ensure dimensional compatibility. Residual connections are weighted by a learnable parameter θ_i .

Table 5.2: Overview of the constituent models of the GRU-based architecture adopted in this work, and corresponding number of hidden units and trainable parameters.

Module	Hidden units	Trainable parameters
GRU	2	9888
FC1	32	1056
FC2	32	1056
FC3	6	198
Residual 1	N/A	1
Residual 2	6	193
SPD	6	N/A

Training database

Here, synthetic data was used to simulate experimental DIC data in order to have a reference in the overall process. Therefore, the training dataset was built from multiple virtual experiments of a heterogeneous biaxial test. For a general cruciform specimen under biaxial loading, like the one depicted in Fig. 5.4a, the region of interest (ROI) corresponds to one fourth of the central zone. Hence, symmetry boundary conditions are defined at the left ($x = 0$) and bottom ($y = 0$) edges and displacements prescribed at each arm of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 5.4c. The virtual experiments were generated with displacements of different magnitudes (in mm), being prescribed in paired combinations (u_x, u_y) from the set:

$$(u_x, u_y) \in \{0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0\}. \quad (5.25)$$

The virtual experiments were carried out with Abaqus Standard software [139], assuming plane stress and small strains. The material behaviour was considered isotropic, with the flow stress evolving according to the Swift's law:

$$\sigma_Y = K(\varepsilon_0 + \bar{\varepsilon}^P)^n \quad \text{with} \quad \varepsilon_0 = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{K}\right)^{1/n}, \quad (5.26)$$

where σ_Y is the flow stress, $\bar{\varepsilon}^P$ the equivalent plastic strain, σ_0 the initial yield stress, K and n are material-specific hardening parameters. The constitutive parameters are listed in Table 5.3.

The geometry was discretized using CPS4R elements with an average size of 0.52 mm, resulting in a total of 2121 elements. Similar refinement levels have been cited in the literature for this specimen ([9, 104], among others). Reduced integration elements were chosen to simulate DIC subsets from full-field measurements, thus, the field output variables were extracted at the centroids of the elements. For each time stage, strain and stress tensors were extracted at all the measurement points and the force applied at specimen's arms was computed from the equilibrium of the internal forces through the following:

$$Fl = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i A_i h, \quad (5.27)$$

where F is the global force, l the length of the specimen, n is the number of elements, A is the area of the element and h the thickness.

Table 5.3: Constitutive parameters for the soft steel material.

E [GPa]	ν	σ_0 [MPa]	K [MPa]	n
210	0.33	160	565	0.26

The whole dataset contained a total of 36 virtual experiments. The data was shuffled and split in half, such that one part was used for training and the remaining part for validation. The training set was then split such that 70% of the virtual experiments were used for training and the remaining 30% for testing. The full training domain is shown on the scatter plot from Figure 5.5. Prior to training, the input data was scaled to have zero mean and unit variance, as follows:

$$\varepsilon' = \frac{\varepsilon - \boldsymbol{\mu}}{\mathbf{s}}, \quad (5.28)$$

where ε' is the scaled strain tensor, $\boldsymbol{\mu} = [\mu_{\varepsilon_{xx}} \ \mu_{\varepsilon_{yy}} \ \mu_{\varepsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of mean values and $\mathbf{s} = [s_{\varepsilon_{xx}} \ s_{\varepsilon_{yy}} \ s_{\varepsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of variances of the strain tensor components, respectively. The statistical variables $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and \mathbf{s} were saved for later usage. For each virtual experiment, the inputs have dimensions $[n_{\text{pts}} \times n_t \times k \times 3]$, where n_{pts} is the number of measurement points, i.e. the number of elements, n_t is the number of time stages, k the sequence length and the last dimension the number of strain components.

Figure 5.4: Biaxial test virtual experiment: (a) selected region of interest, (b) specimen's geometry and (c) applied boundary conditions.

Figure 5.5: Principal strain and normalized yield locus diagrams for the complete set of virtual experiments used for training, taken from the material points at all the time stages.

Training procedure

The RNN model was developed using PyTorch library, following the indirect training methodology described in Section 5.1.3 without labelled data.

The user-defined virtual fields considered for training are mathematically defined in Table 5.4. For each virtual field, the variables W and H are the width and height of the specimen, respectively, while X and Y are the material coordinates in the reference frame. The resulting virtual displacement and virtual strain contour maps are shown in Section 5.1.7. The best combination of virtual fields was determined by a sensitivity analysis.

Training was performed with the Adam optimizer with weight decay factor 10^{-3} . A linear warm-up scheduler was configured to increase the learning rate from an initial value of 10^{-5} up to a maximum learning rate η_{\max} within the first 10 epochs, followed by a gradual decay according to a cosine annealing scheduler, defined as [106, 107]:

$$\eta_t = \eta_{\min} + \frac{1}{2}(\eta_{\max} - \eta_{\min}) \left(1 + \cos \left(\frac{T_{\text{cur}}}{T_{\text{max}}} \pi \right) \right), \quad (5.29)$$

where η_t is the current learning rate, η_{\min} is the minimum learning rate, T_{cur} and T_{max} are the current iteration and the maximum number of iterations, respectively. The minimum learning rate η_{\min} was set to 10^{-5} . For each epoch, the order of the virtual experiments was shuffled, as well as the corresponding inputs along the time dimension. Mini-batch training was employed due to GPU memory restrictions. Therefore, considering that each experiment has a variable number of time stages, the batch size $N_{t,b}$ was defined taking the floor division of the total number of time stages N_t by an integer $d_{\text{batch}} \in \{2, 4, 8, 16, 32\}$. An early-stopping criterion was implemented to prevent overfitting and interrupt the training if the test loss did not improve after 350 epochs. In RNNs, gradients can grow exponentially during backpropagation through layers, or time steps, becoming excessively large (exploding gradients). This leads to unstable training dynamics that can make the network fail to learn effectively, as weight updates become too large to converge to a stable solution [57]. To prevent the gradients from exploding, clipping

was employed, based on the L2 norm of the gradients, through a clipping parameter c_{norm} .

The loss function was based on the VFM loss from Eq. 5.20, adapted to mini-batch training, such that:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{N_{t,b} \cdot N_{\text{VF}}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{VF}}} \left(\mathbf{W}_{\text{int},k}^{*(i)} - \mathbf{W}_{\text{ext},k}^{*(i)} \right)^2, \quad (5.30)$$

where $N_{t,b}$ is the number of time stages per batch. The physics-based constraints used in this work were the plastic power condition, the stress triaxiality and the lode parameter, added as penalty terms to the VFM loss, resulting in a multi-objective loss with the general form:

$$\mathcal{L}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \varepsilon) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i \mathcal{L}_i, \quad (5.31)$$

where the constants λ_i are scaling factors used to balance the loss terms, \mathcal{L}_i is the i -th objective loss to minimize and k is the total number of conflicting objectives. The implementation for each penalty is presented in Table 5.5. The inequalities were imposed through the ReLU6 function, which is a modified version of the ReLU, where the activation is limited to a maximum size of 6 [140]. The preference was due to improved training stability. The loss balancing terms λ_i were automatically computed during training, based on the Relative Loss Balancing with Random Lookback (ReLoBRaLo) algorithm, introduced by Bischof and Kraus (2021) [131]. The algorithm adapts the terms λ_i based on a moving average and a random lookback mechanism, at each iteration, as follows:

$$\lambda_i^j = \alpha \left(\beta \lambda_i^{j-1} + (1 - \beta) \hat{\lambda}_i^{j:0} \right) + (1 - \alpha) \hat{\lambda}_i^{j:j-1}, \quad (5.32)$$

where λ_i^j is the scaling for the i -th loss term at iteration j , α is the moving average parameter and β a Bernoulli random variable with a value close to 1. The term $\hat{\lambda}_i^{j:j'}$ is responsible for computing the scalings based on the relative improvements of each loss between iterations j and j' , such that:

$$\hat{\lambda}_i^{j:j'} = k \cdot \frac{\exp \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i^j}{\tau \mathcal{L}_i^{j'} + \epsilon} - \max \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i^j}{\mathcal{L}_i^{j'}} \right) \right)}{\sum_{m=1}^k \exp \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_m^j}{\tau \mathcal{L}_m^{j'} + \epsilon} - \max \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_m^j}{\mathcal{L}_m^{j'}} \right) \right)}, \quad (5.33)$$

with k being the total number of loss terms, \mathcal{L}_i^j and $\mathcal{L}_i^{j'}$ the values of the i -th loss term at iterations j and j' , respectively; τ is a hyperparameter that controls the amplitude of the scalings and ϵ a small number. The parameter α controls the weight given to past scalings in relation to the scalings from the current iteration, while β allows the model to occasionally look back until the start of training.

A hyperparameter tuning was performed in order to select the best combination of parameters α, β, τ , along with the maximum learning rate η_{\max} , the mini-batch size and the gradient norm clipping value c_{norm} .

During training, additional metrics were logged to provide a better insight into the training dynamics. Namely, the predictive accuracy was monitored through the error between the predicted stress $\hat{\sigma}$ and reference stress σ , such that:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\sigma} = \frac{1}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} (\hat{\sigma} - \sigma)^2, \quad (5.34)$$

along with the error of the resulting approximation of the global force, given as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\mathbf{F}} = \frac{1}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} (\hat{\mathbf{F}} - \mathbf{F})^2, \quad (5.35)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{F}}$ is the global force obtained by taking the integration of the stress, as in Eq. 5.27. It is important to note that these metrics were logged solely for information purposes, during the test loop, and were not used for training.

Validation database

From the data generation phase, 18 virtual experiments based on the cruciform specimen were kept separate for the validation set. This set of experiments had different prescribed displacements than the ones used for training. From this set, a virtual experiment with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm was chosen for further analysis.

Three additional heterogeneous mechanical specimens, documented in the literature for constitutive model calibration, have also been considered for validation purposes, each of which exhibiting increasing levels of geometric complexity within the respective regions of interest (ROI): the S specimen [132], the Sigma specimen [133] and the D specimen [134]. An uniaxial external load along the y -direction is normally applied to each specimen. The complex shapes induce multiaxial heterogeneous stress states, despite the loading being uniaxial. For the purpose of the present work, a displacement u_y is prescribed at the top-surface of each specimen with magnitude 2.0 mm for the D specimen and 1.5 mm for the S and Sigma specimens. The corresponding geometries, principal strain distributions, yield locus and equivalent plastic strain field, when using a classical constitutive model, are illustrated in detail in Figures 5.6 and 5.7, respectively.

Validation procedure

Error statistics

Model performance was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE), a standard benchmark metric in ML to assess the accuracy of predictive models. A lower RMSE indicates higher accuracy. RMSE quantifies the average magnitude of errors between the predicted and observed values as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{\sigma} - \sigma)^2}, \quad (5.36)$$

Table 5.4: Full set of possible user-defined virtual fields considered for training.

Virtual fields	u_x^*	u_y^*
$\mathbf{u}^{*(1)}$	$\frac{X}{W}$	0
$\mathbf{u}^{*(2)}$	0	$\frac{Y}{H}$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(3)}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(4)}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\cos\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$	$\cos\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(5)}$	$\frac{X}{W}$	$\cos\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\cos\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(6)}$	$\cos\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)\cos\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$	$\frac{Y}{H}$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(7)}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\sqrt[3]{\frac{Y}{H}}$	$\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)\sqrt[3]{\frac{X}{W}}$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(8)}$	$\sin\left(\frac{X}{W}\pi\right)$	0
$\mathbf{u}^{*(9)}$	0	$\sin\left(\frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(10)}$	$\sin\left(8.5 \cdot \frac{X}{W}\pi\right)$	0
$\mathbf{u}^{*(11)}$	0	$\sin\left(8.5 \cdot \frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(12)}$	$\sin\left(8.5 \cdot \frac{X}{W}\pi\right)$	$\sin\left(8.5 \cdot \frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)$
$\mathbf{u}^{*(13)}$	$\sin\left(3 \cdot \frac{X}{W}\pi\right)\cos\left(3 \cdot \frac{Y}{H}\pi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)$	0
$\mathbf{u}^{*(14)}$	0	$\sin\left(3 \cdot \frac{Y}{H}\pi\right)\cos\left(3 \cdot \frac{X}{W}\pi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right)$

Table 5.5: Penalty terms used for training, with k being the k -th sample and N_b the total samples per batch.

Penalty term	
Plastic power	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{WP}} = \frac{\lambda_2}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \text{ReLU6} \left(-\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{(k)} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{(k)}^{\text{P}} \right)^2$
Lode parameter	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Lode}} = \frac{\lambda_3}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \text{ReLU6} \left(- L_{(k)} + 1 \right)^2$
Stress triaxiality	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Triax}} = \frac{\lambda_4}{N_{t,b}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \text{ReLU6} \left(- \mathcal{T}_{(k)} + \frac{2}{3} \right)^2$

Figure 5.6: Geometric definition of the three heterogeneous mechanical specimens chosen for model validation: (a) S specimen, (b) Sigma specimen and (c) D specimen.

Figure 5.7: Major and minor strain distributions, normalized yield locus and equivalent plastic strain at the last time stage for (a) the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, (b) the S specimen (c) the Sigma specimen and (d) the D specimen. The grey colour highlights material points in the elastic regime. These values were retrieved using the von Mises model with isotropic hardening.

where $\hat{\sigma}$ is the predicted stress, σ the actual stress and N the number of observations. Additionally, the absolute error, i.e.:

$$\delta = |\hat{\sigma} - \sigma| \quad (5.37)$$

was used to compare the predicted stress fields and stress-strain curves with the reference FEA solution.

Validation KPI

The reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR), introduced by Peshave et al. [135], was also used to check the physical correctness of the RNN's predictions. The RAFR exploits the fact that, in uniaxial tensile tests, the load applied by the testing machine F_a is known. Moreover, the horizontal average of the stress multiplied by the cross-sectional area F_c^i should be equal to the applied load at any cross-section (see Fig. 5.8). For a given cross-section i , the reconstructed force F_c^i is computed by integrating the axial stress σ_{yy} , as follows:

$$F_c^i = \int_{S_c} \sigma_{yy} dS_c, \quad (5.38)$$

where S_c is the surface of that particular cross-section of the mechanical specimen. Assuming constant stress through the thickness, the surface integral reduces to:

$$F_c^i = h \int_{l_c} \sigma_{yy} dl_c, \quad (5.39)$$

where h is the specimen's thickness. Considering a regular grid of measurement points with sufficiently high spatial density, the line integral can be approximated as:

$$F_c^i = h S_t \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \sigma_{yy}^j, \quad (5.40)$$

where N_i is the number of evaluation points at the cross-section i and S_t is the step size. The RAFR is then computed as:

$$\text{RAFR} = \frac{F_c^i}{F_a}. \quad (5.41)$$

The metric is used to evaluate how well the section-averaged stress field matches the applied force at each cross-section. Any deviation from the ideal value of 1 indicates problems with the approximation of the stress field.

UMAT implementation

Another step taken to validate the trained RNN models involved incorporating them as material constitutive models in a FEA solver (here, Abaqus Standard) through a custom user material subroutine (UMAT). The code was developed in C++ and made use of the official C++ implementation of PyTorch (LibTorch). The architecture and data flow for the UMAT implementation are described in the flowchart of Figure 5.9.

Figure 5.8: Schematic of RAFR calculation. The force acting at the i -th cross-section is reconstructed by integrating the corresponding axial stress σ_{yy}^i along the cross-section length l_i and multiplying it by the thickness h .

Figure 5.9: Flowchart of the UMAT-RNN implementation.

5.1.6 Results

Hyperparameter tuning

Hyperparameter tuning was performed to select the optimal parameters α , β , τ of the ReLoBRaLo algorithm, alongside with the maximum learning rate η_{\max} , the gradient norm clipping value c_{norm} and the batch size through the integer parameter d_{batch} . The base network architecture was the one shown in Fig. 5.3. The hyperparameter sweep functionality of platform Weights & Biases was used to manage the tuning process, monitor and log the results. The tuning relied on the Bayesian method combined with the hyperband algorithm to terminate underperforming runs. The Bayesian method uses a probabilistic model to choose the best parameter configurations to test, aiming to minimize a target metric [141]. The hyperband stopping algorithm evaluates if a run should stop or continue, at one or more predefined iterations, called brackets. When a run reaches a bracket, its objective metric is compared with all previously reported values. The run is terminated if the metric is too high. For the hyperparameter tuning of this work, each model was run using a subset composed of the virtual fields 1 through 9, during 150 epochs, and the mean squared error of the predicted stress \mathcal{L}_σ , as well as the corresponding approximation of the global force \mathcal{L}_F were logged during the test loop. Note that these metrics were not used for training, only for information purposes. The Bayes method was set to minimize \mathcal{L}_σ as an objective.

The universe of parameter values given to the program to be cycled through is shown in Table 5.6. The searching domain resulted in a total of 2160 runs to be launched with a unique hyperparameter combination. However, due to time constraints, the sweep agent was configured to launch a maximum number of 150 runs, 113 of which ended up being terminated by the hyperband algorithm. The resulting metric \mathcal{L}_σ for the remaining 37 runs is presented in the scatter plot of Fig. 5.10. The learning curves for the 5 models highlighted by the black solid line can be closely inspected in Fig. 5.11 and the corresponding training stats are compiled in Table 5.7. The models are identified by the letters A to E, respecting their order of appearance and colour code in the scatter plot. The corresponding sets of hyperparameters are also shown in Table 5.6, with the best combination found on the tuning session marked in boldface.

Results show that the best run corresponds to model E with a metric \mathcal{L}_σ as low as 206.462 MPa². Additionally, the learning curves show that model E not only exhibit the most stable training dynamics, but also achieved the lowest VFM training loss. Worthy of note is the fact that Model A achieved similar values for the VFM loss, for both training and testing, however the stress error was one order of magnitude higher. In contrast, the remaining models show higher VFM losses but lower stress error. These observations allow to conclude that the hyperparameter combination corresponding to model E is the best, not only achieving the lowest error but also allowing the stress error and the force approximation to correlate well with the minimization of the VFM losses. All the following analyses were performed using the hyperparameter combination selected here as the best.

Table 5.6: Searching domain for the hyperparameter tuning and hyperparameters for the five highlighted models. The best combination of hyperparameters is marked in boldface.

Parameter	Searching domain	A	B	C	D	E
α	{0.9, 0.99, 0.999}	0.99	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.999
β	{0.9, 0.99, 0.999}	0.99	0.9	0.999	0.99	0.999
τ	{10, 1, 0.001, 0.0001}	0.001	0.001	10	0.001	1
η_{\max}	{0.01, 0.005, 0.001}	0.01	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
c_{norm}	{1, 2, 5, 10}	1	5	5	5	10
d_{batch}	{2, 4, 8, 16, 32}	32	4	8	8	16

Figure 5.10: Resulting \mathcal{L}_σ metric for the non-interrupted runs, the line marks the runs with lower metric.

Table 5.7: Training stats for the five models under analysis.

	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VFM}}^{\text{train}}$ [J ²]	$\mathcal{L}_{\text{VFM}}^{\text{test}}$ [J ²]	\mathcal{L}_σ [MPa ²]	\mathcal{L}_F [N ²]
Model A	2743.325	2255.196	2239.393	3139.855
Model B	22010.424	22695.210	436.148	39152.723
Model C	5291.868	5490.525	338.928	9150.831
Model D	6419.348	4824.316	291.314	8017.327
Model E	2098.595	2340.699	206.462	2734.911

Figure 5.11: Learning curves of the five models selected from the hyperparameter tuning: (a) VFM train loss, (b) VFM test loss, (c) loss of the stress prediction and (d) loss of the approximation of the global force.

Sensitivity analysis to the virtual fields

Discretization error

When calculating the equilibrium based on the PVW, theoretically, each virtual field should yield an exact balance between the external and virtual works. Nonetheless, some discrepancies may occur due to, e.g., mesh discretization or background noise. The virtual fields shown in Table 5.4 were mathematically defined to ensure compatibility with the boundary conditions. The kinematic admissibility can be confirmed upon inspecting the corresponding contour maps shown in Figs. 5.24 and 5.25 from Section 5.1.7, where it can be seen that every virtual field is zero at the edges with symmetry boundary conditions and either zero or constant at the edges with applied tractions. However, it is critical to know the underlying error related to mesh discretization, which is independent of the constitutive model.

In Fig. 5.12 the curves for the internal and external virtual works, corresponding to each virtual field, are shown. The data was obtained for the virtual experiment based on the cruciform specimen, with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, and calculated based on the reference field outputs extracted from Abaqus software. The curves show, in general, a good match between the internal and external virtual work for virtual fields that activate the components of the global force, although slight deviations emerge towards later time stages, particularly for the virtual fields 10, 11 and 12. For the virtual fields that do not activate the external work (i.e. 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 13 and 14), the internal virtual work starts to increasingly deviates from the external work curve over time, to an extent that depends on the virtual field.

Given that the kinematic admissibility is ensured and these are results obtained from virtual experiments without experimental noise, these discrepancies are likely due to mesh discretization. The use of reduced integration elements to simulate DIC subsets may have led to a mesh that is too coarse to capture local variations in strain or stress within certain regions of the specimen, causing imbalances in the virtual work calculations.

Number of virtual fields

In theory, the higher the number of virtual fields the more accurate should be the stress reconstruction through the VFM. However, certain combinations of virtual fields may introduce undesirable effects when coupling the VFM with neural network training. Moreover, due to computational constraints and the manual method of introducing the virtual fields, their selection must be made correctly. As such, an analysis was conducted in order to determine the effects of the choice of virtual fields on both the training dynamics and predictive accuracy of the RNN model. For the purpose, various models were fully trained using the optimal combination of hyperparameters identified from the hyperparameter tuning (i.e. Model E - see Section 5.1.6) and different subsets of virtual fields. The model using the virtual fields 1 through 9 was taken as baseline. Each model was given a name and its correspondence with a given subset of virtual fields, as well as the resulting RMSE on the validation set after training, are shown in Table 5.8.

Analysing the results from Table 5.8, the RMSE metrics clearly show that the number of virtual fields has a significant impact on the predictive accuracy of the RNN. It is

Figure 5.12: Comparison between the internal and external virtual work, for the whole set of virtual fields, along the time stages of the virtual experiment based on the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm.

Table 5.8: Model naming and subsets of virtual fields used for training. RMSE metrics on the validation set with virtual experiments based on the cruciform specimen. The baseline model is shown in boldface, and enclosed in parentheses is the percentage gain or loss in the RMSE relative to the baseline.

Model	Virtual fields	RMSE validation [MPa]			
		Min.	Mean	Median	Max.
4VF	{1-4}	24.881 (+87.8%)	32.804 (+84.4%)	32.361 (+101.1%)	41.399 (+65.6%)
6VF	{1-6}	23.766 (+79.4%)	30.288 (+70.3%)	29.586 (+83.8%)	36.894 (+47.6%)
7VF	{1-7}	15.791 (+19.2%)	18.691 (+5%)	18.217 (+13.2%)	22.294 (-10.7%)
9VF	{1-9}	13.242	17.785	16.089	24.993
10VF	{1-9,12}	12.903 (-2.62%)	13.955 (-21.5%)	13.711 (-14.7%)	15.333 (-38.65%)
11VF _a	{1-11}	12.892 (-2.64%)	13.979 (-21.4%)	13.842 (-13.9%)	15.325 (-38.68)
11VF _b	{1-9,13,14}	10.747 (-18.8%)	11.778 (-33.7%)	11.604 (-27.8%)	13.076 (-47.68%)
12VF	{1-9,12,13,14}	10.537 (-20.4%)	11.810 (-33.5%)	11.498 (-28.5%)	13.644 (-45.4%)

seen that any given model trained with larger sets of virtual fields than the baseline, shows substantial improvements. Models 11VF_b and 12VF both achieve similar RMSE and the highest percent error reduction. Models 10VF and 11VF_a have similar RMSE, confirming that there is no substantial difference when opting between the pair of virtual fields 10,11 or the virtual field 12. The latter is component-wise identical to the former, however it has both components of the external force simultaneously active. Regarding the models trained with smaller sets of virtual fields, the 7VF registers an RMSE closer to the baseline and shows significant improvements upon 4VF and 6VF, solely due to the inclusion of virtual field number 7. It is also noticeable that not only the number but also the type of virtual fields influence the final predictive accuracy. Observing the results in more detail and keeping in mind the formulations of Table 5.4, it can be seen that introducing virtual fields that do not activate the external component of the virtual work (i.e. 7, 13, 14), seems to result in significant improvements, as seen by the relative differences in RMSE obtained by the 7VF model, compared to the baseline, and the 11VF_b compared to the 11VF_a model. In the latter models, the positive effect was due to the introduction of virtual fields 13 and 14, while removing the virtual fields 10 and 11 (which activate the external component of the load).

Extending the analysis on these error metrics to different heterogeneous mechanical specimens, the box plots from Fig. 5.13 show the component-wise RMSE of the stress tensor obtained with each model. The plots further highlight the general downward trend of error with increasingly larger sets of virtual fields. The error dispersion as well as the magnitude of the outliers is also significantly lower for larger sets.

Looking in detail into each mechanical specimen, the cruciform test shows similar error tendencies for both stresses in the x - and y -directions, with higher errors being registered for the shear component. Here, the RMSE is seen registering large dispersion and outliers for smaller sets of virtual fields, which could be due to the fact that the strain space provided by the cruciform specimen is not very rich in shear states. However, the issue seems to be mitigated with larger sets of virtual fields. Regarding the D specimen, it is interesting to verify that the median errors are, in general, lower than those seen

for the cruciform specimen. Given that the strain space provided by the D specimen contains states that fall outside the training domain, this shows that the models were capable of retaining good extrapolation capacity. The S specimen shows similar error metrics to the cruciform except for the stress coincident with the loading direction, exhibiting higher error dispersion and outliers using smaller sets of virtual fields. For the Sigma specimen, overall low median errors are registered, however there seems to be no significant influence coming from the number of virtual fields.

Regarding training dynamics, for the sake of visual clarity, four most distinctive models were selected from Table 5.8 to be analysed, namely: 9VF (baseline), 4F, 7VF and 12VF. The corresponding learning curves and evolution of the physics-based constraints logged during training are shown in Figs. 5.14 and 5.15, respectively. Focusing on the train and test losses (Figs. 5.14a and 5.14b), the curves show a healthy “L” shape exhibiting a sharp decrease at the starting epochs that smoothly evolves into a more gradual slope. This is an indicator of good training stability considering that the training progressed without labelled data and the VFM loss had to be adapted to the context of ANN training. None of the curves seem to achieve total convergence because all of them still show signs of downward trend at the triggering points of early-stopping. The training lasted longer for the baseline model, 9VF, lasting 2661 epochs and allowing it to achieve the lowest value of loss, 202.034 J², followed by 7VF (263.552 J²), 4VF (359.820 J²) and 12VF (898.356 J²). There seems to be no significant overfitting, except for the 4F and 12VF models, with the latter showing a large increase on the test error, causing the early-stopping to trigger at an earlier point in training, at epoch 897. Interestingly, the 7VF model stopped relatively close to that point, epoch 1194, however resulting in a much lower loss. Looking at the MSE of approximation of the global force (Fig. 5.14d), there seems to be a tight correlation with the test loss given the similarities in both magnitude and behaviour. Analysing the MSE for the predicted stresses (Fig. 5.14c), the curves follow a very different dynamic, decreasing sharply at the starting epochs with a slight undershoot and evolving into what could be considered a plateau. The curves show that, the predictive error improves with larger subsets of virtual fields with the best performer being the 12VF model with an MSE as low as 105.048 MPa² at the early-stopping point, followed, in descending order, by the 9VF (277.658 MPa²), 7VF (303.585 MPa²) and 4VF (1012.424 MPa²).

Concerning the curves of the physics-based constraints, for the plastic power (Fig. 5.15a) all the models register similar dynamic with a sharp increasing at the starting epochs with a slight overshoot smoothly evolving into a plateau, albeit at different magnitudes for each model. The lowest value corresponds to the 4VF model, while the remaining models stabilize into nearly identical values. The lode parameter curves (Fig. 5.15b) register the inverse dynamic, however all the models seem to stabilize at nearly the same values.

Effect of loss normalization in the force reconstruction

In this section, the models’ predictive accuracy is further assessed by evaluating the quality of the force reconstruction through the RAFR KPI. In a first stage, the analysis is focused on the results obtained by the four models selected in the previous section.

The corresponding RAFR plots obtained for the three heterogeneous uniaxial tests are shown in Fig. 5.16. In general, the results show that larger sets of virtual fields

Figure 5.13: Component-wise RMSE of the stress tensor for the models trained with different subsets of virtual fields corresponding to the virtual experiments based on (a) the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, (b) the D specimen, (c) the S specimen and (d) the Sigma specimen.

Figure 5.14: Learning curves for four models trained with different subsets of virtual fields: (a) VFM train loss, (b) VFM test loss, (c) MSE for the stress prediction and (d) MSE of the corresponding approximation of the global force.

Figure 5.15: Loss curves the physics-based penalty terms for three models trained with different subsets of virtual fields: (a) plastic power, (b) lode parameter and (c) triaxiality factor.

provide a more accurate force reconstruction. For both the D and S specimens, the 4VF model shows significant scatter along the time stages while the remaining models present smoother curves, well within the error margin of $\pm 10\%$, only with slight deviations in specific areas. However, all the models struggle to obtain an accurate force reconstruction for the Sigma specimen, exhibiting significant scatter across the entire length of the specimen. Nevertheless, the deviations are of lower magnitude for models trained with larger sets of virtual fields. In general, all the models fail to achieve an accurate force reconstruction at the initial time stages for all the specimens. This is due to the fact that the magnitude of the internal virtual work evolves with the time stages. Naturally, in an experiment the earlier a time stage the lower the corresponding internal virtual work, due to lower stresses, and vice-versa. For that reason, it is common to normalize the VFM loss, forcing the different loss terms to lie within similar range, thus avoiding some terms having more importance than others. In the VFM, the loss function from Eq. 5.20 can be normalized, such that:

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{N_{t,b} \cdot N_{VF}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{t,b}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{VF}} \frac{\left(\mathbf{W}_{int,k}^{*(i)} - \mathbf{W}_{ext,k}^{*(i)} \right)^2}{\max_k \mathbf{W}_{int,k}^{*(i)}}, \quad (5.42)$$

where the denominator is a vector containing the maximum values of the virtual work for each virtual field. To evaluate the effect of this modification, the four previously selected models were re-trained using the modified loss from the equation above. The corresponding RMSE metrics on the validation set and RAFR plots are shown in Table 5.9 and Figure 5.17, respectively.

Table 5.9: RMSE metrics on the validation set with the virtual experiments based on the cruciform specimen, obtained by the selected models re-trained with the normalized version of the VFM loss. Enclosed in parentheses are the percentage gain or loss in RMSE, relative to the homologous with the denormalized loss.

Model	RMSE validation [MPa]			
	Min.	Mean	Median	Max.
LN-4VF	27.506 (+10.5%)	37.072 (+13.0%)	36.664 (+13.2%)	47.575 (+14.9%)
LN-7VF	12.275 (-22.2%)	15.675 (-16.1%)	14.696 (-19.3%)	19.913 (-10.6%)
LN-9VF	10.449 (-21.0%)	14.236 (-19.9%)	14.065 (-12.5%)	18.935 (-24.2%)
LN-12VF	8.649 (-17.9%)	10.273 (-13.0%)	9.804 (-15.1%)	12.583 (-7.7%)

Analysing the results from Table 5.9, it is clear that normalizing the VFM loss has a positive impact on the final predictive accuracy, with all the models showing substantial error reductions across the board, compared to the homologous versions from Table 5.8. In contradiction with the overall trend, the LN-4VF model registered a deterioration in its final accuracy. Regarding the RAFR plots, it can be seen that with the VFM loss normalization all the models achieved a correct force reconstruction at the initial time stages, for all the specimens, independently of the number of virtual fields. In general, the LN-4VF model starts to deteriorate in performance with significant scatter in later stages, while the remaining models achieve smoother curves, albeit with

some deviations still present. These results are in line with the conclusions taken from Figure 5.16 at the beginning of this section. Nonetheless, the normalization seems cause a slight degradation in the RAFR on the plastic stages, particularly for the D and Sigma specimens, with the latter showing the same kind of results as previously discussed.

Figure 5.16: RAFR along the length (in mm) of the three heterogeneous uniaxial specimens for the selected models. The ideal value is denoted by the dashed horizontal line, and the grey area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$. For the S specimen, the vertical dashed lines indicate the location of each notch root.

Figure 5.17: RAFR along the length (in mm) of the heterogeneous uniaxial specimens, for the models trained with the normalized VFM loss. The ideal value is denoted by a dashed line, and the grey area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$. For the S specimen, the vertical dashed lines indicate the location of each notch root.

Stress reconstruction

In this section, the best performing model, LN-12VF trained with the normalized VFM loss, was selected to evaluate the quality of the corresponding stress reconstruction on different mechanical specimens.

Mechanical test with cruciform specimen

The virtual experiment based on the cruciform specimen, with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, was chosen as an example from the validation dataset. The contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 124$) of the virtual experiment are shown in Fig. 5.18. It can be seen that the LN-12VF model approximates the FEA solution quite well, exhibiting low absolute errors across the specimen, for all the stress components. In general, the highest error magnitudes correspond to key regions around the fillets near the central hole and on one of the sides of the arms of the specimen. On the latter regions, the white blobs indicate a tendency to substantially underestimate the stress, particularly for on the x - and y - directions. Along the circumference of the central hole, there are small areas denoted by black blobs that indicate a slight overestimation happening for all the stress components. Although this specimen is not rich in shear information, surprisingly, the model performs the best when predicting the shear stress, exhibiting the lowest absolute errors for that component. For the stresses along the x - and y - directions the model shows very similar performance.

Mechanical test with D specimen

The contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 143$) of the virtual experiment based on the D specimen are shown in Fig. 5.19. This specimen was not part of the training data and is considered to be the more complex, however, the results indicate the LN-12VF is able to predict the stress fields in good agreement with the FEA solution, capturing the major features and symmetries of the stress fields. The results show, in general, low mean and median absolute errors across the entire ROI for all the stress components. Particularly for the stress in the x -direction and the shear stress, the model exhibits a slight tendency to overestimate their magnitudes on specific zones along the left circular edge of the ROI, which show more subtle gradients on the reference solution. The model seems to struggle when evaluating the stress tensor on a key area near the lower region of the small interior notch, resulting in the highest absolute errors. There is a notable underestimation of the stress in the y -direction on left circular edge of the specimen, evidenced by the white blob over that region. Once again, the model performs the best when predicting the shear stress, as shown by the lower absolute errors for this component.

Mechanical test with S specimen

The contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 121$) of the virtual experiment based on the S specimen are shown in Fig. 5.20. This specimen was also not included in the training dataset. The results indicate the LN-12VF is able to predict stress fields that closely match the FEA solution, perfectly capturing the main features of the stress fields. The error maps show low mean and median absolute errors

Figure 5.18: Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_t = 124$ of the virtual experiment, based on the cruciform specimen, with boundary conditions $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm. Comparison between the FEA solution and the LN-12VF model predictions with corresponding absolute difference

Figure 5.19: Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_t = 143$ of the virtual experiment based on the D specimen. Comparison between the FEA solution and the LN-12VF model predictions with corresponding absolute difference

across the entire ROI, for all the stress components, and lower maximum absolute errors compared to the D specimen, which could be attributed to the lower complexity of the S specimen. For the stresses along x - and y -directions, there is a tendency to slightly underestimate the stress in a small region near the root of both notches, which is the area of maximum absolute error. In contrast, for the shear stress, the model tends to overestimate the stress on that region of the ROI.

Figure 5.20: Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_t = 121$ of the virtual experiment based on the S specimen. Comparison between the FEA solution and the LN-12VF model predictions with corresponding absolute difference

Mechanical test with Sigma specimen

The contour maps of the stress components for the last time stage ($n_t = 121$) of the virtual experiment based on the Sigma specimen are shown in Fig. 5.21. This specimen was also not part of the training data. The results show that the LN-12VF predicts stress fields in good agreement with the FEA solution, capturing the main features of each stress field and the major symmetries, particularly for the shear component. In general, the results show low mean and median absolute errors across the entire ROI,

for all the stress components. The model struggles to predict the stresses on the regions around the central zone of the specimen, with stress being underestimated in areas with lower magnitudes and overestimated in the areas of higher magnitude. The effect is particularly visible on the shear stress. The maximum absolute errors also originate from these specific regions. The component x -direction seems to be affected to a lesser extent, showing the lowest absolute errors across the board.

Figure 5.21: Contour maps of the three components of stress for stage $n_t = 121$ of the virtual experiment based on the Sigma specimen. Comparison between the FEA solution and the LN-12VF model predictions with corresponding absolute difference

One-element tests

The uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves obtained for the one-element tests performed with the UMAT implementation of the LN-12VF model and the corresponding absolute error along the time stages are shown in Fig. 5.22, respectively. The curves are compared with the FEA solution and with the RNNs' inference predictions.

The results show that, in general, the model performs better for both rolling (RD) and transverse (TD) directions, with nearly identical predictions both for inference and its

UMAT implementation. The elastic portion for the three stress curves is captured quite well, however, both versions of the model fail to provide accurate predictions for the plastic stages due to plastic yielding. Here, the models' responses diverge significantly from the reference curve on the shear test, resulting on the highest errors being around 125 MPa, approximately. Nonetheless, for both RD and TD the deviation from the reference is less pronounced with the highest errors being approximately around 30 MPa. Despite the results, the simulations were stable due to the model providing the symmetric positive definite tangent stiffness. The similar responses between both versions of the model indicate that there are no issues with the UMAT implementation.

Figure 5.22: Uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves. Comparison between the FEA solution based on the Swift's law (Eq. 5.26) and the UMAT implementation of the LN-12VF model.

5.1.7 Appendices

Sigmoid-weighted linear units

The Sigmoid-weighted linear unit (SiLU) is smooth, approximately equal to the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) for large activations z_k and approximately zero for large negative activations (see Fig. 5.23a). Unlike the ReLU function, the SiLU is differentiable at $z_k = 0$ and admits a global minimum (-0.28 at $z_k \approx 1.28$). The latter acts as a “soft floor” for the weights and introduces a regularizing effect avoiding learning weights with large magnitudes. The first derivative of the SiLU (dSiLU) has a shape similar to the sigmoid (see Fig. 5.23b), albeit steeper and with some overshoot [142].

Figure 5.23: Plots for the (a) SiLU and ReLU activation functions and (b) the corresponding derivatives dSiLU, dReLU, compared to the Sigmoid activation.

User-defined virtual fields

Figure 5.24: Contour plots of virtual displacements considered for training - part I.

Figure 5.25: Contour plots of the virtual displacements considered for training - part II.

Figure 5.26: Virtual strains corresponding to the full set of virtual displacements considered for training.

5.2 Final remarks

The current paper capitalized on the findings of the previous two papers of the authors to train a GRU-based RNN with the VFM from scratch, without labelled data. A new and improved neural network architecture was adopted, employing residual connections to improve the gradient flow and stabilize the training dynamic. A hyperparameter tuning allowed to optimize the model even further by identifying the best combination of a select set of hyperparameters.

In general, the learning curves show stable training dynamics for all the models, even though the training was performed without labelled data, relying only on the VFM loss and the physics-based constraints. The test loss curves indicated a slight tendency to overfit when specific sets of virtual fields were used. A sensitivity analysis has shown that the predictive accuracy is highly correlated with the number of virtual fields, with the models trained with larger sets of virtual fields achieving lower RMSE metric on the validation set. The same also applies to the force reconstruction, with the RAFR plots showing that models trained with seven or more virtual fields were able to achieve a more accurate correct reconstruction, except for the initial (elastic) time stages. However, this issue was addressed with a proper VFM loss normalization, which has shown to improve the accuracy of force reconstruction, for all the models, across all the time stages.

The stress contour plots show predictions in good agreement with the reference solution, with residual median and average absolute errors. Nevertheless, in very specific zones of the specimens, the models seem to over- or under-predict the stresses resulting in high maximum errors being registered on those areas. Further validation studies were conducted with one-element tests, taking into consideration the incorporation of the best-performing model into a FEA solver. In this context, the model shows very similar results for both inference and the UMAT version, confirming an accurate implementation without any issues. In general the elastic response is captured quite well, however the model fails, in general, to provide accurate plastic yield response, particularly on the shear test with the model response being highly spurious. Despite these results, the stress predictions for both the RD and TD are closer to the reference curve.

These findings show that the VFM is effectively deemed feasible for neural network training. More importantly, this indirect training methodology using unlabelled data is proven to provide robust results, on par with labelled training approaches. Nonetheless, the results show that there is margin for further improvement. For example, using the ReLU function instead of the ReLU6 would allow for the penalty terms to have stronger effect, which could result in improved final accuracy. However, the ReLU being unbounded caused the training to be unstable. The universe of training data could also be enhanced with the introduction of data from a specimen richer in shear states and/or data from classical homogeneous tests such as tensile, shear or bulge tests.

Within the context of validation, the RAFR provided invaluable insights during model selection and allowed to identify a key area of improvement, thus the authors highlight once again the importance of using external KPIs on the validation workflow.

5.3 Author contributions

The author made significant contributions across multiple domains in this work, having played a key role on conceptualizing the study, designing the test methodology, implementing software tools in Python to automate model training and validation, as well as hyperparameter tuning and KPI calculations. The author also played a key role in the investigation process, including data analysis, result validation, and the creation of figures and charts. In addition to drafting the original manuscript, the author actively participated in revising and refining it based on feedback from the co-authors.

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Chapter 6

Conclusions and perspectives

6.1 Conclusions

This thesis has pioneered a novel approach to constitutive modeling by coupling RNNs with the VFM, addressing critical challenges in data-driven material characterization. By moving away from the limitations of traditional phenomenological models, this work represents a significant advance in the field, towards more accurate, efficient and scalable models.

In Chapter 2, an overview on the application of ML techniques to constitutive modelling for metal forming processes was presented. The literature review has shown that ANNs possess unique advantages in capturing complex material behaviour from data. Unlike traditional models that rely on explicit formulations and parameter identification, ANNs can leverage the large datasets from full-field measurements to learn material responses without predefined equations. However, some challenges remain in achieving physically consistent predictions using ML-based models, particularly in low-data regimes, pointing to the need for physics-based constraints to ensure reliable predictions.

Chapter 3 introduces the core innovation of this thesis, a methodology that couples RNNs with the VFM for indirect training. This approach was shown to be computationally efficient and compatible with full-field measurements, enabling the use of displacement/strain and force data to indirectly train the RNNs. The key advantage here is the avoidance of explicit parameter identification, offering a more flexible and scalable method for capturing material behaviour. Validation tests demonstrated that this method can achieve performance levels comparable to conventional supervised learning approaches, while remaining computationally efficient and free from depending on FEA simulations during training.

In Chapter 4, the importance of incorporating physics-based constraints and external KPIs into the training and validation workflows was emphasized. Seven physics-based constraints were introduced to guide the neural network training, ensuring that the model outputs remained physically realistic and consistent with elastoplastic theory. The chapter also introduced a more robust validation methodology that goes beyond standard error metrics, incorporating heterogeneous mechanical tests and KPIs such as the Reconstructed Axial Force Ratio (RAFR). These validation steps were crucial for

evaluating the models' predictive accuracy and their generalization capacity to unseen data. The use of constraints had shown to significantly improve model performance, stability, and training efficiency.

Chapter 5 revisits the indirect training approach presented in Chapter 3, applying it to unlabelled data while coupling the VFM with GRU-based RNNs. The chapter focuses on a more robust model architecture, employing residual connections for better gradient flow and applying the insights gained from the use of physics-based constraints. The extensive hyperparameter tuning and sensitivity analysis performed here underscored the importance of selecting the right virtual fields for training. The results showed that this indirect training approach, can produce models that generalize well to unseen data and maintain physical consistency.

In summary, this thesis contributes a novel and scalable framework for data-driven constitutive modelling, capable of overcoming the limitations of traditional models. By integrating ML with the VFM and using physics-based constraints, this work delivers accurate, physically consistent models that are computationally efficient and well-suited for complex material behaviour in engineering applications. The enhanced validation approach ensures robust generalization, making this methodology highly relevant. This work lays a strong foundation for future research and developments in data-driven material modelling.

6.2 Perspectives for future work

The research presented in this thesis pioneered the integration of the VFM with neural network training and has advanced the understanding of data-driven constitutive modelling using unlabelled data, offering valuable contributions that promise to tackle key challenges on the field of material characterization. Nevertheless, new questions and opportunities arose that deserve to be further studied and the tools here developed constitute a solid base for future works. This section outlines several recommendations for future research, aiming to build upon the findings presented and push the boundaries of the field towards greater innovation and practical application. For further research the following recommendations are given:

1. Integration with sensitivity-based virtual fields

The applicability of the current framework has been demonstrated based on user-defined virtual fields. A natural extension would involve integrating the sensitivity-based virtual fields in the methodology, to achieve a more systematic way to define the virtual fields, and effectively exclude the user influence on their choice. By doing so, the final accuracy of the model could potentially be improved. Nevertheless, this implementation should be approached carefully, due to the fact that the virtual fields would be generated based on the parameter sensitivities of the model. In the case of phenomenological constitutive models, the approach makes perfect sense as there is a limited number of parameters to deal with and their influence on the output is well known. In the case of ANNs, however, this is not straightforward due to the multiple layers resulting in hundreds, at times thousands, of parameters, which of course raises issues related not only to interpretability, but also to the computational efficiency as there will be the need to calculate the sensitivity to each parameter. A possible approach to this problem

would be, e.g. to conduct a study in order to determine the most influential parameters and generate the virtual fields based only on that subset.

2. Extension to finite strains

Despite the ultimate goal being directed at material characterization for sheet metal forming, where large deformations take place, the methodology presented here was developed followed an infinitesimal strain framework. Given that most of the research done was highly exploratory, the choice made sense, as one of the primary goals was to prove how feasible would be to couple the VFM with an ANN for unlabelled training. Now, that the method's feasibility is proven, future efforts should focus on adapting the current methodology to a finite strain framework as this is the most commonly used in material characterization for sheet metal forming.

3. Refinement of training data

The training dataset based on the cruciform specimen proved robust enough for the analyses performed here, however it could be further refined. In future researches, one could explore the possibility of adding data from different mechanical specimens to enrich the existing strain space with shear information. With a richer strain space, the existing training database could also potentially be reduced. Using distinct mechanical specimens in the training dataset would entail switching between different sets of virtual fields during training, depending on the virtual experiment being evaluated. Nevertheless, this implementation should be straightforward and expected to provide improved predictive accuracy. The extension to other phenomena like anisotropy and viscoplasticity should also be considered.

4. Use of synthetic images

The current training database uses virtual experiments that simulate full-field measurements, however, the behaviour they replicate is purely numerical, and the data is used as-is. Future research should consider using synthetic images, which are artificially generated to simulate real-world experimental conditions. Essentially, experimental noise is introduced in the numerical data by a speckle pattern. The approach would allow understanding how robust the developed methodology is to real-world imperfections and what kinds of errors to expect under different conditions.

5. Long-term validation and real-world testing

While the analyses and simulations performed during this research provide strong evidence for the viability of the methodology presented here, long-term validation through real-world experiments remains a key area for future research. Testing the method under real-world conditions could provide essential feedback for refining the model and improve its practical utility, eventually leading to the method being fully integrated into the MT2.0 framework workflow.

6. Improve user-material subroutine

The developed user-material subroutine has plenty of room for improvement. The code should be made as dynamic and robust as possible for a seamless use when using ANN models with different architectures, different data scalings, etc.

Moreover, the conversion of the Python model into the JIT format to be used in the C++ environment would benefit from further automation. Other formats should also be explored, namely ONNX. The whole building environment is integrated with Abaqus Standard software within a Virtual Machine (VM), which albeit convenient is not the ideal. A possible improvement would be to containerize it via Docker with all the dependencies, ensuring it runs the same way regardless of the underlying environment. Docker containers are also lighter than VMs allowing for lower resource usage and the ability to run more containers on the same hardware.

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